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Deliverable 7: Final report of all meetings, consultations, webinars and workshops and the publication of a co-production guidebook for cities consisting of 2 guidebooks: 'A practical guide to using co-production for nature-based solutions' and 'A practical guide to using reflexive monitoring for nature-based solutions' (including infographics)

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Executive summary

This Deliverable presents our underlying conceptual and methodological approach as well as analytical results by which we have co-developed co-production and reflexive monitoring methodologies for the planning, delivery and stewardship of nature-based solutions on a large scale in cities. Next to supporting co-production and reflexive monitoring processes on the ground in the Connecting Nature Front-Runner and Fast-Follower Cities, a main aim was to generate systematic insights about how cities go about designing and implementing such novel governance approaches.

On the one hand, **co-production** is booming in cities worldwide as a mode of collaborative governance. By bringing together diverse actors – for example, civil servants, practitioners, social innovators, scientists, entrepreneurs and citizens – co-production can support the generation of transformative nature-based solutions (pertaining not only to their mere technical design but also to their financing, business models and social innovations) addressing local needs and mobilising local opportunities. We developed a comprehensive framework that supports the design, implementation and evaluation of co-production. The framework covers different types of co-production, methods, principles for process design and evaluation as well as capacities for co-production to implement the principles.

On the other hand, we developed a **reflexive monitoring** process to support processes of ongoing learning-by-doing and doing-by-learning. Nature-based solutions planning, delivery and stewardship requires ongoing reflection as well as adaptability to respond to new insights, demands and needs. Our reflexive monitoring methodology consists of a step-wise approach with several process tools that the cities have adapted into their regular activities to create space for reflection and capturing learnings. The recording of learning objectives and outcomes helped the cities structure what opportunities and barriers they have encountered and how they have navigated them, generating insights on critical steps and lessons learned for the design, delivery and stewardship of nature-based solutions.

Building on a comparative analysis of the cities, we generated several **key lessons** about how to adapt and implement co-production and reflexive monitoring:

- Overall, all cities recognised the value of co-production to engage with and empower diverse actors and reflexive monitoring to facilitate continuous learning and adaptation in real time when planning, delivering and stewarding nature-based solutions. In this way, co-production and reflexive monitoring are able to address the various governance needs for knowledge, partnerships, societal and political support and learning.
- Adopting new governance processes and tools that challenge conventional practices requires the creation of institutional and organisational space in cities and the acquisition of new skills and knowledge. It also requires new cultures within city governments to work across siloes.
- Co-production and reflexive monitoring are flexible approaches that need to be made fit to a specific city's contexts. For example, we could distinguish between various types of co-production processes depending on different goals and settings, including different types of actors and methods.
- Regarding co-production, it has been challenging to reach out and motivate diverse actors to participate in co-production, including especially vulnerable and low-income communities or specific actors from the business and finance community. This requires dedicated communication and community engagement efforts and skills as well as making the process accessible to different audiences.
- The value of reflexive monitoring extended to the facilitation of knowledge transfer and peer-to-peer learning between Front-Runner and Fast-Follower Cities. We learned that, from the idea initiation stage, it can take a few years before the cities started implementing their learning outcomes with reflexivity changes.

Based on our work with the cities and comparative analysis, we produced conceptually grounded and practice-proven, hands-on **guidebooks** that help urban practitioners and planners design and implement concrete steps, activities and tools for the co-production and reflexive monitoring of nature-based solutions. We have put in place several mechanisms to ensure the long-term sustainability of our co-production and reflexive monitoring work – in particular to continue to spread knowledge for example through the OPPLA platform and the UrbanByNature programme.

1 Introduction

While nature-based solutions harbour opportunities to deal with multiple urban challenges simultaneously, building resilience and creating healthier and just cities (Lafortezza et al. 2018; Connop et al. 2016), cities have to grapple with a number of governance challenges in their implementation. To realise their transformative potentials, nature-based solutions need to be embedded in their specific contexts: they need to reflect environmental conditions and needs, political, social and economic priorities, norms and values, human perceptions and institutional contexts characterising specific local neighbourhoods, the city as a whole and regional connectivity (Kabisch et al. 2017; Pauleit et al. 2017). This relates to a number of governance needs – that we also identified in our Connecting Nature cities – including the availability of knowledge about nature-based solutions as multifunctional solutions that is dispersed across multiple actors and institutions, sufficient and adequate skills, support and resources as well as new partnerships crossing sectoral and societal divides (Frantzeskaki et al. 2020; Hölscher et al. 2019a).

In Connecting Nature, we have developed the Connecting Nature Framework to provide a comprehensive perspective on what kind of innovations are required for the planning, delivery and stewardship of nature-based solutions on a large scale in cities, as well as on how and when to develop those innovations (Figure 1; Hölscher et al. 2019b; 2022). As part of the framework, we have developed the co-production and reflexive monitoring elements to help cities grapple with some of the underlying governance challenges, relating in particular to collaboration with diverse actors and learning-based decision-making and planning.

Figure 1: The Connecting Nature Framework

This Deliverable presents our underlying conceptual and methodological approach as well as analytical results by which we have co-developed co-production and reflexive monitoring methodologies for the planning, delivery and stewardship of nature-based solutions on a large scale in cities. Next to supporting co-production and reflexive monitoring processes on the ground, a main aim was to generate systematic insights about how cities go about designing, implementing, and learning such novel governance approaches. We were thus able to produce conceptually grounded and practice-proven, hands-on guidebooks that help urban practitioners and planners design and implement concrete steps, activities and tools for the co-production and reflexive monitoring of nature-based solutions (van der Have et al. 2022; Lodder et al. 2022).

On the one hand, **co-production** is booming in cities worldwide as a mode of collaborative governance (Box 1)¹. By bringing together diverse actors – for example, civil servants, practitioners, social innovators, scientists, entrepreneurs and citizens – co-production can support the generation of transformative nature-based solutions (pertaining not only to their mere technical design but also to their financing, business models and social innovations) addressing local needs and mobilising local opportunities (Frantzeskaki 2019; van der Jagt et al. 2019; Mees et al. 2018). In addition, the collaborative nature of co-production generates novel and shared problem framings and visions, spurs new relationships between actors (for example between local government and citizens, across city departments) and triggers the (re)definition of roles and responsibilities and empowerment of actors (Frantzeskaki and Kabisch, 2016; Hölscher et al.

¹ Co-production is a widely used concept and interpreted differently across different disciplines and practice (Nordström et al. 2020; Miller and Wyborn 2018). We draw on public administration and environmental governance literatures that refer to co-production as a mode of collaborative governance (Jaspers and Steen 2019; Brandsen et al. 2018). In Deliverable 4 (Hölscher et al. 2019a) we also explain the use of co-production instead of co-creation.

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2019c). There is the aspiration to develop and apply co-production not only for the design and delivery of nature-based solutions but also to engage in a continuous process with stakeholders at multiple scales and across sectors to contribute to post-implementation sustainability and long-term stewardship (Biggs et al. 2018).

We worked together with cities to co-develop and evaluate our co-production approach, as well as to translate concrete steps and lessons into the *Co-production for cities guidebook* (van der Have 2022). We hope that the guidebook will help address recurring challenges of co-production. So far, despite its promises, co-production is no ready-made and easy-to-implement governance approach, especially as most city governments are still unexperienced with it. Past experiences show that co-production, if not properly designed and implemented, can rather reinforce disinterest and participation fatigue, mutual frustration, limited representation, and power imbalances (Turnhout et al. 2019; Hölscher et al. 2019c; Brandsen et al. 2018; Muñoz-Erickson et al. 2017). We take a comprehensive framework that supports the design, implementation, and evaluation of co-production. As such, the framework covers different types of co-production, methods and tools, principles for process design and evaluation as well as capacities for co-production. The guidebook translates these into concrete, iterative steps for the design of co-production processes, including the evaluation of the outcomes and enabling conditions to be put in place for successful co-production. Building on a comparative analysis of the cities, the guidebook integrates insights about how the different Connecting Nature cities designed co-production processes in practice, what are different types of co-production processes, examples of best practice methods and lesson learned.

Box 1: Connecting Nature definition of co-production

Co-production is a collaborative governance process that actively involves diverse actors (e.g. citizens, policymakers, planners, entrepreneurs, scientists) from the beginning to plan, deliver, and steward new solutions to shared problems. Co-production can in principle be initiated by public servants, citizens or other actors; a central implication is that it shifts the roles of public servants from being service providers in an offer-oriented way and the roles of citizens from being solely the receivers of services towards all actors becoming service (co-) producers (Jaspers and Steen 2019; Brandsen and Honingh 2018).

Co-production focuses on outputs and outcomes in terms of improved delivery of public services that create value for the public. Outputs refer to the products, services or activities that are generated as part of the co-production effort, including the infrastructure for the nature-based solution itself as well as the services it provides (e.g. communal space, storm water retention facilities), but also underlying new definitions of problems and goals, new business models and forms of nature-based entrepreneurship. Outcomes generally refer to what difference is achieved in terms of more efficient, responsive, inclusive, etc, service delivery and real-world social, economic, and ecological improvements (Voorberg et al. 2014; Mattor et al. 2020; Biddle and Koontz 2014).

On the other hand, **reflexive monitoring** refers to a dynamic and learning-oriented governance method to facilitate, capture and assess processes of learning-by-doing and doing-by-learning with a focus on learning in situ and real time (Beers and van Mierlo 2017) (Box 2). Reflexive monitoring was developed as a comprehensive methodological approach in the context of complex and uncertain sustainability challenges, which require ongoing learning and adaptation of how progress towards sustainability is sought (Sol et al. 2017; van Mierlo et al. 2010a). Monitoring and assessment are introduced right at the beginning of a planning process, not retrospectively, to systematically link learning to implementation, facilitate flexible and adaptive responses as well as generate insights on critical steps and lessons learned. As such, reflexive monitoring can complement the co-production of nature-based solutions, which is an inherently open-ended and iterative process marking a departure from conventional urban governance and planning approaches that tend to start from clear problem definitions and objectives and only include evaluations at the end.

Box 2: The Connecting Nature definition of reflexive monitoring

Reflexive monitoring is a monitoring and evaluation method developed based on transition theory (Roorda et al. 2014) to navigate the complex and unpredictable nature of non-linear and multi-actor processes manifest in the development of transformative solutions. It supports urban planners and policymakers (but can also be used by e.g. citizens, entrepreneurs and scientists) to break through barriers, oversee the different actions and how they are related, and stay connected to the long-term goals of a project (Lodder et al. 2022).

Reflexivity is the ability to change and interact with the context in which one operates. A learning process is reflexive when participants are self-critical and reflect on the nature of how they build knowledge, including their own assumptions guiding them. This learning will change how lessons learned are applied to change existing or create new structures, strategies or practices, identifying needs for adaptation and ultimately how and what kind

of goals are achieved (Beers and van Mierlo 2017; Dentoni et al. 2016; Frantzeskaki et al. 2016). As thus, reflexive monitoring is about enhancing the ability to develop new ways of dealing with issues, which can also change the context of the transformative solutions.

Throughout the Connecting Nature project, reflexive monitoring has become a highly valued approach in and by itself, having fed directly into all activities of the project – not only related to co-production but to each element² of the Connecting Nature Framework and the knowledge transfer from Front-Runner to Fast-Follower Cities (Hölscher et al. 2022; Xidou et al. 2021). Regarding the latter, reflexive monitoring had a crucial role in the Knowledge Transfer – Phase 2 (Figure 2). Reflexive monitoring has been intended as an exploration of how expertise emerging in the Connecting Nature cities can be shared through peer-to-peer support, and how learning processes captured by reflexive monitoring can be continued for our Fast-Follower Cities and transitioned to a city-to-city process. Our reflexive monitoring methodology consists of a stepwise approach with several process tools that the cities have adapted into their regular activities to create space for reflection and record learnings. The recording of learning objectives and outcomes helped us structure what opportunities and barriers cities have encountered and how they have navigated them, generating insights on critical steps and lessons learned for the design, delivery, and stewardship of nature-based solutions. The *Practical guide to using reflexive monitoring for nature-based solutions* presents steps and tools of reflexive monitoring, examples of how the cities have adapted them as well as how to generate learning outcomes, assess the effects of reflexive mind-sets on scaling nature-based solutions as well as examples of the city’s learning experiences captured through the process (Lodder et al. 2022).

Figure 2: Knowledge Transfer – Phase 2, including the Reflexive Monitoring Platform, the Knowledge Hubs, and Networks.

In the following, Section 2 presents our method for developing the guidebooks for co-production and reflexive monitoring via an iterative co-production process between the scientific partners and the Front-Runner and Fast-Follower Cities, building on the previous work that was reported in Deliverable 4 (Hölscher et al. 2019a) and corresponding draft versions

² At the beginning of Connecting Nature and the development of the Framework the term ‘Building Blocks’ was used; this evolved to CN Framework Elements as the Framework evolved into its current form.

of the guidebooks (Frantzeskaki et al. 2019; Lodder et al. 2019). Section 3 and Section 4 present our results from our comparative analysis of co-production and reflexive monitoring of all ten Connecting Nature cities, respectively. This yields in-depth and practical insights and lessons on the practical implementation of both approaches and marks the foundation of the guidebooks. Section 5 includes final reflections on our approach as well as further steps for ensuring long-term sustainability of co-production and reflexive monitoring in the Connecting Nature cities and beyond.

This Deliverable is complemented by the two final guidebooks that have been conceived as methodological guidance based on the theoretical review and practical experiences and examples with co-production and reflexive monitoring that are presented here. The guidebooks speak to urban policymakers and urban planners, but also others who are interested in setting up co-production and reflexive monitoring processes.

2 Method

This section presents our methodological approach to co-develop and apply the approaches to co-production and reflexive monitoring together with the cities in Connecting Nature (Section 2.1), as well as to derive lessons learned for the guidebooks (Section 2.2) (Figure 3).

In general, our approach consisted of several iterative steps combining conceptual and analytical research work with the practical implementations, reflection and learning in the cities. After initial literature review and workshops with the Front-Runner Cities to co-develop our co-production and reflexive monitoring approaches – as presented in Deliverable 4 (Hölscher et al. 2019a) – we worked with the planners from the Connecting Nature Front-Runner and Fast-Follower Cities to introduce them to our co-production and reflexive monitoring approaches, co-designed a process to implement them into their projects and processes, and continuously coached and reflected with them throughout the planning, delivery, and stewardship of their nature-based solutions exemplars. In this way, we could gather extensive information in the form of notes, further advance our conceptual approach and generate comparative results about steps, methods, best practices, and lessons that were taken up in the guidebooks.

Figure 3: Co-production and reflexive monitoring work with the Connecting Nature cities to develop guidebooks

2.1 Working with the cities

We have worked with the cities in different interactive formats to co-develop their co-production and reflexive monitoring approaches, guide the implementation and the reflection thereof, and derive and discuss lessons learned. As has been

reported extensively in the preceding Deliverable 4 (Hölscher et al. 2019a), firstly we have worked with the three Front-Runner Cities – Genk (Belgium), Glasgow (United Kingdom) and Poznań (Poland). In this way, we could test and advance our conceptual approach and produce first drafts of the co-production and reflexive monitoring guidebooks. While we have continued to work with, coach, and learn from the Front-Runner Cities, from 2019 onwards we, together with the Front-Runner Cities, transferred the best practices and approaches to the seven Fast-Follower Cities – A Coruña (Spain), Burgas (Bulgaria), Ioannina (Greece), Málaga (Spain), Nicosia (Cyprus), Sarajevo (Bosnia) and Pavlos Melas (Greece). The experiences and lessons from these cities are also included in the final guidebooks.

Appendix C provides a complete overview of our activities with the cities per different interaction formats including the dates. These were the following:

- **Co-production workshops and webinars:** A series of co-production workshops and webinars were held throughout the course of Connecting Nature to introduce to the cities and co-develop with them the co-production method, collect best practices for co-production, facilitate exchange between the cities and discuss experiences and lessons learned.
- **Reflexive monitoring workshops and webinars:** A series of reflexive monitoring workshops and webinars were held throughout the course of Connecting Nature to introduce the cities to and co-develop with them the reflexive monitoring method, collect best practices, facilitate exchange between the cities, and discuss experiences and lessons learned.
- **Learning sessions Front-Runner Cities:** Since September 2018, we have held monthly reflexive learning sessions with each Front-Runner city individually that continued throughout the project (since September 2019 bi-monthly). In preparation of the sessions, the cities sent their Dynamic Learning Agenda and the participating experts (Connecting Nature Framework Element leads) prepared clarification questions. During these sessions, the cities presented the critical turning points they had encountered, resembling opportunities or barriers, learning objectives and follow-up actions to mobilise the opportunities or overcome the barriers. As of 2019, we co-analysed the learning outcomes with the cities by discussing the results of what they learned by changed rules, relations, practices and discourses. This has produced extensive materials about learning outcomes for each Connecting Nature Framework Element (see Deliverable 6, Hölscher et al. 2022). It also strengthened the cities' abilities to identify learning outcomes themselves, as well as their narratives about how they implement the Connecting Nature Framework and why they employ reflexive monitoring.
- **1-on-1 learning sessions Front-Runner Cities and Fast-Follower Cities:** We have realised together with WP4 three sets of 1-on-1 learning sessions between the Front-Runner Cities and the follower cities. The follower cities prepared a Dynamic Learning Agenda. This structured the call with the Front-Runner city and exchange of experiences and best practices of both Front-Runner and Fast-Follower city. The researchers (WP4 and WP2) made notes of these sessions without interfering. This has produced extensive materials about learning objectives and learning outcomes for each Connecting Nature Framework Element.
- **Learning Experience Webinars Front-Runner Cities:** We organised four webinars in which the analysed learning outcomes of the Front-Runner Cities were presented and discussed. This resulted in verified and clustered learning outcomes in terms of the dimensions of reflexivity and the Connecting Nature Framework Elements. The cities discussed selected learning outcomes to exchange their experiences and learning lessons. In the second part of webinars, we discussed specific steps and/or tools of the reflexive monitoring method to exchange experiences and lessons learned.
- **Learning Platform Webinars Fast-Follower Cities:** The four Learning Platform Webinars sought to facilitate further exchange between cities and Knowledge Hub experts on critical learnings about the Connecting Nature Framework Elements. Based on the notes from the one-on-one support sessions between the Front-Runner Cities and the Fast-Follower Cities, the learning objectives were clustered per Connecting Nature Framework Element. The Fast-Follower Cities looked at the learning objectives before the webinar and indicated when they recognised an objective of another city. The Connecting Nature Framework Element leads prioritised the learning outcomes to discuss with the cities during the webinar. This was used to align or adapt the guidance the cities received from the element leads. This resulted in a Miro board with the clustered learning objectives and notes of the break-out sessions per Connecting Nature Framework Element (see Deliverable 4.1 for a detailed description of the process of these webinars in Xidou et al., 2021).
- **Multiplier Webinars:** We recorded four webinars for UrbanByNature, two on co-production, one on reflexive monitoring, and one on the Connecting Nature Framework. During the webinars we discussed with the Brazilian, Caucasus and Chinese participants about their questions and the value of our topics in their context.
- **Organisational Coaching Programme:** This programme sought to facilitate organisational capacity building to support the cities in stress management in COVID times and foster interpersonal and team building skills (Appendix F).
- **EM|Path approach:** The EM|Path approach was applied within the Connecting Nature teams in Sarajevo and Nicosia and with urban gardeners in A Coruña to create a sense of connectedness within the groups, ownership,

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and empowerment (Xidou et al. 2022; van der Have et al. 2022).

- **Stakeholder mapping workshop:** The workshop provided an opportunity for the Fast-Follower Cities to explore and experience various techniques for identifying and initiating engagement with stakeholders.

2.2 How we captured our learnings on co-production and reflexive monitoring

We conducted a comparative analysis of how the Connecting Nature cities developed and implemented co-production and reflexive monitoring, respectively, to generate insights about similarities and differences, identify best practices and lessons learned that are taken up in the respective guidebooks. We iteratively discussed these insights with the cities to refine them and facilitate learning and transfer of important lessons between the cities.

Through our various interaction formats we were able to collect a large amount of materials and information about how the Connecting Nature cities developed and implemented co-production and reflexive monitoring (Appendix C). For example, our co-production webinars included structured reflections along the lines of the different elements of our co-production approach (see Section 3), which helped us create co-production patterns for all cities. Especially the regular learning sessions with the Front-Runner Cities yielded rich data about the day-to-day experiences, challenges, and opportunities the cities faced and allowed us to distil learning outcomes regarding each element of the Connecting Nature Framework (presented in Deliverable 6, Hölscher et al. 2022). Next to these sessions, interviews were conducted with co-production participants in Genk (n = 8) and Glasgow (n = 11) and co-production workshops were attended in both cities by a masters student researching how context conditions influence co-production (Kindlon 2020). The city reports (also part of Deliverable 6) were additional sources of information about how the cities translated the co-production and reflexive monitoring methods to their practices, detailing their activities and including reflections on lessons learned.

Our comparative analysis was based on our conceptual work on co-production and reflexive monitoring. Regarding **co-production**, we have used our co-production framework to create co-production patterns for each Connecting Nature city and compare them across cities (see Section 3 for an overview of the framework). These include (1) co-production goals and settings (including co-production methods) and (2) co-production principles.

Following this framework, we have coded the collected data per city. We first distinguished between different types of co-production processes per city (based on goals and settings), including the actors involved and methods used. The co-production principles were coded in an overarching way (i.e. per city and not per individual co-production process). For the principles, we have identified how the cities have interpreted the principle, how they have delivered it and what were shortcomings (outcome focus). Additionally, we have identified how they have delivered the principle to discern necessary capacities for co-production as well as capacity gaps and challenges.

Subsequently, we have compared all co-production processes per city – along the dimensions of goals and settings as well as principles – to identify similarities and differences, best practices, and overarching lessons. Our results are reported in Section 3. Additionally, we have translated our findings into a guidebook for co-production as described in the corresponding sections below (van der Have et al. 2022).

Regarding **reflexive monitoring**, we have developed a method to capture the types of learning in form of learning outcomes occurring in the Front-Runner Cities (see Section 4.2) based on the literature (Sol et al. 2017; van Mierlo 2012; van Mierlo et al. 2010b; 2010c) (Appendix D). For the knowledge transfer between Front-Runner and Fast-Follower Cities we analysed the learning objectives identified and discussed during the 1-on-1 learning sessions and Learning Platform Webinars (see Section 4.3). Both learning outcomes and learning objectives are clustered according to the elements of the Connecting Nature Framework (Appendix E), and are in detail reported in Deliverable 6 (Hölscher et al. 2022).

Front-Runner Cities learning outcome analysis

Together with the Front-Runner Cities, we analysed the reflexivity of their learning outcomes, i.e. innovative ways the respective Connecting Nature city team handles the barriers or opportunities captured in the Dynamic Learning Agenda. The analysis is based on Beers and Van Mierlo (2017) that distinguish between the following reflexivity categories:

- **Rules** guiding actors' practices, for example tendering procedures or the way a city department is organised.
- **Relations** between actors and between the nature-based solution and its context, for example who is involved in the planning process.
- **Practices** concerning common ways of working, for example how the team collaborates internally.
- **Discourse** related to the future of the nature-based solutions, for example the way a mayor talks about the benefits of nature-based solutions for the city

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After all items on the Dynamic Learning Agenda (i.e. Critical Turning Points, see Section 4.1) have been discussed in the learning session, we identified learning outcomes. To ensure the learning is reflexive, we discussed with the cities which of the reflexivity categories applied per learning outcome. In our analysis, we created a table per city, in which we linked the learning outcomes to their critical turning points, learning questions, and follow-up actions and to the reflexivity categories and the Connecting Nature Framework Element. We asked the cities to verify the written analysis in the table which resulted in clarifications and some corrections.

Then, for a cross-city comparison and discussion of learning outcomes, we clustered the learning outcomes of the three Front-Runner Cities around common barriers/opportunities that resulted in reflexivity changes in cities. We asked the Connecting Nature Framework Element leads to verify the written analysis, which resulted in clarifications and some corrections (Appendix D). This resulted in 19 clusters of common opportunities and barriers presented in 3 tables that present for all three cities: 1) critical turning points and learning questions connected with the learning outcomes of the opportunities/barriers per city, 2) associated reflexivity categories of the learning outcomes and 3) associated Connecting Nature Framework Elements of the learning outcomes. We presented the analysis during the learning experience webinars for another round of discussions with the cities. The results of the analysis are presented and further discussed in Section 4.2. Additionally, it provided in-depth information for the analysis of how the cities have implemented the Connecting Nature Framework (see Deliverable 6, Hölscher et al. 2022).

Fast-Follower Cities learning objectives analysis

In order to assess the learning objectives of the Fast-Follower Cities, we analysed the survey we conducted for Learning Platform Webinar #0 and the 1-on-1 learning sessions between Front-Runner Cities and Fast-Follower Cities. In the minutes of these 21 meetings (3 for each city), we coded learning objectives per Connecting Nature Framework Element, and also marked in which reflexivity category they fit (rules/relation/practice/discourse). Furthermore, we analysed whether the learning objective has received a response or advice from another city, either during one of the 1-on-1 learning sessions, a Knowledge Hub meeting or the third Learning Platform Webinar. In addition, we considered the latest versions of the cities' Dynamic Learning Agendas, but only to provide context. After making the overview of the learning questions, we subsequently asked the other Fast-Follower Cities to mark the learning objectives that they recognised in their own cities. The complete overview of the analysis is presented in Appendix E and the results are presented and further discussed in Section 4.3.

The experience of working with the Front-Runner Cities offered insights on how to work with reflexive monitoring in practice. This we used when writing the reflexive monitoring guidebook (Lodder et al. 2022). The method of analysing the Front-Runner and Fast-Follower Cities' learning outcomes was fed into the reflexive monitoring guidebook steps 4, 6 and 7 (Lodder et al. 2022). In this way, other cities or researchers can replicate our process in other contexts. The cities also contributed to the guidebook sharing their experiences and recorded testimonials (Box 2), which makes the guidebook very accessible for practitioners.

3 Results: how the cities worked with co-production and what was learned

Here, we present our results on how the cities have worked with co-production and what we have learned for the guidebook along the different dimensions of our co-production framework.

Based on our literature review on co-production as well as our exchanges on, and experiences with, co-production in the Connecting Nature cities, we have developed a comprehensive framework of co-production to enable urban actors – including policymakers, planners, researchers, business and finance communities, and citizens – to design their own repertoire of co-production processes and activities, as well as to rethink and redesign on-going processes to become co-production processes. Setting up high quality, viable, inclusive and effective co-production processes requires good process designs, knowledge about the right tools and methods as well as enabling institutions and resources to facilitate collaboration tailored to local contexts and cultures, include marginalised actors and enable open discussions without starting from pre-defined problems and solutions (Bremer et al. 2019; Bussu and Galanti 2018; Sorrentino et al. 2018).

On a general level, our framework distinguishes between the 'what' – i.e. the content of co-production in terms of the goals, settings and methods used – as well as the 'how' – i.e. how to design and evaluate co-production based on co-production principles and capacities (Figure 4). In terms of 'what', the co-production goals refer to the key aims for which co-production is employed, which determine the type of co-production process and (actor) setting. Co-production methods are used to facilitate specific activities within a co-production process, depending on goals and settings (e.g. vision

development, problem framing). In terms of ‘how’, we have identified a set of co-production principles that provide a heuristic to design, implement and, evaluate co-production (Hölscher et al. 2019a, based on Frantzeskaki et al. 2019 and Frantzeskaki and Kabisch 2016). As such, they give guidance on how to ensure good quality co-production processes, identify which capacities are needed to ensure those and evaluate co-production processes and outcomes.

Figure 4: Co-production framework

We have used the different elements of the framework to help the Connecting Nature cities design and reflect on their co-production processes, as well as to analyse and compare the co-production processes across all cities. In the following, we first present the different types of co-production goals and settings we found in the cities (Section 3.1) and then how the cities have implemented the co-production principles, including which outcomes they have aimed for and achieved, how they have been able to ensure the principles and what were shortcomings and challenges (Section 3.2). Note that here we don’t explicitly refer to co-production capacities when understanding how the cities implemented the principles. We come back to necessary co-production capacities in our overarching conclusion about lessons learned, which also includes a critical reflection about the co-production processes in the cities (Section 5.1).

3.1 Co-production goals and settings: defining what co-production is for

The co-production goals refer to the key aims for which co-production is employed, which determine the type of co-production process and (actor) setting. We distinguish between strategic, tactical, and operational aims and settings³, which address different governance levels (Loorbach 2010; Frantzeskaki et al. 2014) and thus influence who is typically involved and what are useful activities and methods. Settings refer closely to the goals for co-production and the corresponding governance levels and actors to pursue them.

Across all cities, we could identify various co-production processes related to their respective nature-based solution exemplars, which can be distinguished based on different goals and settings (Table 1).

Table 1: Co-production goals and settings

Co-production setting	Goals	Actors involved	Activities and methods
Strategic	Developing and linking to strategic goals and agendas	Governmental actors from different departments/jurisdictions	Data collection to distil knowledge (e.g. citizen science)

³ We do not include reflexive co-production goals and settings here. These refer to on-going monitoring and learning, which in Connecting Nature took place through reflexive monitoring (Section 4). As thus, reflexive co-production, or more specifically in our cases reflexive monitoring, cuts across and contributes to reflecting on all other co-production processes irrespective of the goals and settings.

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	nature-based solution (exemplars)	Key private actors to provide expertise on and generate support for goals and plans (e.g. academics, landscape architects) Citizens (mainly consultation based to provide feedback)	Exploring the context (e.g. bike tours) Workshops for problem definition and visioning Public consultation (e.g. online surveys, information points, postcards, public exhibitions)
Tactical	Building partnerships and generating knowledge for planning, delivery, stewardship, and scaling	Governmental actors from different departments/jurisdictions Key private actors for public-private partnerships (e.g. local enterprises, architecture companies, schools, NGOs) Key citizen groups (e.g. associations)	Setting up Open Innovation Teams EM Path approach (Xidous et al. 2022; van der Have et al. 2022) Business Model Canvas Tool (McQuaid and Fletcher 2020) Nature-based solution Accelerator Establishing and formalising cross-departmental collaborations, public-private partnerships and citizen groups (e.g. Friends of... groups, gardeners' associations)
Operational	Planning of specific nature-based solutions and co-stewardship	Governmental actors from different departments/jurisdictions Key private actors to provide expertise (e.g. academics, landscape architects) Citizens (users of nature-based solution, nearby residents)	Visioning workshops including brainstorming, storytelling, mood board, drawing Site visits and walks Idea competitions (e.g. Junior teams)

Most cities employed a combination of different co-production processes and corresponding goals and settings. For example, in Genk, co-production started out on the strategic level with the goal to develop a masterplan for the redevelopment of the Stiemer valley through nature-based solutions and connect it with other city strategies. On a tactical level, it developed citizen-based partnerships (the Friends of the Stiemer). On the operational level, several co-production processes took place to implement specific Stiemer Programme nature-based solutions. While a city often initially started with one co-production process on one level, which level was chosen first varied. In Poznań, and contrary to Genk, the co-production started out operational, in terms of bringing actors together for the design of open gardens in specific kindergarten, and moved towards the tactical level later to build partnerships for scaling open gardens and nature-oriented playgrounds in the city. Notably, most Fast-Follower Cities employed mainly strategic co-production – this links on the one hand to the state of their exemplar implementation and on the other hand the limited experience with co-production. They sought to develop plans for their nature-based solution exemplars based on internal cross-departmental collaborative processes and citizen consultation.

The types of actors involved in each process differed. For example, strategic co-production processes are in all cities mainly pursued within the city government, building on cross-departmental collaboration and with the support of public-private partnerships, while at tactical and operational levels much broader forms of partnerships also with citizens and businesses are established that are at the same time more localised regarding the specific solutions. We did critically discuss the extent to which all such processes that the cities labelled as co-production were indeed co-production, since at times co-production seemed equated with collaboration (including cross-departmental, which was termed ‘internal co-production’). We come back to this critical reflection throughout the analysis and specifically in the conclusion (Section 5.1).

The Connecting Nature cities stated that the distinction in different co-production settings and goals helped them define their goals, identify whom to involve and plan their process including methods. In the co-production guidebook, we have incorporated the identification of setting as a tool to plan the co-production process. As a method, identifying and discussing on the governance activities helps to reflect on what is currently happening and what needs to happen, as well as to diagnose the activities that different actors engage in. Additionally, we have incorporated the different collaborative methods the cities applied within their specific co-production settings as exemplary methods in the guidebook, including the Business Model Canvas tool (McQuaid and Fletcher 2020) and the EM|Path approach (Xidous et al. 2022; van der Have et al. 2022).

3.1.1 Strategic co-production

Several Connecting Nature cities employed strategic co-production to develop the strategic overarching goals and agendas for nature-based solution implementation and scaling. This provides a direction for the identification and development of specific nature-based solution, links nature-based solution to other strategic goals and agendas and thus generates political support and enables financing. For example, Genk employed strategic co-production to develop the spatial masterplan of the Stiemer valley and connect that masterplan to other city strategies. Similarly, the Open Space Strategy (OSS), which serves as an overarching framework for open space implementation in Glasgow and links to other city strategies (e.g. Strategic Development Plan, Local Biodiversity Action Plan) (Table 1). Most Fast-Follower Cities employed mainly strategic co-production to develop plans for their nature-based solution exemplars based on internal cross-departmental collaborative processes and citizen consultation. For example, the Pavlos Melas Metropolitan Park Strategy outlines the regeneration of the former military camp towards a green space, marking an important administration mechanism that is legally binding because it is connected to existing policy plans and official documents. In Nicosia, the Local Strategic Sustainable Development Plan and Integrated Spatial Development Strategy (OXA) include the proposal for the urban garden network.

Strategic co-production involved mainly actors from different city departments or jurisdictions as well as key private stakeholders in order to build cross-departmental collaboration and alignment towards shared goals, while the wider public is involved through consultation processes. The OSS was developed together with multiple strategic partners, including actors from different city departments, the regional government and private organisations (e.g. Greenspace Scotland, Central Scotland Green Network). For example, Open Space Standards to identify open spaces were developed with advice from Greenspace Scotland. Actors from other city departments have reviewed the standards from their specific field of expertise. The wider public and local communities were involved in the identification and assessment of open spaces, building on participatory data collection and citizen science approaches to develop an interactive map. Similarly, Burgas sought feedback from the public on the internally developed concept for the Saint Trinity Park renovation and conducted a sociological survey in which people stated that they want more green areas in the city.

Methods for strategic co-production have been diverse, depending on who is involved in specific activities. In Ioannina, roundtable meetings took place with all public stakeholders to develop the programmatic agreement between different governments involved. Genk has employed multiple engagement formats to also engage the public in multiple ways. An internal project group with multidisciplinary experts collected diverse input and advice for the masterplan. A workshop on ecosystem services for actors from different departments and external partners (led by Flemish Research Institute Nature and Forest) sought to unite and connect interests and visions, define win-wins and trade-offs, gather multidisciplinary input on functions and services of the valley. Neighbourhood dialogues were held in different parts of the valley to introduce the master planning process and harvest local knowledge. Additionally, bike tours were organised to explore the valley and an info quiz to seek support and raise awareness on the masterplan. Notably, citizens are in strategic co-production are mostly involved on a consultation bases to obtain additional input and feedback, for instance in Glasgow through online questionnaires, public exhibitions and key questions on postcards and surveys. For these purposes, online platforms can be important – in Ioannina for public consultation and in Glasgow to ensure iterative data collection and sharing on the quality of open spaces. In Burgas, a temporary office in the park was set up for citizen consultation.

3.1.2 Tactical co-production

Tactical co-production helped the cities specify action agendas and build local coalitions and networks between public and private actors. In all cities, new collaborations and partnerships were formed across departments and between public and private actors for the joint development of the action agenda and initiatives. Poznań has established new public-private partnerships to facilitate the scaling of open garden and nature-oriented playgrounds in kindergarten. This process involved actors from different city departments, including the Project Coordination and Urban Regeneration Office and Department of Education, and the mapping, selection of and collaboration with suitable and interested kindergarten. The creation of partnerships with more kindergartens was a result of a conference on “Natural Playgrounds for Youth Education” (November 2018).

In some cities, formalised citizen groups were established to provide connections between citizens and the city government and to develop initiatives from the bottom-up. In Genk, the “Friends of the Stiemer” is a group of engaged citizens that are ambassadors of nature-based solutions in their city and mediate between the city government and citizens using the Stiemer valley. Members have a strong connection with the valley and were identified during the preparation of the masterplan. While it has initially been a very informal and ill-defined group, it has become a more formalised soundboard for the local government. The Stiemer team meets them once a year and keeps them informed, and asks the

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friends to put questions on the agenda. Glasgow has also put in place “Friends of...” groups that are local people who organise activities in open spaces and are supported by the city council. In A Coruña, a local group on urban agriculture has been set up, including urban gardeners, teachers, trainers, representatives of municipal departments, NGOs, SMEs to exchange knowledge and experience on urban gardening and facilitate co-stewardship of urban gardens. Nicosia is planning to develop a NBS Agency as an umbrella organisation responsible for stewarding their open garden network and involving stakeholders from all municipalities as well as academia, advisors and entrepreneurs.

The main methods for tactical co-production relate to partnership building and mobilising networks. Several dedicated Connecting Nature methods that were developed for these purposes were useful. The Osmos Innovation Team workshops in the Fast-Follower Cities helped them identify and connect with key stakeholders. For instance, in Sarajevo, the workshops led to the conclusion that partnerships will be essential for project delivery and financing. They differentiated between a relatively small group of actors who will be directly involved and a larger communications network to engage actors in the long-term. The Business Model Canvas (BMC) tool, which was applied in all cities, has allowed them to elaborate the wider value propositions of their nature-based solutions and to clarify how these will be delivered through key activities and partners (McQuaid and Fletcher 2020). The Connecting Nature Enterprise platform⁴ facilitates connection with and networking between nature-based enterprises (NBEs), which has also been translated into local versions (e.g. a Cluster of Metropolitan Park NBEs in Pavlos Melas and Glasgow’s Nature-Based Accelerator). The EM|Path approach was applied within the Connecting Nature teams in Sarajevo and Nicosia and with urban gardeners in A Coruña to create a sense of connectedness within the groups, ownership and empowerment (Xidou et al. 2022; van der Have et al. 2022).

3.1.3 Operational co-production

Operational co-production refers to those settings, in which concrete initiatives and projects are being designed. Operational co-production in Connecting Nature cities mostly resembled ‘traditional’ co-production by engaging diverse actors, particularly local communities, in the design of the nature-based solution exemplar. In A Coruña, an open participatory process involved meetings with citizens, associations, architects and gardeners in the planning and delivery of the urban garden in the Adolfo Suarez Park. In Poznań, a series of informational and consultation meetings were held with residents, children, parents, teachers and architects, who could express their opinion on the open garden in kindergarten no. 42 at Wilda District, its concept and the form in which it would function in the future and what attractions it would provide to all visitors. In Glasgow and Genk, operational co-production was used for the development of nature-based solutions in specific areas. In the Pollok area, Growchapel and within the city’s Stalled Spaces programme in Glasgow, co-production with local communities found out what their needs and aims were regarding open space and nature-based solutions.

Operational co-production involves diverse actors from local governments, experts and in particular local communities, who have direct connections with the nature-based solutions – such as urban gardeners in A Coruña, children, parents and teachers in Poznań, and children, elderly and people with disabilities in Sarajevo. The process to develop a community garden, Growchapel, on a previously vacant and derelict site in Drumchapel in Glasgow included actors from city council departments, Greenspace Scotland, Drumchapel police, education establishments, G15 Youth groups, local organisations (e.g. housing associations, social enterprises, health organisations) and local residents.

Methods for operational co-production are diverse, centring around workshops and creative facilitation methods to generate shared problem framings, visions and solution ideas. In Poznań, a visioning workshop with children, teachers and parents contributed to the design of a natural playground at a kindergarten: During a brainstorming exercise, parents, children and teachers exchanged ideas about how an open garden could look like and how they will spend free time and how they can play and fun there. The next step was to visualise the thoughts and prepare pictures/drawings that represented the envisioned open garden – plants, flowers and other elements. In Genk, a set of three workshops were held in the development of Schansbroek park (source area of the Stiemer) for participants to get to know each other, create ownership, identify a common project objective, prioritise expectations, define functions and measures for the future park, propose the design plan, receive feedback and inform on specific actions. Participants (local stakeholders, city departments, neighbourhood managers) were asked to invest a fictional sum of €1000 on the generated ideas to prioritise. Other methods included a mood board, storytelling, drawing, brainstorm, an inspirational walk and an informative exhibition. Park tours and site visits can be an important mechanism to explore local dynamics and identify existing

⁴ This platform is a stand-alone innovation developed in the Connecting Nature project: <https://www.naturebasedenterprise.eu>. It is a sustainable platform that will continue after the Connecting Nature project ends in May 2022.

issues. In Glasgow, the Every Tree Tells a Story project seeks to empower communities to use creativity to capture stories about the trees and spaces in which they set.

3.2 Co-production principles: designing and evaluating co-production

We have identified six principles that provide a heuristic to design, implement, and evaluate co-production processes (Figure 5). The principles build on the design framework of knowledge co-production presented by Frantzeskaki and Kabisch (2016).

The co-production principles integrate both process as well as outcome design considerations into the set-up of co-production processes:

- Three *process principles* identify critical criteria for ensuring the procedural quality of co-production processes in terms of their inclusivity, openness and legitimacy. Rather than providing a step-by-step blueprint, the process principles provide guidelines and questions that can be adapted to a specific context and process.
- Three *outcome principles* identify what kind of results are generated throughout co-production processes and how they feed into urban policies, strategic agendas, institutions and wider engagement of actors. Rather than looking at improved substantive outcomes (e.g. improved health services or environmental quality), the outcome principles focus on governance outcomes in terms of enhanced capacity of public and private actors to solve or progress on public problems and increase public service delivery across agency, jurisdictional and public problem domains, for example by overcoming fragmentation and inconsistency in the delivery of public services (Bianchi et al. 2021; Rogers and Weber 2010).

Figure 5: The co-production principles

The principles, as well as how we have developed them based on literature review and consultation with the Front-Runner Cities, were in detail introduced in our prior Deliverable 4 (Hölscher et al. 2019a). Based on our findings and further literature review, we have enriched them with a view on outcomes and capacities (how to implement the principles). We have used the principles in a twofold way to support the cities both design and evaluate their co-production processes. Here, we present our findings from our cross-city analysis in terms of how the cities have translated the principles to their co-production processes, to what extent they were able to fulfil them and how they have done so (see Table 2 for an overview). We have translated this into the co-production guidebook in several ways: Firstly, the principles themselves are introduced with examples of why they are important and how to address them. Secondly, they are presented as consideration for each step in designing and implementing a co-production process – e.g., when setting the goals, the principles aid thinking about different issues that should be addressed and what kind of results are sought, and the principles give structure for reflecting on the process and results. Moreover, the analysis of how the cities addressed the principles provides, thirdly, specific tools to implement the different co-production steps (e.g. actor mapping) as well as, fourthly, lessons learned about important conditions and capacities for co-production (see also Section 5.1).

Generally, the cities stated that before Connecting Nature, they have not been working with the principles upfront but they found them important to keep in mind before, during and after a co-production process. However, given that most cities, especially the Fast-Follower Cities, did not have extensive experience with co-production, the cities struggled to think about how to implement the principles.

One of our main propositions with the principles is that when thinking about and designing co-production it is about putting all the principles to work together and in synergy with each other and not compromise one principle. We could discern many synergies between principles – for example between inclusivity and the perceived legitimacy of a process. Accordingly, the cities questioned the legitimacy of their co-production process when inclusivity could not be ensured. Additionally, the extent to which the outcome principles were achieved strongly depended on the process. For example, empowerment of participants strongly relates to whether the process indeed allows for open and candid discussions and exchange (openness) and is legitimate to generate trust and ownership.

Table 2: Co-production principles: how to design, implement and evaluate co-production

Co-production principle	What for and results	How to ensure the principles	Shortcomings and challenges
Process principles			
Inclusivity: involving diverse actors on equal basis	<p>Inclusive participation of actors with different expertise, background, gender etc.</p> <p>Reaching unusual suspects and vulnerable groups</p> <p>Getting diverse input and contextualising solutions</p> <p>Building new relationships and partnerships between diverse actors</p>	<p>Actor mapping:</p> <p>Identifying selection criteria for participation</p> <p>Employing actor mapping tools, also paying attention to including 'unusual suspects' and 'voiceless' or disadvantaged actors</p> <p>Building on previous connections and key partners to identify actors</p> <p>Actively reaching out:</p> <p>Employing tailored communication formats and communication experts (e.g. street-level professionals)</p> <p>Providing incentives to raise motivation to participate (e.g. financial support, training, social recognition)</p> <p>Harnessing and building relationships with diverse communities, spending time with communities, fun activities</p> <p>Make process accessible and equal:</p> <p>Identifying and tailoring process to different needs and capabilities of participating actors</p> <p>Ensuring equality between different groups (e.g. experts, citizens) and giving equal voice to everyone</p>	<p>Ensuring inclusivity, especially involvement of vulnerable groups and unusual suspects</p> <p>Lack of motivation to participate / no participation culture</p> <p>Bringing together multiple actors in the same setting (e.g. public actors and citizens)</p> <p>Ensuring long-term motivation to participate and thus inclusivity</p> <p>Time constraints for ensuring inclusivity</p>
Legitimacy: ensuring the process and results are accepted and relevant	<p>Ensuring the process and results are accepted and relevant</p> <p>Building ownership over and trust in the process and results</p> <p>Shielding the process from being politicised and captured by political agendas</p>	<p>Resources and skills for co-production:</p> <p>Mobilising and fostering facilitation skills (e.g. hiring a professional facilitator, professional development training)</p> <p>Defining and transparency about goals, procedures and roles:</p> <p>(Co-)defining and communicating problems and goals, procedures and basic ground rules, roles and responsibilities</p> <p>Managing expectations</p> <p>Establishing key coordinating actor/team responsible for oversight</p> <p>Upholding standards for knowledge entering the process:</p> <p>Checking knowledge and arguments before entering the process</p> <p>Ensuring relevant expertise is becoming available in the process</p> <p>Facilitating critical discussions on different knowledge sources and arguments</p>	<p>Ensuring resources and skills for co-production</p> <p>Asymmetrical power relations, different motives etc.</p> <p>How to deal with conflicts and divergent views</p>
Openness: facilitating collaborative learning and adaptation to new insights, knowledge and demands	<p>Facilitating collaborative learning and openness to exchange ideas and opinions</p> <p>Adapting the process to new insights, knowledge and demands</p>	<p>Open process setting:</p> <p>Allowing candid and constructive knowledge exchange, disagreement and criticism</p> <p>Recognising cultural differences and addressing power imbalances, mediating conflict</p> <p>Reflexivity and adaptability:</p> <p>Allocating time and space for reflection and learning about assumptions and goals, process implementation, barriers and opportunities and</p>	<p>Hierarchical and top-down way of working in city governments</p> <p>Risk-averse city governments that don't allow for open-ended and flexible processes</p> <p>No experience with co-production and</p>

		<p>necessary adaptations</p> <p>Allocating time and resources for adaptations to the process and results</p> <p>Employing reflexive monitoring throughout</p> <p>Communication about process and results</p> <p>Developing communication brand/strategy to showcase and disseminate relevance of co-production process and results to different target audiences (e.g. PR campaigns, site visits, events)</p> <p>Hiring communication specialists to ensure inclusive narrative and use appropriate dissemination channels</p> <p>Ensuring political and institutional support:</p> <p>Explaining co-production and its benefits to political leaders and decision-makers</p> <p>Making use of momentum and opportunities for co-production (e.g. through research project funding)</p> <p>Inviting political leaders and decision-makers to experience co-production processes</p> <p>Allocating explicit budget to co-production, connecting to existing capacities and projects</p> <p>Mainstreaming co-production in existing processes and projects (e.g. tendering)</p>	<p>benefits</p> <p>Making time and ensuring skills for continuous adaptation and communication</p>
Outcome principles			
<p>Actionable knowledge: results are applicable in practice</p>	<p>New knowledge about problems and solutions that recognises complexity of societal problems, is contextually relevant and socially robust</p> <p>Filling data gaps</p> <p>Relevant, innovative and applicable solutions, strategies, agendas and processes (e.g. new policies, institutions, routines, plans, goals, financing)</p> <p>Acceptance of, and support for, new solutions etc.</p> <p>Learning for scaling and replication</p>	<p>Salience to urban needs and priorities:</p> <p>Developing working knowledge of decision context to ensure procedural and content-wide quality</p> <p>Recognising different knowledge systems and linking the process to urban needs and priorities</p> <p>Linking co-production process and results to existing goals, processes, needs</p> <p>Identifying existing processes, goals etc. in policy, business and local communities</p> <p>Ensuring knowledge about background information, legislation etc.</p> <p>Prioritising knowledge transfer</p> <p>Identifying key actors to communicate about process and results</p> <p>Reaching out to and building partnerships and networks, advocacy coalitions to take results further</p>	<p>Not using or cherry-picking co-production results</p> <p>Discrepancies between informal co-production processes and the formal institutional context</p> <p>Depoliticization of conflicts</p> <p>Wider legitimacy from small-scale co-production processes</p> <p>Uncertainty due to political processes</p>

<p>Empowerment of participants</p>	<p>(Re-)defining roles and responsibilities</p> <p>New and deeper relationships</p> <p>Own initiative, new practices and routines of societal actors vis-à-vis nature-based solution</p> <p>Self-management of nature-based solution</p> <p>Changed relations</p> <p>Increase ownership of citizens towards the project</p>	<p>Defining new roles and responsibilities</p> <p>Co-defining and sharing responsibilities</p> <p>Clarifying pre-conditions and requirements</p> <p>Organising continuous engagement activities</p> <p>Organising workshops, fun activities etc. connected to the nature-based solution</p> <p>Collaborate and engage diverse actors (e.g. NGOs, citizen organisations) in organisation of activities</p> <p>Strengthening community capacities</p> <p>Providing trainings, workshops and toolkits to local communities on e.g. self-management, ecological education</p> <p>Ensuring additional resources and capacities for training and informing citizens/communities</p>	<p>Disempowerment: e.g. increased sense of powerlessness, reinforced power structures and further marginalisation</p> <p>Maintaining high levels of motivations and engagement in the long-term</p> <p>Positioning citizenship as 'gap filling'</p>
<p>Aligning actors and agendas for synergies</p>	<p>Aligning and embedding nature-based solutions across multiple policy, planning and community strategies and agendas</p> <p>Connecting resources and priorities for synergies (crossing siloes)</p> <p>New collaborative governance practices, partnerships and collaborations</p> <p>Political and institutional support for nature-based solution and co-production</p>	<p>Connecting and embedding nature-based solution goals and agendas with other goals, agendas and planning documents</p> <p>Showing how nature-based solutions contribute to and deliver on other strategies, agendas etc</p> <p>Linking nature-based solution to other strategic priorities (e.g. historic value)</p> <p>Promoting nature-based solution as flagship programme</p> <p>Nurturing collaboration across multiple urban projects and agenda</p> <p>Identifying key actors and enablers for collaboration</p> <p>Ensuring good communication and working relationships, building trust</p> <p>Creating informal spaces for communication and collaboration</p> <p>Establishing cross-cutting working groups and task forces</p> <p>New collaborative governance modes</p> <p>Formalise cross-departmental collaboration and public-private partnerships</p> <p>Establishing a central node for overseeing, guiding, connecting and supporting the follow-up activities of the co-production process</p> <p>Investing in organisational capacities</p> <p>Identifying and hiring agents responsible for overseeing and implementing the shared agendas</p>	<p>Lack of support from higher level decision-makers (sources)</p> <p>Reluctance to cooperate, mainly due to lack of time and resources</p>

3.2.1 Inclusivity: involving diverse actors on an equal basis

Inclusive co-production ensures that throughout the process diverse knowledge is becoming available, with the aim to complement and enrich each other, and fosters new partnerships between participants (Frantzeskaki and Kabisch 2016). It also invites questions about who is having access to participate and which capabilities people have to participate in order to ensure that diverse actors are brought together on equal footing (Bussu and Galanti 2018).

What for and results

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Focusing on inclusivity ensures that different perspectives are represented in an equal way, which enriches the process and results towards more legitimate and salient outcomes that address local and specific needs. The Connecting Nature cities emphasised the need for inclusivity to connect to different actors, get more expertise and perspectives and raising new questions about and design ideas for their exemplar, thus facilitating actionable knowledge (Box 3, Section 3.2.4). Considering inclusivity facilitated an opening up of their urban governance and planning approaches towards looking beyond the ‘usual suspects’. Further, the cities valued inclusivity to build new relationships and partnerships and make everyone feel part of the process, thus linking to alignment and empowerment outcomes (see Sections 3.2.5 and 3.2.6).

What counts as inclusive participation depends on the goal and context of a co-production process (see Section 3.1). Generally, the cities identified a large variety of actors to involve in their co-production processes, for example to connect to local needs, ensure expert knowledge becomes available and generate political support:

- A main group to include are the citizens and specific groups of users relevant for the nature-based solution. For example, in Sarajevo, because the exemplar aims to create green spaces for diverse groups, including children, elderly and children with disabilities, it was important to include all of these groups.
- Governmental actors and politicians from diverse city departments and governance scales need to be involved for specific regulatory questions and to ensure support for delivery and long-term stewardship. In A Coruña, other departments needed to be involved such as the Department of Education that is responsible for school gardens and the Department of Markets and Tourism to link gardeners to organic markets where they can sell their products. Additionally, school curriculums are dependent on the regional government, while physical space for integrating ecological education depends on the municipality. This highlights the need to reach agreement with different people for different things.
- Various experts on issues in question support the planning, delivery and stewardship of nature-based solutions. Experts are diverse: In Poznań, to support the design of the open garden at the kindergarten it was important to include both a landscape architect, experts on ecological education as well as the police to address questions of safety when opening the kindergarten garden to the public. Experts also include academics and universities, that support feasibility studies, data collection etc.
- NGOs, local associations and groups can help providing expertise and connections to the wider public and be key actors to get local needs across (Box 3). In A Coruña, it was important to include neighbourhood associations to ensure potential users of the garden from the neighbourhood get involved. Additionally, an NGO working with migrants facilitated connection to wider groups.
- Involving local entrepreneurs and private companies can provide opportunities for nature-based entrepreneurship and financing of the nature-based solution delivery and stewardship. Nicosia aims to set up the “Adopt a Park” Scheme to promote long-term partnerships between local businesses and local governments, in order to maintain and beautify the small/medium-sized neighbourhood parks.

Box 3: Inclusivity in Nicosia

Nicosia Development Agency is developing a network of green spaces throughout the city. One of the parks included in the project is Ayios Dimitrios Park, which is located close to a children’s hospital. By involving representatives from the hospital in the development process, a new perspective was added to the redesign process: The park could function as an escape for parents and children visiting the hospital. This introduced new design questions: what are needs of the kids and their parents and how can the park add to their wellbeing? Ultimately, more activities for families and younger kids were added.

How to ensure inclusivity?

A crucial step is **actor mapping** to identify the right people, which are motivated and can contribute to the project, irrespective of their function or level of hierarchy. The cities learned that whom to involve should be identified from the very beginning, including defining what for and for which stage. Burgas employed a problem-based approach to actor mapping: stakeholders would be invited depending on what the problem is, who is responsible and who is able to give support. In Nicosia, it was found important to identify the end users, for example in the case of Ayios Park the parents of kids in the hospital, pupils at the English school and people who live in the area. Additionally, the cities stated it was important to select participants based on diversity in backgrounds, social status, role, gender and knowledge, including for example practical, legal and operational knowledge. Actor mapping tools support the identification of actors (see e.g. van der Have et al. 2022 for applied methods for actor analysis and unusual suspect mapping). Actor mapping can be supported by key contact actors embedded in a local context. In Poznań, the green classroom project was developed in a district the team didn’t know well before, therefore the team asked the kindergarten management and voluntary district

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council for contacts. In Glasgow, Greenspace Scotland had contacts with a variety of relevant organisations and actors to be included.

In order to mobilise and motivate actors to participate in co-production processes, the cities found it necessary to **actively reach out to people** by spending time with communities and employing tailored communication formats (street-level professionals) and incentives (e.g. financial support, training, social recognition) (see also Bussu and Galanti 2018; Ferli et al. 2019; Campbell et al. 2016; Puerari et al. 2018; Voorberg et al. 2014; Barrutia and Echebarria 2012). In these efforts, the cities stated the importance of making it relevant for people to be involved, and for example increasing their motivation to participate through informal, fun activities. Different channels need to be established for reaching out to different actors, including social media, open park days or eye opener workshops with actors from other departments. To mobilise local communities, it was important to actively go into the neighbourhoods with locally embedded persons such as community or neighbourhood managers. This can be supported by formalised citizen groups or associations like “Friends of...” groups (see Section 3.1.2). The way of communicating and attention to simple language was considered important, such as avoiding the use of acronyms (e.g. NBS for nature-based solutions in Glasgow) to limit confusion.

Since not all actors have the same capabilities, time, experiences and interests to participate, inclusive participation requires **making the process accessible and equal** (Matuk et al. 2020; Reed and Abernethy 2018; Tengö et al. 2017). As thus, the choice of instrument and method depends on specific objectives, phases, power at play and target group. For instance, involving youths requires different types of processes and methods. Poznań employed different visioning exercises in the design of the open garden at kindergarten 42 and the green classroom, because the latter didn't involve children. In Genk, a Junior Team idea competition took place to involve children in the development of the valley, raise their awareness and knowledge about topics related to the valley and co-develop ideas on how to make the valley attractive for children. In different activities the children got to know the Stiemer valley, made proposals, invited other children to vote for the proposals and then elaborated 10 proposals. Facilitation needs to guarantee equality between different groups (e.g. experts, citizens), pay attention to people who find it more challenging to speak-up and articulate knowledge into a form that can be shared with others. In Glasgow, it was important to consider the digital element for participants to complete open space mapping in workshop. A hybrid method was employed so no one got excluded: participants could fill in a web form with various questions about data before the workshop, or use provided laptops or worksheets (if uncomfortable with using laptops) at the workshop. Additionally, Glasgow stated that they think about accessibility (by public transport) when planning workshops and venues.

Shortcomings and challenges

A main challenge and resulting shortcoming related to involving all the people that were intended to be involved and thus actually ensuring inclusivity. The cities found it particularly challenging to reach local residents and diversity among them, which in their view resulted in a less legitimate process and results (see Section 3.2.2). Many cities stated the unfamiliarity with co-production and lack of participation culture as a barrier. Genk is critical about their level of diversity and representation of the population, especially of citizens with immigrant origin and disadvantaged groups. The cities also faced challenges in involving other actors, like actors from different departments, nature-based enterprises and private companies, and universities. A problem relates to a lack of awareness about and appreciation of co-production and collaboration, as well as rigid ways of working and other priorities. For example, Nicosia stated that universities may find it difficult to be involved because of existing time and research funding. It is necessary to make the process part of what universities are already doing. One of their strategies is to continuously think of new ways to reach out to actors and remain alert to new actors. A related challenge is keeping enthusiasm high in the long-term, especially when there are large gaps between different project phases (e.g. visioning and implementation).

Another challenge in some cities was to bring different actors together in one setting, such as actors from the city government and citizens. For several cities, there are existing conflicts between different communities or between citizens and the local governments. A basic problem is the different languages of municipality, community and business. It also links to problems in designing a process in a way that ensures equal participation and makes everyone feel safe in the context of asymmetrical power relations and divergent opinions and motives. For example, Malaga stated that it can be difficult to work in some areas on revitalisation because people who live in the area can be afraid of gentrification.

A final challenge concerns the availability of time and skills for identifying and mobilising actors as well as dealing with conflicts of divergent opinions, which the cities considered highly time intensive and as requiring constant attention.

3.2.2 Legitimacy: ensuring the process and results are accepted and relevant

Legitimate co-production foregrounds whether procedures and results of co-production are accepted by and relevant to participants and the wider urban actors (Matuk et al. 2020; Turnhout et al. 2019; Muñoz-Erickson et al. 2017).

What for and results

Legitimate co-production is important because it builds ownership over and trust in the process and the results (Djenontin and Meadow 2018; Campbell et al. 2016). In Glasgow, legitimacy has been critical from the beginning of the process, in order to create a sound knowledge base for the OSS that ensures political and societal buy-in (Box 4). Getting a good database for making decisions and clear data-based communication were considered most critical. This also meant it was important to ensure that the knowledge entering the process was trustworthy and reliable. Generating trust and ownership as well as support for process and results facilitates relationship-building and sound outputs and outcomes. Legitimate co-production also shields co-production from the risk of being politicised and captured by political agendas (Hölscher et al. 2019c). According to the Connecting Nature cities, legitimate co-production needs to ensure that democratic procedures are maintained.

Box 4: Legitimacy in Glasgow

In Glasgow, legitimacy has been critical from the beginning in order to create a sound knowledge base for the Open Space Strategy (OSS) that ensures political and societal buy-in. The OSS should serve as a strategic tool for planning, delivering and managing a network of existing and new nature-based solution projects in Glasgow. It aims to provide an overarching strategic vision for, and coordinate the responsibilities associated with, the open spaces to ensure a well-coordinated network of green spaces that offer multiple benefits and address multiple pressing challenges.

How to ensure legitimacy?

Ensuring legitimate co-production processes requires substantial *resources and skills* to mobilise and effectively engage with participants, process discussions and follow-up on agreements and results (Frantzeskaki 2022; Jaspers and Steen 2019; Chatterton et al. 2018). Co-production processes require diverse skills for design and facilitation, ranging from maintaining project flow and deadlines, organising meetings and venues, building trust, activating creativity, mediating conflict and power imbalances, and translating different knowledges (Reed and Abernethy 2018; Djenontin and Meadow 2018; Chatterton et al. 2018). Several cities sought to ensure there are the right skills by engaging professional facilitators or community engagement experts. They emphasised that it was important to have facilitators who are charismatic, trusted, objective, and embedded or knowledgeable about the local context.

Additionally, legitimate co-production processes need to **clearly define and be transparent with regards to their purpose, procedures, roles, responsibilities, content, and results** so that the participants and wider public are aware about what is going on and how decisions are made (Laktić and Malovrh 2018; Rosenström and Kyllonen 2006; Rowe and Frewer 2000). The (co-)definition of roles and responsibilities in the process gives clarity about what is expected from actors and helps them feel comfortable in their (new) roles and functions (Ferlie et al. 2019). Basic ground rules (e.g. timetables, procedures) give clarity to how discussions and data are treated (Ferlie et al. 2019; Frantzeskaki 2019; Chatterton et al. 2018). According to the cities, this also closely links to expectation management: it is important to be honest – aspirational but realistic – when communicating the goals and benefits about the co-production process when motivating citizens to participate. The cities have learned that otherwise there is a risk of participation fatigue, with participants ending up thinking “this is just another project by the city government, nothing will happen”. Additionally, the cities stated the importance of getting the right people involved and having one designated coordinator/coordinating group who is in charge of the process and ensures it keeps in line with goals. If responsibilities are not clearly defined, there is a risk that some withdraw into an advisory role, which has been experienced by some cities.

With diverse sources of knowledge being included, it is important to **uphold quality criteria** to check the reliability and credibility of knowledge and arguments entering the process (Reinecke 2015). Some cities did not work with this explicitly, such as doing source checks, but emphasised the need to involve recognised experts and legitimate data holders, such as the university or Chamber of Commerce and Technical Chamber in Ioannina. This links to inclusivity: In Poznań, for instance, it was important to include the police in the design of the open garden at the kindergarten to address questions of safety when opening the kindergarten garden to the public. Additionally, the facilitation of critical discussions on the input can help mediating different opinions and interests, thus generating better agreement and trust.

Shortcomings and challenges

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A main challenge for ensuring legitimacy concerned dealing with conflicts and divergent opinions and motivations, and doing so in a way that doesn't bypass democratic procedures. The cities recognised the danger of certain stakeholders getting involved for personal motives and objectives that don't align with the nature-based solution goals. The cities considered it overwhelming to deal with the "chaos" of multiple opinions when involving diverse actors. Relatedly, some cities struggled to clarify what will happen with the ideas of the participants in the process and ensure follow-up. In some cities, the actual scope for ideas for the design was limited due to strong opinions of experts or governmental actors involved about what were the most suitable options. As a result, many participants didn't trust in the process and that their opinions are taken into account. In other cases, citizens' demands were considered truly unfeasible.

Another challenge was the high amount of time required to obtain the right skills and expertise (e.g. for facilitation) as well as to collate and produce results in a way that is understandable for all.

3.2.3 Openness: collaborative learning and adaptation to new insights, knowledge and demands

Open co-production is about facilitating the exchange of knowledge, perceptions, values and desires in a way to allow new needs and solutions to emerge, and adaptation in line with those new insights. The openness principle draws attention to the need for actively communicating to, and engaging, diverse actors, as well as for being open to diverse actors and opinions.

What for and results

Open co-production is about establishing open learning environments that enable candid discussion based on mutual respect and trust and that remain open and adaptive to new actors, insights and knowledge that emerge as the co-production unfolds. Openness is important because it support engagement and trusting exchange, recognising that everyone's opinion matters, ensuring that results meet the needs and building shared ownership. This openness extends beyond the process and results, which becomes manifest in various engagement and outreaching activities to inform and involve actors (Box 5). Additionally, open co-production ensures continuous learning by regularly reflecting about goals, rules, actors involved, and engagement methods to ascertain whether adaptations are needed (Frantzeskaki and Kabisch 2016; Dentoni et al. 2016; Ferlie et al. 2019). In all cities, openness has been a critical principle in that regard, for example ensuring iterations of actor mapping and involvement and facilitating greater inclusivity. Nicosia stated as an important lesson learned, that in a co-production process it is not possible to be sure that the process will be the same at the start and the end; it is a living process. Genk emphasised that openness also facilitates recognising both barriers and opportunities throughout and navigating them.

Box 5: Openness in Genk

Genk emphasised the importance of creating a positive vibe for in-depth exchange and trust building as well as to maintain a high level of enthusiasm. An important strategy was to allocate dedicated personnel to social innovation as a way to ensure diverse engagement and outreaching activities and also enhance inclusivity.

To communicate about the process and engage more actors in the regeneration of the Stiemer valley, Genk developed a professional communication strategy with recognisable visual language to reach out to and involve stakeholders. For example, the logo that was designed for the Stiemer valley is used by an entrepreneur who is selling Stiemer ice-creams, which contributes to the visibility of the valley.

Additionally, in order to create support for co-production, the Genk team sought strong connections with the mayor. Despite struggling with rigid institutional procedures (e.g. including co-production in tenders), the city team successfully mainstreamed co-production in every aspect of implementing the Stiemer programme.

How to ensure openness?

Firstly, an open co-production process builds on an **open process setting** to enable candid and constructive knowledge exchange, disagreement and criticism (Hölscher et al. 2019c; Reed and Abernethy 2018; Frantzeskaki and Kabisch 2016). The cities sought to create, or complement other settings with informal settings and employ methods like the EMPath approach to facilitate participants' reflection on their own mind frames, understanding of conflicting and paradoxical paradigms, and open up to plurality of visions and solutions. They found that facilitators have an important role here, creating a creative, inspiring, and positive vibe.

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Co-production requires constant **adaptability** to respond to new insights, demands and needs (Chatterton et al. 2018; Muñoz-Erickson et al. 2017; Ferlie et al. 2019). According to the cities, this pertains to always keeping eyes open for new actors, ongoing refining of their used concepts and goals and revisiting the reasons for the co-production process and how it addresses local needs. This requires creating room to reflect, improvise and respond to new insights. All cities recognised the value of reflexive monitoring for this purpose (Section 4). Adaptability also extends beyond an individual process: Poznań has taken the experiences gained and lessons learned from past co-production processes and into consideration for current and future co-production processes.

Open co-production also requires **communication and sharing of knowledge** throughout about process and results, not only between the co-producers of knowledge but also to outsiders and potential newcomers. The cities employed diverse communication formats, tailored to specific target audiences. For instance, Burgas used their website and social media, events and press conferences. Similar to Genk (Box 5), Nicosia aims to develop a communication strategy and brand name for its exemplar: “Connecting Nicosia”. In Sarajevo, all co-production activities are followed by a journalist who writes articles about urban agriculture and promotes urban gardens on social media. It can help to engage different actors in communication efforts: In A Coruña, urban gardeners serve as community leaders who communicate the project to a wider audience. In Glasgow, the Thriving Places initiative acts as a medium to communicate the results of workshops back to the wider local community. Similar to when reaching out to and mobilising actors to participate in a co-production process, it was found important to be attentive to language. One of the barriers for implementing nature-based solutions is a lack of understanding what the concept actually means. For these reasons, it is important to increase awareness by developing different communication formats tailored to different audiences. In Glasgow, the language that is used to describe degraded open space or the colours that are used to show when open space is not in good condition. Malaga emphasised the importance of not being vague so there are no assumptions or new questions raised.

Co-production in general and ensuring open co-production specifically require **political and institutional support** to help secure resources for co-production, protect co-production from political and financial pressures, connect to existing processes and projects and navigate conflict (Bussu and Galanti 2018; Bianchi et al. 2021 Ziervogel et al. 2016; Voorberg et al. 2014). Especially within city governments, a supportive environment is essential to create organisational structures and mindsets for collaborative work – building on open mindsets and settings and reflexivity – that departs from conventional structures and procedures (Hölscher et al. 2019c; Hölscher 2018). Several cities sought to create space for co-production by establishing different forms of collaboration with other departments. They considered it important to invest time in informing people about the process and encourage them to take part in meetings. A Coruña sought to create openness and support by starting with small projects that have less risk of failure. Ioannina promoted their work in the election campaign to get political support. Similarly, the Genk Connecting Nature and Stiemer valley team had strong connections with the mayor. However, they also stated that tendering processes can be a problem when there is no clear mandate for co-production and the time investments. Nonetheless, co-production has become institutionalised as a standard that is considered for every aspect of implementing the Stiemer programme. Additionally, having deliberately chosen to allocate dedicated capacity to social innovation has boosted their co-production approach.

Shortcomings and challenges

The major challenge regarding ensuring open co-production in the cities was the difference between existing ways of working and thus ensuring political and institutional support and open mindsets – which is also reflected in challenges for ensuring the other process principles. (Open) co-production requires a lot of time investment, while conventional urban planning projects often require quick action. Additionally, co-production is open ended by definition, while the construction and engineering process is very specific and detailed. As a result, existing tendering processes can be a problem when there is no clear mandate for co-production and the time investments. The cities also name departmental siloes as a key barrier for advancing collaboration in general and co-production more specifically. This is exacerbated when multiple levels of government are involved, due to increased bureaucracy and lack of flexibility. While it was important to first create an understanding about what co-production means, but the cities still struggle to convey this to further people within the city government who don't believe in benefits of co-production and consider it a waste of time. In Genk, a success has been to set co-production as an important principle for the city and embedding it in the policy plan, thus ensuring political support – even though this ambition is not always translated into practice.

Another challenge concerns making time for communication and process adaptation and reaching beyond certain audiences. Additionally, it is time consuming to collate and produce results in a way that is understandable for all stakeholders, as well as to communicate the results. Constant attention is required to inform the public about the activities undertaken in the city. The complexity of the term ‘nature-based solutions’ has caused uncertainty as to how it should be introduced and communicated to other stakeholders. It was also found that communication depends on stage of process, as it is challenging to communicate results that are not consolidated/agreed upon yet.

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Finally, openness needs to be weighed against delivering co-production outputs and outcomes. There is the risk that by continuously adapting problem framings and solution options no concrete steps will be taken. It helps to manage expectations: decide together on a process for how to decide on changes.

3.2.4 Actionable knowledge: results are applicable in practice

Co-production represents a mechanism to bridge the plurality of knowledge and experiences of diverse urban actors and generate more holistic and socially robust knowledge that is embedded in a specific place, context and time, and helps addressing the wickedness of urban sustainability challenges (Brix et al. 2019; Boothroyd et al. 2017; Rogers and Weber 2010). The range of voices included can improve understanding of local issues and needs, fill data gaps and thus lead to more contextually relevant, credible and accepted policies, practices and solutions and increase ownership and accountability (Chatterton et al. 2018; Loeffler and Bovaird 2018; Demszky and Nassehi 2012).

What for and results

Actionable knowledge means that the co-produced outputs are immediately useful and applicable for urban actors, for example informing (new) policy and community goals and agendas, solutions and practices (cf. Caniglia et al. 2020; Frantzeskaki and Kabisch 2016; Jagannathan et al. 2020). In the Connecting Nature cities, actionable knowledge can refer to different objectives, depending on the type of co-production process and including the development of the OSS in Glasgow to the operational development of an urban garden in Sarajevo, which should also serve as a general concept for replication (Box 6). A main value of co-producing actionable knowledge is getting diverse input, adjusting to local needs and ideas, and closing data gaps, while stimulating local actors to actively participate and thus increase ownership of developed plans and solutions. The Pavlos Melas Metropolitan Park Strategy outlines the inclusive regeneration of the former military camp towards a green space, requiring input from diverse actors. In A Coruña, the open participatory process involving citizens, associations, architects and gardeners in the planning and delivery of the urban garden in the Adolfo Suarez Park resulted in a small building with a multifunctional common room and an outside area with a pergola to facilitate social interactions, because the gardeners emphasised that they don't have a dedicated area for gathering or even a shadowed area where to sit for a rest. In Genk, the set-up of Junior Teams resulted in the selection of three concrete projects that are going to be implemented in the Stierner valley in collaboration with the pupils and the city government. Actionable knowledge outcomes also refer to the applicability of generated knowledge for future projects as well as concern knowledge about how to design and implement co-production processes themselves. The Connecting Nature team in Poznań stated that having gone through the process enhanced their abilities to solve technical issues and gave them confidence to work with new tools because they know what to expect – even though emphasising that each case is different.

Box 6: Actionable knowledge outcomes in Sarajevo

In Sarajevo, SERDA has worked on the implementation of an urban garden within the "Children's House" area or "Centre for healthy ageing" area which are located near each other. This should be a sensory park which will provide the inhabitants of the city a place for relaxation, entertainment, learning and play, not forgetting people with special needs - children with intellectual and/or physical disabilities. The idea is that the communities of both the children's house and the Centre for healthy aging jointly create and maintain the garden and provide cross generational exchange.

The main aim of this project is to create a nature-based solution within the urban part of the city, which can function as a pilot project and can be replicated in other areas as well. The team has considered this from the start and made the outcomes actionable by ensuring that the design can be applied in other areas, and by linking the idea to issues that are important for the city as a whole and not only the two included organizations (e.g. lack of green spaces, air pollution, traffic, deforestation etc.).

How to generate actionable knowledge?

Generally, the generation of actionable knowledge closely links to ensuring the process principles, as indicated above, including inclusivity to make diverse knowledge available and legitimacy to create trust.

Actionable knowledge is **salient to urban needs**, meaning that the co-production process and results are relevant and useable to the needs and priorities of urban stakeholders. In the Connecting Nature cities, this closely links to ensuring motivation of participants to participate (see Section 3.2.1) as well as ownership over the process and results. Salience requires working knowledge of decision context and apprehension of different knowledge systems to situate co-

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production within the social, economic and ecological context and consider different needs and interests (Tangcharoensathien et al. 2021; Matuk et al. 2020; Reed and Abernethy 2018; Djenontin and Meadow 2018). For example, when aiming to implement a green classroom in Poznań, it was important to identify reasons why the green classroom closed in the past and how to prevent this from happening again.

Actionable knowledge requires **linking the co-production process to existing goals, processes and needs**. This requires considering what processes are going on in policy, businesses and local communities and checking how results of the co-production process could feed into other programmes. For example, Glasgow recognised that the statutory requirement for the OSS implementation in cities by the Scottish government is an opportunity to influence how data is collected about public space and how nature-based solutions are embedded. Ensuring such links also requires knowledge about formal rules and regulations as well as expert knowledge about design options and civic knowledge about local needs, thus linking back to the need to ensure inclusivity (Section 3.2.1). It has also been considered important to avoid problems of ownership and focus on areas with more freedom to act.

Additionally, an important condition for actionable knowledge is **prioritising knowledge transfer**: actionable outputs need to be taken up by others to make an impact on governance, processes and politics, for example to involve the community in using and stewarding nature-based solutions, motivate replication of processes and solutions and ensure long-term maintenance (Buijs et al. 2018). For this, it is important to know the ‘relevant’ actors, for instance across different departments and governance scales, and reach out to them to inform them about the results. Genk used the momentum in policy planning to make use of the created knowledge in the Stiemer programme and gain support from the mayor and aldermen to embed results into policy planning. In Poznań, the conference on open gardens aided the sharing of knowledge and information: Kindergarten directors and teachers were able to visualise what nature-based solutions look like through presentations at the conference. This enabled them to understand the idea of nature-based solutions more effectively, creating a larger interest in the project. While this links to communication about the process, it is more targeted communication about design concepts and a nature-based solution catalogue as a guidebook of good practices for those interested in co-designing and co-implementing open gardens and natural playgrounds in Poznań.

Shortcomings and challenges

There is a general risk that co-production efforts are wasted when they remain unused or when results are ‘cherry-picked’ (Bovaird and Loeffler 2013; Demszky and Nassehi 2012). Co-produced results often don’t get taken up at the policy level due to discrepancies between informal co-production processes and the formal institutional context and different requirements for achieving administrative and legal legitimacy (Ferlie et al. 2019; Jaspers and Steen 2019). A challenge faced by some Connecting Nature cities related to integrating the co-production process into the regular way of working to assure the uptake of knowledge, because co-production processes are often something extra next to the standard procedure. Often, there is a need for political approval so that it is not possible to guarantee the implementation of ideas and agreements. The problem becomes bigger when multiple government levels are involved and bureaucracy increases, as it takes more time before an idea gets implemented (risking to lose momentum). Also, political elections can create uncertainty.

3.2.5 Empowerment of participants

Participating in co-production may empower actors to take active roles in developing and managing solutions for service delivery, for example by becoming ambassadors of the results, collaborating and taking their own initiative (Ma et al. 2019; Jaspers and Steen 2019; Brix et al. 2019).

What for and results

Participating in co-production processes enables actors to exchange and enrich their perspectives, develop new relationships, and learn new ways of applying their knowledge. All cities stated empowerment as one of their main objectives, in order to create a shared sense of belonging to the nature-based solution and to engage diverse actors in the long-term stewardship and use of the nature-based solution. For example, Glasgow seeks to engage communities in contributing to open space development, while Nicosia aims to involve citizens in the maintenance of green areas. A Coruña aims to develop a bottom-up governance model for the self-management of gardens (Box 7). Genk has introduced the Stiemer deals as innovative mechanism to invite citizens, organisations, knowledge institutions, companies, project developers to play an active role in the development of the Stiemer valley. For example Crème Le Lis & Nostalgie, an ice cream company from the valley, developed a Stiemer-ice-cream inspired by a Friend of the Stiemer. This was a great success for the ice-cream entrepreneur, who became an ambassador for the Stiemer programme. Empowerment also

addresses changing relations between actors and between humans and nature. A Coruña, Málaga and Sarajevo aim to facilitate intergenerational and intercultural relationships to enhance social cohesion through their urban gardens. Several cities also actively involve children for environmental education.

Box 7: Empowerment in A Coruña

A Coruña is aiming to facilitate the self-management of the ecoHortas by its users. This has been supported by an expert trainer and facilitator of collaborative processes and team work who organised workshops and advised users with the objective of facilitating the provision of operation norms and the election of a Management Committee for each of the urban gardens. At the same time, the municipality offered training in the field of organic agriculture to users of ecoHortas, with theoretical classes, practical workshops at the ecoHortas and an online platform in which users can ask their questions. In three municipal urban gardens associations of gardeners were created (“De leira na leira”) to manage the plots better (more direct contact, on the ground, with less bureaucracy). There will also be one dedicated person from the municipality to assist the gardeners.

How to generate empowerment of participants?

How co-production can promote empowerment also closely depends on how the process is designed and implemented, by creating space for social learning, building trust, connecting with likeminded people and prompting reflection on roles and responsibilities (Hölscher et al. 2019c; Guemes and Jorge 2019). For example, citizen co-producers can feel motivated by the appreciation they receive to contribute to society, by enhanced ownership and a sense of belonging and solidarity with other co-producers (Jaspers and Steen 2019; Loeffler and Bovaird 2018; Ferlie et al. 2019; Mattor et al. 2020). Specific methods that facilitate openness, like the EM|Path approach can support empowerment (Sections 3.1.2 and 3.2.3). In Sarajevo, Nicosia and A Coruña, the process was found unique as a new way of working that created a sense of connectedness, helped the participants to express themselves and speaking not only their thoughts but also their feelings. Sarajevo aims to employ the process with children to develop their awareness about nature from an early age.

Several co-production processes resulted in, or were connected to the **definition of new roles and responsibilities** that would relate to the nature-based solutions such as urban gardens in the long-term. This is particularly visible in the formalised groups and tactical settings such as the set-up of urban gardeners’ associations for self-management of urban gardens in A Coruña and the “Friends of the Stiemer” in Genk (Section 3.1.2). To facilitate empowerment, especially in the long-term, it is important that responsibilities and roles are co-defined and shared. In Málaga, the stewardship use of the garden was split among two associations (Lagunillas Neighbours Association and Association Fantasia) to guarantee activities for schools and the elderly. The lease was set for a year with a calendar of meetings between both associations and the environmental department with the aim to control the development of the activities. In the Stiemer deals in Genk, the role and task distribution between city and stakeholders is made explicit in the deal, custom designed and depending on the deal.

Additionally, several cities (plan to) **organise continuous engagement activities** that can sustain momentum and commitment as well as involve new actors. The cities recognise the need to keep involvement and enthusiasm alive. Sarajevo plans to organise an urban garden Monday in the urban garden in the Children’s House with an open call to citizens and specific target groups and organisations (e.g. Centre for Healthy Aging) to organise workshops connected with the garden. In Genk, the Genk Stiemert programme organises a lot of activities connected to the Stiemer valley together with diverse people, including an exhibition of an artist who work in the valley. The Stiemer Hub, part of the pilot project Gardens of Waterschei, aims to link other projects to the valley (e.g. making ice cream or honey) to enrich its development.

Several cities emphasise the need to **strengthen community capacities** for empowerment. For example, Glasgow recognised capacity gaps in community organisations to develop and maintain projects and started to collaborate with colleagues from the Neighbourhoods and Sustainability Department to facilitate community capacity building. As part of workshop outputs, information on toolkits for community capacity building and nature-based solution guidance is being collected. In A Coruña, the self-management of the ecoHortas by its users has been supported by expert trainings on self-management and organic agriculture (Box 7). Additionally, several cities facilitate the development of educational projects related to their urban gardens. For example, the urban garden in A Coruña is available to NGOs to develop educational projects and support citizen engagement. A new information point was created by the municipality to provide advice, support, information and workshops for citizens interested in urban gardens. A new pilot project to implement gardens in schools and organise educational activities seeks to integrate the urban gardens into school curricula. The Stiemer deals required additional resources and capacity. The active search for deals is done by the social innovation

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project leader for deals with citizens, associations, civil society etc., and by the business development consultant for deals with companies, governments, investment companies, etc.

Shortcomings and challenges

The risks of *disempowerment* as a result of co-production processes are well-documented in literature (Turnhout et al. 2019; Avelino 2009; Hölscher et al. 2019c). Co-production risks to position citizenship as ‘gap filling’ and “dumping on service users, carers and other citizens some of the most difficult tasks of the state” (Loeffler and Bovaird 2018: 275; see also Bussu and Galanti 2018). Additionally, co-production can increase a sense of powerlessness, reinforce existing power structures and marginalise certain groups further when unaware of the politics underlying co-production processes, including questions of who participates, what values, perspectives and interests do the participants represent and who dominates the process (Turnhout et al. 2019; Bussu and Galanti 2018; Chatterton et al. 2018; Ferlie et al. 2019). This was recognised by some Connecting Nature cities, related to participation fatigue due to previous unsuccessful co-production experiences that didn’t see follow up after some temporary results. A central challenge thus recognised relates to maintaining high levels of motivation and engagement. Also due to limited experience with co-production, some cities struggled to think about what empowerment means, especially in the long-term, and how to ensure that. This further links to concerns about how to deal with political struggles and different opinions, manage expectations and keeping momentum high, which has been discussed in previous sections.

3.2.6 Aligning actors and agendas for synergies

Co-production can serve as a mediating process between diverse actors holding otherwise fragmented knowledge, interests and responsibilities. For example, a co-production process on nature-based solutions can end up to also include discussions on food, mobility and air quality in the city and thus mobilise their potential as multifunctional solutions to address multiple policy and societal priorities and goals simultaneously (Frantzeskaki et al. 2020). Transformative nature-based solutions, which provide multiple benefits and are multifunctional by design, require searching for how different problems and goals relate to one another.

What for and results

Co-production processes can lead to alignment of agendas by making synergies visible, connecting and embedding co-production results across multiple urban policy, planning and community strategies and agendas, as well as facilitating cross-cutting collaboration for mobilising resources across multiple priorities. In this way, it can help crossing siloes and making the nature-based solution agenda relevant for broader priorities and strategies such as air pollution, mobility and recreation and thus boost synergies and pool resources (Box 8; Bianchi et al. 2021; Frantzeskaki 2019; Ferlie et al. 2019). A major transformation point in Glasgow was the adoption of the OSS by the city council, making it a key consideration for any development of Glasgow’s open spaces. Such alignment facilitates new collaborations and governance modes as well as generates political support. In A Coruña, collaboration with the education department provided links to schools and kindergarten as places for urban gardens and collaboration with the employment department enabled training courses on urban gardening, thus ensuring multifunctional delivery. The city’s info point on urban agriculture involves four different departments (Environment, Education, Employment, Tourism and Markets). The nature-based solutions concept supports opening up discourses for collaboration and combine budgets of multiple departments. In Glasgow, the OSS was used to provide a framework for cross-departmental collaboration and financing by formalising meetings with key officers focusing on the 15 themes of the strategy. In Sarajevo, the urban garden and sensory park at the Secondary Vocational Education and Training School is managed by the International Centre for Children and Youth Novo Sarajevo, Children’s House, which has a right to use this part of the land although it is public land. The centre also maintains this area (e.g. cutting, cleaning) on a voluntary basis.

Box 8: Aligning actors and agendas in Genk

The development of nature-based solutions in the Stiemer valley in Genk is connected to the masterplan for the area. One pilot project within the masterplan, Gardens of Waterschei, is closely linked to the upgrading of the brand identity of the nearby trading street, the Stalenstraat, by the economic department. Developing a joint, integrated plan could enhance the result of both projects. This plan would be developed in co-production with the stakeholders of the projects – Stalenstraat dealers, service economy, Department of Environment, Natuurpunt, Friends of the Stiemer, neighbours, and neighbourhood development service.

The principle of aligning ideas came to practice through various conversations on both projects (Stiemer valley and Stalenstraat), in which the Stiemer valley inspired the project of the Stalenstraat and developed their knowledge further. Additionally, it was important to include colleagues from both projects in each other's workshops. As a result, the designs of both area's include innovations (e.g. recreational areas, gateways, bridges) that connect the two area's better.

How to align actors and agendas?

Firstly, the cities sought to **connect and embed their strategic nature-based solution goals and agendas with other goals, agendas and planning documents** of the city government to the agendas of local groups of citizens, businesses etc. (Box 8, see also Ferlie et al. 2019; Jaspers and Steen 2019). In Nicosia, the Local Strategic Sustainable Development Plan and Integrated Spatial Development Strategy (OXA) include the proposal for the urban garden network. As thus, the open garden network is linked to the spatial framework of the area and budgets were ensured. Additionally, the creation of the urban garden network in Nicosia including the development of active mobility connections between plans is aligned with sustainable transport policy, health and wellbeing to ensure links across multiple goals and agendas. In Pavlos Melas, the nature-based solution is linked to the historical importance of the region for Thessaloniki, increasing the relevance of making the park a cultural centre. Such connection and the embedding of nature-based solution strategies also facilitates replication and scaling. Poznań linked its nature-based solution upscaling strategies to the Department of Education's agenda to modernise playgrounds. In Genk, the Stiemer valley programme was promoted as the flagship project within the adaptation policy of the city: a programme in which new strategies can be tested and demonstrated. Nature-based solutions are now being mainstreamed in the next policy round and social and ecological benefits of nature-based solutions are being increasingly recognised and adopted across city departments. This includes transfer of the nature-based solution concept to a new flagship project climate-proofing the city centre through greening. In Glasgow, the OSS has contributed to embedding a place-based approach with nature-based solutions in policy to create a climate adaptive city.

Additionally, aligning actors and agendas, requires **nurturing collaboration across multiple urban projects and agendas** so as to bridge traditionally disconnected knowledge and processes. Several activities were important to establish and nurture the various forms of collaboration and coordination (see also Deliverable 6, Hölscher et al. 2022). Firstly, it was important to identify the key actors and enablers for collaboration based on shared interests. For example, in A Coruña, an important enabler was the participation of the employment department in an Urbact project on urban agriculture, which made it easy to cooperate with them on urban gardening. It also helped transfer good practices on urban agriculture. Moreover, good communication was thought to be key, especially to overcome existing barriers for collaboration such as departmental siloes and diverging goals. In Nicosia, a professional mediator was appointed for these purposes, who was responsible for coordinating the discussion and the communication between the different stakeholders involved in each phase of the project. Depending on the audience, roundtable discussions, workshops or presentations have taken place with clusters of stakeholders (e.g. mayors, engineers). To facilitate good communication and trust building, cities have implemented eye opener workshops and Sarajevo and Nicosia employed the EM|Path approach (see Section 3.1.2 and Xidou et al. 2022). For cross-departmental collaboration, high level meetings with key political responsible persons from different departments were important. For example, it can be beneficial to form alliances with senior decision-makers to help navigate processes that can have unwritten rules and important power relations. Additionally, cross-departmental collaboration is often facilitated by fostering direct relations with individuals from different departments and creating informal spaces for communication and knowledge transfer. In Genk, to reach out to other city projects and establish collaboration, it created the Stiemerloft: a creative working space where all the maps, results of workshops, process charts and other material are put up on the walls. As the room is frequently used by others, this knowledge is visible and hopefully useable for other agendas or stimulates synergies. Genk also established a participatory steering group that is made up of several city departments to scale up participatory processes across departments. Similarly, Burgas sets up cross-departmental teams for strategic and operational collaboration.

The new collaborations are supported by and **manifest in new collaborative governance modes**. New governance approaches and collaborations can emerge between city governments and other groups of stakeholders (local citizens, businesses, researchers etc.) (Frantzeskaki and Kabisch 2016). Nicosia, due to the nature of the exemplar comprising multiple parks, plans to establish a semi-governmental body incorporated by law, which will be responsible for planning and delivery, coordinating the involved actors, as well as monitoring and reporting on the nature-based solution and other development projects in the District of Nicosia. The aim is to reform existing centralised governance towards more decentralised decision-making in the municipalities. In several cities, new working relations were formalised. In Genk, city-wide thematic working groups were established to facilitate discussions with responsible actors in relation to 'safe-guarding' the vision of the masterplan during project development. They also create new working dynamics, creating direct collaborations with external partners that would previously have been managed by another department. It is

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important to clarify responsibilities and split for instance leadership and financial participation. Additionally, several cities emphasised that it is important to avoid problems of ownership.

Finally, alignment is visible in the **investment in organisational capacities**. In Poznań, it was found that scaling-up nature-oriented playgrounds, also the scaling of skills and ‘green agents’ were identified across city departments to ensure influence beyond the immediate team. In Genk, recruitment of human resources was expanded to work both within and beyond the Stiemer valley programme. In Glasgow, the Scottish UrbanByNature Hub aims to drive knowledge exchange and build capacity in relation to nature-based solution implementation amongst several stakeholder organisations including statutory nature, environment, and planning organisations, and local authority network representatives.

Shortcomings and challenges

A key starting challenge for aligning actors and agendas in all cities has been siloes within the city governments, characterised by hierarchical municipal structures and lack of collaboration between different departments that hinders the implementation of integrated strategies. This is exacerbated by some inter-departmental rivalry, lack of clear responsibilities and of trust, as well as competition for political support and resources. Many cities also struggled to involve the private sector in wider and new forms of collaboration. As a result, there is no sharing of knowledge and distributed expertise, no wide awareness about nature-based solutions and limited collaborative financing. Relatedly, another central barrier the cities faced refers to the complex or fragmented ownership structures and rigid bureaucratic processes, manifesting in some levels of inflexibility and challenging permission-seeking procedures. This could be mitigated by strategically selecting sites for the nature-based solutions, changing regulations and tendering processes and establishing collaborations across multiple levels of governments and public-private partnerships. For instance, in Ioannina, Pirsinela Park was selected because the municipality is the sole managing authority and it isn’t governed by strict laws that don’t allow significant changes, which may restrain the possibilities for intervention.

4 Results: how the cities worked with reflexive monitoring and what was learned

Here, we present our results on how the cities have worked with reflexive monitoring and what we have learned for the guidebook, as well as how we have distilled learning outcomes (Front-Runner Cities) and learning objectives (Fast-Follower Cities) for all elements of the Connecting Nature Framework (the implications from this about how the cities have implemented the Connecting Nature Framework are presented in Deliverable 6 (Hölscher et al. 2022)).

We have developed a step-by-step reflexive monitoring method to support processes of ongoing learning-by-doing and doing-by-learning in terms of goals achievement, adopting lessons learned and identifying needs for adaptation when planning, delivering and stewarding nature-based solutions. Nature-based solutions planning, delivery, and stewardship requires ongoing reflection about who is involved, who isn’t, and who benefits and who doesn’t, as well as adaptability to respond to new insights, demands and needs (Chatterton, et al. 2018; Ferlie et al. 2019; Muñoz-Erickson et al. 2017). It cannot be a ‘blueprint’ planned beforehand. In addition, the context might change, new opportunities and barriers may present themselves. Therefore, existing evaluation methods are insufficient because they leave little room for collaborative learning, experimentation and adaptations during the planning, delivery and stewardship phase of the nature-based solution. For example, only after a problem or solution is identified, a monitoring and evaluation process is designed, indicators are selected to measure the effectiveness of the project(s) after implementation.

As described in 2.1 and 2.2, the Front-Runner Cities and the Fast-Follower Cities had a different way of getting introduced to and working with the reflexive monitoring method and tools. Based on our work with the cities and other partners in the Connecting Nature project, we developed a six steps process for cities who want to work with reflexive monitoring (Box 9). This process is described in detail in the practical guide (Lodder et al. 2022).

Box 9: The six steps of Reflexive Monitoring

Step 1: Rethink. This step emphasises that implementing large scale nature-based solutions requires new ways of working, thinking and organising. Practitioners who work with nature-based solutions have to change old habits. This is not an easy process, therefore we advise to start creating time for reflection, to verify whether you and your team are still working on the right things in the right way. Making the time to collectively reflect upon the changing context increases the reflexivity of the practitioners.

Step 2: Roles. Roles will change by working with reflexive monitoring. The method introduces new roles to not only focus on *what* needs to happen but also on *how* things need to happen and *why*. In short, the most important new role is that of the reflexive monitor. Someone responsible for steering the learning process of the team. The second role is that of the reflexive monitoring coach to teach how to apply the tools, supports different facilitation techniques and attitudes, and introduce the skills the team needs to remain in a reflexive mindset during the process. The other roles within the reflexive monitoring team are the project leader and other team members.

Step 3: Record. Recording lessons learnt is important when co-producing nature-based solutions because it requires a lot of learning in a short time. Working with the three tools we selected gives you and others insight into how to deal with barriers, find out how effective you are, and keep an eye out for potential collaborators.

- A. **Timeline of events** helps practitioners to record their learnings by recording all main events that occur and filter out the most important moments, insights or events that influence the nature-based solution process.
- B. **Timeline meeting** allows your reflexive monitoring team to discuss the timeline(s) of events and filter out which events are crucial for continuing your process (**critical turning points**).
- C. **Dynamic Learning Agenda** captures the results of your timeline meeting to record and trace the reflexive learning process. The agenda presents critical turning points connected to learning questions and follow-up actions. The goal of the Dynamic Learning Agenda is to link the long-term goals of the nature-based solution to learning objectives and concrete short-term actions.

Step 4: Analyse. When you work with the reflexive monitoring tools on a regular basis, the Dynamic Learning Agenda changes over time. Turning points are added, learning questions are answered and new questions are emerging. To evaluate the impact of this learning and report on the value of this learning process to project outsiders we analyse it during a learning session.

- D. **Learning session.** A learning session increases the understanding of how to ‘do’ reflexive monitoring (part I) and analyse the reflexivity of your learnings (part II). We call these learning outcomes: innovative ways the team handles the barriers or opportunities captured in the Dynamic Learning Agenda in terms of novel rules, relations, practices, and discourses.

Step 5: Communicate. Reflexive monitoring is a novel governance process with valuable lessons to share with other actors inside and outside your organisation. We selected two tools to communicate about what you learned.

- E. **Personal learning narratives.** Stories that describe the learning journey throughout the process may revolve around an experience, a barrier, a struggle, or a challenge. These personal stories can be shared in different ways, and you may find that they resonate very differently and are remembered really well. For example, record a video about the learning journey, post it on social media or play it at an eye-opener workshop.
- F. **Eye-opener workshop.** Share what is learned from with people who are not yet involved in your project. Your experiences might really benefit colleagues from other departments, people in the mayor’s office or professionals working with co-production or nature-based solutions. This workshop prevents ‘project outsiders’ don’t have to learn everything the hard way and it might give them learning objectives for their own context or projects. For the project team, the workshop will result in new ways to communicate their lessons to those not yet involved in the project. You may get a great blog or website text out of it, for instance.

Step 6: Reflect. This step helps you and your team to reflect on the effectiveness of reflexive monitoring itself, to share your experience of working through the various steps and using the tools, and hear what others thought.

- G. **Learning Experience Events.** This event is organised to facilitate sharing the experiences of different teams that work with reflexive monitoring and are supported by the same (group of) experts/researchers. The exchange focusses on a) how the teams work with the reflexive monitoring method and b) how to reflect on their learning outcomes.
- H. **Learning Platform.** A learning platform facilitates exchange between organisations with different levels of reflexive monitoring experience that are working on similar topics, like nature-based solutions. The platform structure for Connecting Nature was specifically designed to facilitate learning between Front-Runner Cities and Fast-Follower Cities but can be used as a basis to facilitate other types of peer-to-peer learning.

As Figure 6 visualises, steps 3 and 4 are repeated on a (bi-)monthly basis. The entire sequence of step 1-6 is repeated every 6-12 months. In the guidebook you can find graphics explaining each step visually.

Figure 6: The reflexive monitoring steps

In the following, we first describe and analyse how the cities have worked with reflexive monitoring, distinguishing between how the Front-Runner Cities and Fast-Follower Cities have worked with the method and including reflections on the feasibility of the approach for the cities (Section 4.1). Section 4.2 presents the learning outcomes of the Front-Runner Cities, by analysing the reflexivity changes of the learning and how the learning outcomes are connected to the Connecting Nature Framework Elements. In Section 4.3 we present the learning objectives of the Fast-Follower Cities, and analyse to what extent these learning objectives were shared among them and led to further insights or precursors to reflexivity changes.

4.1 How the cities worked with reflexive monitoring

4.1.1 How the Front-Runner Cities worked with reflexive monitoring

We use the six-steps process of the reflexive monitoring as presented in the guidebook and Box 9 to elaborate on how the Front-Runner Cities worked with reflexive monitoring.

Step 1: Rethink. This has been part of many workshops and meetings in the first two years of the Connecting Nature project (Deliverable 4, Hölscher et al. 2019a). Once the cities started working with reflexive monitoring this became a recurring topic of discussion during the reflexive monitoring learning sessions. The Front-Runner Cities also reported about this step in the Connecting Nature Framework reports (Deliverable 5, Hölscher et al. 2019b).

Step 2: Roles and Step 3: Record. These steps are applied differently by each city. The Front-Runner Cities started working with these steps of reflexive monitoring in their project teams as off September 2018. In the first year they decided who would take to role of the reflexive monitor and how the tools fit their existing meeting structure.

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Genk, who had prior experience with the method, supported the other cities by explaining how they capture the important events in their individual bullet journals (page 34 in Lodder et al. 2022) and how they translate these into critical turning points. In Genk this was done as a team effort, during a learning session they organised that resulted in their Dynamic Learning Agenda that was shared with DRIFT. Genk also made a template for the Dynamic Learning Agenda (Lodder et al. 2022, STEP 3 – TOOL C1 – Dynamic Learning Agenda template extended version) that the other Front-Runner Cities used as a basis for their Dynamic Learning Agenda.

In Poznań, the city team decided not to set-up a different structure for reflexive monitoring. They already had a weekly meeting with the main project team and the reflexive monitor used that meeting to capture the most important events. After the team meeting, she individually translated the topics into critical turning points and learning questions on their Dynamic Learning Agenda as of September 2018 (page 40 in Lodder et al. 2022).

In Glasgow, the team changed during the first year which made them start a bit later. Once the team was on full capacity in October 2019, they decided that two team members would work with the reflexive monitoring tools. Around May 2020, we felt they were settled into their way of working with reflexive monitoring. They used the tools to prepare and evaluate a cross-departmental meeting with their colleagues. After this meeting the two reflexive monitors sat together to translate the topics into critical turning points and learning questions on their Dynamic Learning Agenda (page 37 in Lodder et al., 2022 on how Glasgow worked with the critical turning points).

Step 4: Analyse. We (researchers from DRIFT) started this step of the process in the background between September 2018 and May 2019 (Deliverable 4, Hölscher et al. 2019a), based on the notes from the learning sessions (see Appendix C for a complete overview of all the learning sessions organised for the Front-Runner Cities). During the learning sessions the cities used their Dynamic Learning Agenda as a tool to update the researchers of the different Connecting Nature Framework Elements about the critical turning points, learning questions that they have and follow-up actions they wanted to undertake. The researchers all read the Dynamic Learning Agenda before the learning session and wrote down questions. DRIFT facilitated the meeting and asked the questions of the researcher when the cities finished a topic on the agenda. There was also room for the researchers to directly interact or give suggestions or examples on specific questions or actions. As of May 2019, the cities were all familiar with the Dynamic Learning Agenda and formulating learning questions and critical turning points. The learning sessions ranged from 1-2 hours every month to a bi-monthly two-hour session. The last 30 minutes DRIFT and the city-teams used to analyse the learning outcomes based on the notes that DRIFT made. During the next two years (May 2019-June 2021) of the project, we followed this structure. In the beginning we used the 30 minutes to formulate and validate whether the learning took place already or it was a potential learning the cities recognised. After some time, more learning took place in practice, and it was more apparent what the learning outcomes were. At the end, the cities could formulate their learning outcomes themselves (see page 46 in Lodder et al. 2022) on the value of the learning sessions for Genk.

Step 5: Communicate. The Front-Runner Cities applied both tools. We as researchers from DRIFT asked the cities to write personal learning narratives about specific tools of reflexive monitoring. These narratives we used to select the examples for the guidebooks and to evaluate the feasibility of working with reflexive monitoring (later in this section). The eye-opener workshop was organised by once by Poznań and multiple times by Genk. Poznań used the workshop to include more colleagues in their work. The workshop helped them to unlock cross-departmental collaboration around various nature-based solutions in the city (page 46 in Lodder et al. 2022). Genk used the eye-opener workshop to update their mayor and head of the department about their learning outcomes (page 72-73 in Lodder et al. 2022).

Step 6: Reflect. Was organised for the Front-Runner Cities by the researchers from DRIFT. During the learning experience webinars (see Appendix C for a complete overview of all learning experience webinars), we reflected upon how the cities worked with specific tools of the reflexive monitoring process. The cities actively participated in these webinars by sharing their experiences with the tools and giving each other advice or inspire each other by sharing their best practises. In the second part of the webinar we (researchers from DRIFT) presented the cross-case analysis of the learning outcomes of the three cities. Starting with 2-3 selected learning outcomes from all cities and to which Connecting Nature Framework Element and reflexivity categories they related. We discussed the differences and similarities between the cities on the innovations they established of each of the Connecting Nature Framework Element (see Section 4.3 and Deliverable 6, Hölscher et al. 2022). We also discussed the reflexivity categories with the cities and the differences and specific order in which the reflexivity increased in time (Section 4.3). The cities found these webinars very valuable, see for example pages 61 and 73 in Lodder et al. 2022 on how Glasgow experienced ‘light bulb moments’.

In preparation of the Learning Platform Webinars the Front-Runner Cities participated in 1-on-1 learning sessions with 2-3 Fast-Follower Cities (see Table 3). As the Front-Runner Cities are more experienced with working with reflexive monitoring, they facilitated the learning session similar to the role of DRIFT in step 4. The Fast-Follower Cities just

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started working with the method and they prepared their DLA based on step 3. For both cities these 1-on-1 meeting were valuable because through exchanging how they worked with the method both cities got more grip on the method and the value of using it in their daily activities. Additionally, they learned more about each other's nature-based solution (see Appendix C for a complete overview of all the 1-on-1 learning sessions). During Learning Platform Webinars (see Appendix C for a complete overview of all learning platform webinars), the Front-Runner Cities participated as members of the Knowledge Hubs (see Deliverable 6, Hölscher et al. 2022) to share their learning outcomes on the different Connecting Nature Framework Elements with the Fast-Follower Cities. During these break-out sessions they also learned from discussing the learning objectives of the Fast-Follower Cities.

Table 3: Grouping of 1-on-1 learning sessions based on dominant Connecting Nature Framework Elements in the planning phase (see also Deliverable 4.1: Xidous et al., 2021)

Planning phase	FFC	FRC
Co-Production & Reflexive Monitoring	Pavlos Melas	Genk
	Burgas	
Governance	Malaga	Glasgow
	A Coruña	
	Sarajevo	
Technical solutions	Ioannina	Poznań
	Nicosia	

4.1.2 How the Fast-Follower Cities worked with reflexive monitoring

Step 1: Rethink. This step was included during the Knowledge transfer workshops in Nicosia and Malaga and continued to be included in the Knowledge Transfer – Phase 2. We (researchers from DRIFT) also organised various webinars and 1-on-1 sessions to introduce the reflexive monitoring framework to the Fast-Follower Cities (see Appendix C for a complete overview), with an emphasis on this step. In their Connecting Nature Framework reports (see Deliverable 6, Hölscher et al. 2022), the cities included their learning questions and described their barriers and opportunities.

Step 2: Roles and Step 3: Record. During the Knowledge transfer workshops in Nicosia January 2019, the FFC RM in practice 1-on-1 webinars in June 2019 and the Knowledge transfer workshops in Malaga October 2019 the Fast-Follower Cities were introduced to the reflexive monitoring framework and asked to distribute the roles over their teams. The cities also practiced drafting a Dynamic Learning Agenda during a workshop of the AGM in Malaga October 2019. Once the Knowledge Transfer – Phase 2 was completed (Deliverable 4.1, Xidous et al. 2021), the cities started drafting their first learning in the survey in preparation of the Learning Platform Webinar #0 in October 2020. This was also the time all Fast-Follower Cities selected someone in the team as reflexive monitor. Before their first 1-on-1 learning session with the Front-Runner city (see Table 3 above), they shared their first completed Dynamic Learning Agenda in the simplified format (see Lodder et al. 2022, STEP 3 – TOOL C2 – Dynamic Learning Agenda template simple version). Two researchers from DRIFT and TDC participated in these learning sessions for notetaking only (no active and/or felicitating role). This was repeated three times. In total each Fast-Follower city made three versions of their Dynamic Learning Agenda.

The cities each did this in their own way, so it fitted in their existing meeting structure. Most cities worked with reflexive monitoring within the complete project group that worked on Connecting Nature (Ioannina, Sarajevo, A Coruña) or in the smaller core team (Pavlos Melas, Burgas). Malaga aimed to use reflexive monitoring to change their meeting structure within the municipality completely, including have everyone increase their reflexivity, inspired by the presentation of Genk (Knowledge transfer workshops in Nicosia January 2019). But this step was too big and based on the experience in the Front-Runner Cities it was more effective to start with selected strategic meetings first. A Coruña also used reflexive monitoring as a basis for meetings with cross-departmental groups including people from other departments and the Local Urban Garden group to raise awareness and get more people on board. In Sarajevo, participants in the reflexive monitoring process included actors from other departments in City of Sarajevo, SERDA, University of Sarajevo, NGOs and the Children's House that are partners of the exemplar.

Step 4: Analyse. The notes of the 1-on-1 learning sessions were used by the DRIFT researchers to analyse the learning objectives of the Fast-Follower Cities (see Section 2.2). this analysis was presented during the Learning Platform Webinars (see step 6).

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Step 5: Communicate. The Fast-Follower Cities worked on their personal learning narrative on how they work with the Connecting Nature Framework. To support the cities, we (DRIFT) organised Connecting Nature Framework narrative workshop together with partners from TCD, BioAzul, UEL and Climate Alliance in May 2021 (see Appendix C for a complete overview of all workshops). This resulted in recorded presentations by every Fast-Follower and Front-Runner city that were shown during the Learning Platform Webinar #3 and #4 and can be found in Box 10.

Box 10: Personal learning narratives of the cities on how they worked with the Connecting Nature Framework

Genk: <https://youtu.be/-UaoY3ME1iA>
Poznań: <https://youtu.be/xNcRAze39Oc>
Glasgow: <https://youtu.be/bEyF6pt-cs>
A Coruña: https://youtu.be/x5yeivy1_L0
Burgas: <https://youtu.be/PazHCQzeWb4>
Pavlos Melas: <https://youtu.be/vqTyAEfdi6k>
Nicosia: <https://youtu.be/LoP8Rfmqg1w>
Sarajevo: <https://youtu.be/4mLadSUMI2U>

In their Connecting Nature Framework reports (see Deliverable 6, Hölscher et al. 2022), cities recognise the value of the narratives they created for communicating one appealing story to the citizens and gaining political support. In Ioannina, they used it to prepare the proposal for securing the budget for our project through national funds. A Coruña used the narrative to explain their project in an event organised by A Coruña City Council in collaboration with the National Point of the URBACT Program. They valued how the narrative helped them to convey information in a more accessible way. It was useful as a starting point to make new contacts and networking with different stakeholders.

Step 6: Reflect. This step was organised for the Fast-Follower Cities with the Learning Platform Webinars. They looked at the analysis of their learning objectives before the webinar and selected the learning objectives of other cities they recognised (see also Section 2.2). During the break-out sessions of the webinars the cities talked with the Knowledge Hub experts of the Connecting Nature Framework Elements about the selected learning objectives. This helped them to further in their learning process in different ways. The cities listened to examples of other cities and from the experts that inspired them on how to continue and/or the Knowledge Hub coordinators organised activities around the selected learning objectives.

4.2 Learning outcomes of the Front-Runner Cities Genk, Glasgow and Poznań

The analysis learning sessions of the Front-Runner Cities (see Section 2.2 for method) resulted in three different analyses that show all the innovations the Front-Runner Cities worked on during the Connecting Nature project. Section 4.2.1 presents the critical turning points and learning questions of the cities connected to the learning outcomes; Section 4.2.2 presents the reflexivity changes the learnings brought for the cities; and Section 4.2.3 presents how the learnings are connected to the Connecting Nature Framework Elements. This shows what the cities learned from the project and how this occurred. In Deliverable 6 (Hölscher et al. 2022), we built further on the analysis, to identify the innovations of the Connecting Nature Framework Elements in more detail.

4.2.1 The critical turning points and learning questions of the cities connected to the learning outcomes

The learning process results in ‘reflexive learning outcomes’ when knowledge (the what), actions (the how) and relations (the who) become substantively interwoven (Beers et al. 2016) as a result of a shared experience in how to overcome barriers or use opportunities and learning about how to deal with them. Thus, learning outcomes are reflexive, when not only new insights are gained, but when these insights are implemented into the context within which the learning actors operate.

Reflexive learning outcomes can be operationalized in terms of changes in the existing 1) **rules** guiding actors’ practices, 2) **relations** between actors, and between the initiative and context, 3) **practices** as the common ways of working and 4) **discourse** related to the future of the initiative’s sector (Beers and van Mierlo, 2017). For application by the cities in the

Connecting Nature project we developed a method to track and distil learning outcomes and reflect upon their reflexivity that we described in Section 2.2 and in more detail in the reflexive monitoring guidebook (Lodder et al. 2022).

Table 4 below presents all clustered learning outcomes of the Front-Runner Cities with corresponding critical turning points (CTPs) and learning questions (LQs). Because this analysis was conducted two times, we have used a black colour for the related CTPs and LQs from 2019-2020 and a green colour for the related CTPs and LQs from 2020-2021.

This table shows that reflexive monitoring helped track the learning in three different cities. The way we operationalised reflexive monitoring and how the cities worked with the numbers in their Dynamic Learning Agenda helped us to track their learning process in time as well. It shows that per cluster of learning outcomes the cities had multiple critical turning points on their Dynamic Learning Agenda. Sometimes the learning continued around one learning question (Learning outcome 1, GELQ3.41) and critical turning points were added in time (Learning outcome 1, GECTP3.19+4.10; GECTP 3.25; GECTP3.28; GECTP3.40). But we also see critical turning points from different events added to the same learning outcome (Learning outcome 1, GECTP11.33b). This was a different event, connected to different learning questions but resulted in learnings for the other learning question as well. We see the same happening for the other cities in this example. This means that all cities learned at different points in time and at different occasions to overcome barrier of siloed organisation by developing novel governance structures to allow cross- organisational collaboration.

12 out of 18 learning outcomes are related to all three cities, 5 to two cities and one for only one (Glasgow). That shows that although the cities are very different in size, geography, etc. and their nature-based solutions have a different scale and focus, the learning in cities who work on implementing large-scale nature-based solutions evolves around similar topics. We looked at the reflexivity changes in more depth in Section 4.2.2 and what the learning was about using the Connecting Nature Framework Elements in Section 4.2.3. Deliverable 6 (Hölscher et al. 2022) builds further on this analysis in terms of identifying what was needed for the framework implementation.

Table 4: Learning outcomes with corresponding critical turning points and learning questions per FRC

GECTP = CTP of Genk | GLCTP = CTP of Glasgow | POCTP = CTP of Poznań

GELQ – LQ of Genk | GLLQ = LQ of Glasgow | POLQ = LQ of Poznań

In black the CTPs from 2019-2020 | In green the CTPs from 2020-2021

In bold are the selected learning outcomes that we describe in more detail in the following sub-sections.

#	Learning outcomes	Critical turning points	Learning questions
1	To overcome barrier of siloed organisation, novel governance structures were developed to allow cross-organisational collaboration	GECTP3.19+4.10; GECTP 3.25; GECTP3.28; GECTP3.40; GECTP11.33b GLCTP 15C; GLCTP2.16 POCTP2+3.5+5.3;	GELQ3.41 GLLQ2.16.1
2	To overcome challenges of involving enterprises in NBS delivery, innovative approaches were developed to collaborate with and support enterprises	GECTP#; GECTP3.29 GLCTP 5.3 POCTP2;	POLQ2.2
3	New opportunities detected to expand the scope of the nature-based solution exemplar.	GECTP#; GLCTP15B; POCTP3; POCTP2.6;	POLQ2.6;
4	Find opportunities to keep colleagues engaged	GECTP3.17; GECTP5.12 GLCTP2; POCTP3.6; POCTP3.1; POCPT3.2 (old); POCTP3.3; POCTP3.2 (new); POCTP5.4	GLLQ2.0 POLQ3.2
5	From barriers to opportunities by capacity building to facilitate nature-based solution co-production by communities	GECTP3.18 GLCTP4+6; GLCTP3.1; GLCTP2.6a POCTP3.7	
6	Continuation of activities beyond Connecting Nature	GECTP6.27; GLCTP7.1+7.2; POCTP5.2	
7	Using city-wide events, strategies to present the narrative of the nature-based solution exemplar to increase (political) support	GECTP5.12; GLCTP7+8; GLCTP7.2 POCTP4	GLLQ7.1

8	Opportunity to include nature-based solution into multiannual budgets and policy planning	GECTP6.18; GECTP6.26; POCTP5	
9	Opportunities to utilise 'grey solution'-budgets for nature-based solutions	GECTP 6.31+6.20+3.18; GLCTP5; POCTP 5.3+2	
10	Opportunities to develop novel co-production approaches	GECTP11.22+6.30; GECTP11.32; GECTP11.33a; GECTP11.34; GECTP11.37 GLCTP15a; GLCTP2.6 POCTP5.3	GELQ11.11; GELQ11.10; GELQ11.12
11	Switch between strategic and operational levels	GECTP6.28+14.3; GECTP6.37; GLCTP11 POCTP3.3; POCTP2.4;	POLQ2.3;
12	Opportunities for upscaling based on implementation of exemplar by other actors	GECTP11.27; GECTP11.26; GECTP11.35; GLCTP8; POCTP5.3; POCTP1.1; POCTP2.3	POLQ1.3; POLQ2.1; POLQ2.3
13	Barrier to attract local partners with co-production skills	GECTP11.25+11.23; POCTP2+5	
14	Shifting from Planning to Delivery requires change of governance styles	GECTP3.26; GLCTP2.6; POCTP 3.3;	GELQ3.13 GLLQ2.6 POLQ3.1
15	External funding applications based on CN Framework, perceived as recognition for innovative work	GECTP3.44; POCTP2	POCTP2.1
16	Replicating innovative structures developed in CN result in new practices of other departments.	GECTP14.7; GLCTP2.2; GLCTP2.3	GLLQ2.3.1
17	Simple communication about nature-based solutions is not easy but is very effective to get strategic actors involved	GECTP11.34b POCTP5.4	POLQ5.3
18	CN Framework can be used as to report on progress of nature-based solution projects (e.g. gap-analysis).	GLCTP15;	GLLQ

We selected three learning outcomes to describe in more detail (in bold in the table above) to illustrate the type of events that are related the learning outcomes in the different cities and what type of reflexivity changes and connecting nature elements they related to.

4.2.1.1 Learning outcome #2: To overcome challenges of involving enterprises in nature-based solutions delivery, innovative approaches were developed to collaborate with and support enterprises

Genk started a procedure of 'Open Oproep' [Open Call] and by appointing Tractebel as agency for development of Masterplan allowed for continued collaboration on the long-term because they did not have to work with different companies all the time. This resulted in novel **relations** and **practices** for the team. The team realised that their long-term relationship with Tractebel is very symbiotic: Tractebel knows and works with the nature-based solutions strategy of the city since the beginning. It also simplifies the tendering process, not having to look for a new supplier for every phase. The long-term partner knows the project and can easily continue, so it saves the team time. This learning outcome is related to **Governance** because the new practices and relations are with project partners of the municipality. It only had effect on governance, and not so much on other elements yet. This means that Genk's nature-based enterprise strategy is still emerging. They invested in this new relation with Tractebel. This was very much the planning phase: they really needed this long-term relation. Now Genk is in the implementation phase: more opportunities pop-up that can help them, that offer opportunities for nature-based entrepreneurship.

Glasgow used their local networks to identify suitable partners to collaborate on a nature-based enterprise programme. These partners have reached out across their networks to promote the pilot programme and to help find nature-based enterprises to participate. This way new **relations** are explored through the networks of partners. The new **practice** is to work with enterprises, to develop the nature-based enterprise programme makes them think about what the team would like to teach the nature-based enterprises. It was not completely new for the city of Glasgow, more latent potential. The Connecting Nature project helped Glasgow in retrofitting an existing **practice**, restarting an existing programme under the

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nature-based enterprises. This learning outcome is related to **Co-production** because this is a novel way to co-produce a teaching programme together with local partners. It is also related to **Financing** because the programme includes content around how enterprises can be funded and what sort of business model they could adopt. And **Entrepreneurship** because this programme is developed to attract more nature-based enterprises and, last, **Governance** because they also collaborate with the centre for civic innovation, and this collaboration is set up in a novel way.

Poznań realised that working with a private sponsor requires more time at first but can result in a well-designed process and more financing possibilities. This first experience with a private partner made the team realise that it takes time, but that this is necessary. They never had this experience, and they gained confidence to undertake more of these partnerships. The **relation** with the company is new but worked out this time because team realized their strength is setting up expectations about the quality. **Practice**: due to the covid pandemic and this intermediary role of the team and the school, the company and their own director, it takes more time. But, also, because it is the first time they are doing this. This learning outcome is related to **Co-production** because the process is together with schools and sponsors; to **Governance** because they have to align financing with internal requirements and to **Financing**: working with a private company is a novel way of funding nature-based solutions.

4.2.1.2 Learning outcome #14: Shifting from planning to delivery requires change of governance styles

Genk realised that they need to transition their way of governing to fit the implementation phase of the project. This new phase requires sets of new **relationships** and **practices** geared towards delivery of the Stiemer valley's projects. It also changes the **discourse**, how their colleagues first saw the team as the ones that are visioning and planning to a shift towards implementing and delivering. This learning objective is related to **Governance** since the new practices, relations and discourse are novel collaborations within the city hall.

Glasgow's team discovered story mapping as an opportunity to showcase funding opportunities in a dynamic way to policy makers. This is a novel **practice** because for the team it is novel to use story mapping to showcase funding opportunities, to use it to share learnings and as an engagement tool. Story mapping was used as a good method to discuss funding options cross-departmentally because making it visual helps in the discussions with other policy makers. This resulted in new **relationships** and **discourse** because they have changed the way people think about this. The learning objective is related to **Governance** because they use it for internal and cross-departmental collaborations within the City Hall. And to **Financing** because it is a method to showcase funding opportunities.

Poznań's team realised they are not only the organisers of sessions like the Urbact Local Group but they can also exchange and propose their own ideas and put them on the agenda. It is a novel **practice** to not only organise a brainstorm to harvest ideas but to contribute to the brainstorm themselves. And a novel **relation** is formed when the team takes up the role of not only facilitators but also of experts. It leads to a different perception of the team by others. This learning outcome is related to **Co-production** because NGOs are involved and see them in this new role and to **Governance** because of the changed role within the city, from facilitators to experts on their projects and nature-based solutions.

4.2.1.3 Learning outcome #15: External funding applications based on Connecting Nature Framework, perceived as recognition for innovative work

Genk's team received €2.01 m investment funding for Gardens of Waterschei, which is not only funding but mainly (and finally) a recognition for the Stiemer programme. The recognition for the team and the Stiemer programme equals a recognition for implementing and scaling nature-based solutions. This implies changes in **relations** in how they collaborate with their colleagues. Also new **practices** because this way of working is valued by more people and will be 'mainstreamed'. It also contributes to a novel **discourse** because within the city nature-based solutions are now also recognised as an important strategy and as a way to get this type of funding. This learning outcome relates to: **Technical solutions**: recognition for how nature-based solutions can deliver on city strategic objectives (environmental, social, economic); **Co-production**: the proposal includes citizens-oriented public private partnership; **Financing**: the proposal is based on a strategy of combining citizens-oriented public private partnership; **Entrepreneurship**: the proposal includes the involvement of entrepreneurs of the Stalenstraat; and **Governance**: it is also a recognition for working horizontally.

Glasgow did not have a learning outcome based on their Dynamic Learning Agenda, but during the Learning Experience Webinar the team explained that they are using the Connecting Nature Framework for approving incoming funding applications themselves. They are using it for their strategic programme. It helps them to discuss what is wrong and right for each of the elements (it therefore relates to **all Connecting Nature elements**). It is helpful to start the conversation with their colleagues. On a strategic level: it has been fundamental: it is a check to see if a project that applies has

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everything it takes. It is a novel **practice** to use a framework like the Connecting Nature Framework for evaluating the value of novel **relations** and the use of the framework like this is a novel **rule**.

Poznań's team realised when working on tenders and applications that ask for complex solutions, the team bumps into the barrier: they are not able to fit their proposal to into the system of the tender/application. The tender/application asks for complexity but doesn't have a template for it. This resulted in changed **rules**: e.g. limited words and categories are especially challenging when working with nature-based solutions in tenders and project applications. A new **practice** was developed as the solution now was to create Appendices in which they could write more, but the team is not sure if this was successful. Next time they would do it differently. The consultant they collaborated with realised they focused more on the Appendices and not on the short forms. Next time they will also ask different things. This learning outcome resulted in new insights on **Technical solutions**: As it is hard to explain a complex solution like a technical solution for nature-based solution in current tender/applications due to the format of the tender/application. And **Governance**: it is complex to apply for tenders e.g. with cross-departmental collaboration.

4.2.2 Reflexivity of the learning outcomes

Looking at the reflexivity of the learning outcomes (Table 5, see section 2.2 for an explanation of the methods, and above for definitions of learning outcomes and reflexivity), we see that the majority of changes are related to relations and practices, especially in the first period between 2019 and 2020. There are fewer changes in rules and discourse. Most of the time the changes in relations and practices are linked to each other because they are about changes on the short-term that the city teams have a direct influence on. They can design and implement their novel ideas about the process themselves, without permission from higher up. It's also linked to their way of working: for example, by implementing a new practice such as a co-production process, new relations are formed as well. Those relations often result in other new practice, for example to apply for a new type of funding together. So, changes in relations and practices are closely intertwined.

Changes in rules imply policy changes and institutionalisation which needs more time before they can be implemented especially in a large city hall like Glasgow. Changes in discourse are less tangible, more on the long-term so it seems logical that the city teams experience less learning outcomes regarding to those changes between 2019 and 2020. We did recognize more discourse changes between 2020-2021 for the learning outcomes.

Table 5: Learning outcomes related to the reflexivity categories
Ge=Genk; GL=Glasgow; Po= Poznań

Learning outcomes 2019-2021	Rules			Relations			Practices			Discourse		
	Ge	Gl	Po	Ge	Gl	Po	Ge	Gl	Po	Ge	Gl	Po
1 Governance structures for cross-organizational collaboration	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
2 To overcome challenges of involving enterprises in NBS	●		●	●	●		●		●	●		
3 Find opportunities to expand scope of NBS			●			●	●	●	●			●
4 Find opportunities to keep colleagues engaged			●	●	●	●	●	●	●			●
6 Barriers of capacity building among civil servants / communities				●	●		●	●	●		●	
7 Continuation activities beyond Connecting Nature				●		●	●		●	●	●	
8 Use events / strategies for political support				●	●	●			●	●	●	
9 Include NBS into multiannual budgets / policy planning	●			●		●	●		●			
10 Use 'grey solutions' budget for NBS				●	●	●		●	●	●		
11 Develop novel co-production approaches			●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
12 Establish new connections between strategic and operational levels				●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	
13 Other actors implement NBS as way of upscaling	●		●	●	●	●	●		●	●	●	●
14 Barrier to attract local partners with co-production skills				●		●	●		●			
15 Shifting from Planning to Delivery				●		●	●	●	●	●	●	
16 Use CN Framework for funding applications		●	●	●	●		●	●	●	●	●	
17 Replication CN innovations to other departments	●	●	●	●	●		●	●	●	●	●	●
18 Communication strategy to involve other actors	●								●			
19 Use CN Framework to report on progress		●		●				●				

added 2020-2021

4.2.3 Learning outcomes related to the Connecting Nature Framework Elements

We also looked at the learning outcomes in relation to the Connecting Nature Framework Elements (Table 6). While we don't aim to analyse their content in terms of embedded innovations and changes (see Deliverable 6, Hölscher et al. 2022), here we aim to show that we can distil many learning outcomes based on our reflexive monitoring analysis.

What is visible is that the cities in particular started to rethink their governance and co-production processes. That explains the many learning outcomes for these elements, especially in the first years of the project. Additionally, the cities also focus on implementing technical solutions and the financing of their nature-based solutions. More novel for the cities has been the elements of entrepreneurship and impact assessment. Because these topics are more novel to the cities, they had to explore them first. They had to learn about what these topics meant before they could start working with them. Once they started to work on, for example, the indicators, this started to change their rules, relations, practice and/or discourse, and then reflexive learning outcomes started to appear for these elements.

It thus takes time before novel topics turn into learning outcomes. Once a city starts working with a novel Connecting Nature element in practice the learning starts and can be captured as critical turning points on the Dynamic Learning Agenda. When the learning results in a changing context in terms of novel rules, relations, practices or discourse a reflexive learning outcome occurs.

Table 6: Learning outcomes related to the Connecting Nature Framework Elements
Ge=Genk; GL=Glasgow; Po= Poznań.

Learning outcomes 2019-2021	Technical solutions			Governance			Financing & business models			Entrepreneurship			Co-production			Impact assessment		
	Ge	Gl	Po	Ge	Gl	Po	Ge	Gl	Po	Ge	Gl	Po	Ge	Gl	Po	Ge	Gl	Po
1 Governance structures for cross-organizational collaboration			●	●	●	●	●	●	●			●	●		●	●		
2 To overcome challenges of involving enterprises in NBS				●	●	●	●	●		●				●	●			
3 Find opportunities to expand scope of NBS	●		●	●	●				●					●	●			
4 Find opportunities to keep colleagues engaged	●	●	●	●	●	●			●									●
6 Barriers of capacity building among civil servants / communities	●		●	●	●				●		●		●	●	●			●
7 Continuation activities beyond Connecting Nature		●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●		●	●	●			●
8 Use events / strategies for political support		●		●	●		●	●		●				●	●			
9 Include NBS into multiannual budgets / policy planning				●				●										
10 Use 'grey solutions' budget for NBS	●		●	●	●	●			●				●	●	●			●
11 Develop novel co-production approaches			●	●		●			●				●	●	●			●
12 Establish new connections between strategic and operational levels	●			●	●	●	●											●
13 Other actors implement NBS as way of upscaling			●	●		●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●			
14 Barrier to attract local partners with co-production skills				●		●			●				●		●			
15 Shifting from Planning to Delivery				●		●		●							●			
16 Use CN Framework for funding applications	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●		●	●		●	●				●
17 Replication CN innovations to other departments				●	●									●				●
18 Communication strategy to involve other actors				●											●			
19 Use CN Framework to report on progress		●		●				●		●				●				

○ added 2020-2021

4.3 Learning objectives of Fast-Follower Cities

As part of their reflexive monitoring process, we wanted to give the Fast-Follower Cities the opportunity to share their learning objectives with each other. We hypothesised that the questions and objectives that one city had, might well be shared by others, and that peer-to-peer exchange would facilitate reflexivity and learning.

In order to do so, we first made an overview of the learning objectives per Connecting Nature Framework Element that the Fast-Follower Cities presented in their 1-on-1 Reflexive Monitoring sessions (see also Section 2.2). We subsequently asked the other cities to mark the learning objectives that they recognised in their own cities. During the third Learning Platform Webinar, there was room to discuss these (shared) learning objectives and for more reflexivity and learning between the cities.

Below we give an overview of the synergies of these learning objectives per Connecting Nature Framework Element, as well as whether the learning objective has received a response or advice from another city, either during one of the 1-on-1 learning sessions, or during a Knowledge Hub activity or a break-out session at the third Learning Platform Webinar. In Deliverable 6 (Hölscher et al. 2022) we further analyse the content of these learning objectives. Here, we only focus on the learning process between cities. For brevity, we have only included the numbers of the learning objectives/questions; see Appendix E for the full description of each learning objective. For each learning objective, we mark which city had or recognised this learning objective with a circle. The circles with a dark border indicate a city that had a response to this question, or an advice. See Figure 7 below.

Figure 7: Learning objectives related to the Connecting Nature Framework

Connecting Nature Framework

Learning objective	1	2	3	4
A Coruña	●	●	●	
Burgas		●		
Ioannina	●			
Malaga		●	●	
Nicosia	●	●	●	●
Pavlos Melas	●	●		
Sarajevo		●	●	
Genk	○			
Glasgow				
Poznań				●

Technical Solutions

Learning objective	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
A Coruña	●			●		●		
Burgas	●	●	●		●	●		
Ioannina	●	●			●	●		
Malaga	●			●				
Nicosia	●			●	●	●		
Pavlos Melas		●		●		●		●
Sarajevo			●	●		●	●	
Genk		○						
Glasgow	○		○					
Poznań								

Governance

Learning objective	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
A Coruña	○			●	●	●	●	
Burgas	●						●	●
Ioannina	●	●		●		●		
Malaga	●	●			●		●	●
Nicosia		●			●	●	●	●
Pavlos Melas	●				●		●	●
Sarajevo			●					
Genk	○							
Glasgow	●							
Poznań								

Finance and business models

Learning objective	1	2	3	4	5	6
A Coruña	●	●		●		●
Burgas	●			●		●
Ioannina	○	●		●		
Malaga				●	●	●
Nicosia	●	●	○	●		●
Pavlos Melas	●	●		●	●	●
Sarajevo		●		●	●	●
Genk				○		
Glasgow	○					
Poznań			●			

Nature-based Entrepreneurship

Learning objectives	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
A Coruña		●			●			
Burgas								●
Ioannina								
Malaga		●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Nicosia	●	●			●		●	●
Pavlos Melas	●	●						●
Sarajevo		●						●
Genk								
Glasgow			●	●		●	●	
Poznań								

Co-production

L. obj.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
A coru.		●	●	●	●			●			●	●				●			
Burgas	●		●	●		●		●			●			●			●	●	
Ioan.			●									●						●	
Malaga	●	●		●			●	●	●		●				●	●		●	●
Nicosia	●			●		●		●	●		●			●	●			●	●
Pavl. M.	●		●	●	●			●	●		●		●	●	●		●	●	
Saraj.	●	●	●	●				●	●	●	●		●	●	●			●	●
Genk			●																
Glasgow	●		●	●	●					●									●
Poznan											●								

Reflexive Monitoring

Learning objective	1	2	3	4
A Coruña		●		
Burgas	●			
Ioannina	●		●	
Malaga	●			●
Nicosia	●			
Pavlos Melas				
Sarajevo	●	●		
Genk				
Glasgow	●			
Poznań				

Impact assessment

Learning objective	1	2	3	4	5	6
A Coruña	●				●	●
Burgas						
Ioannina				●		
Malaga	●			●	●	
Nicosia		●		●	●	
Pavlos Melas	●	●	●	●	●	
Sarajevo		●		●		●
Genk			●			
Glasgow	●					
Poznań				●		

From Figure 7, we can see that of the 63 learning objectives identified, 57 were shared and/or responded to by other cities; only 6 learning objectives were city-specific. Furthermore, 27 responses were given to learning objectives, to 24 unique learning objectives (three learning objectives received two responses). We believe this number of responses indicates the value of peer-to-peer learning: being able to share learning objectives and also getting advice on a good number of them. Furthermore, the sharedness of the learning objectives across cities highlights the great potential of peer-to-peer learning. It might seem that setting up nature-based solutions and the challenges that go with that are highly context dependent, but in fact, many experiences are shared and can benefit from peer-to-peer learning.

Second, we observe that the directionality of learning is not only from Front-Runner city to Fast-Follower city: in eight cases, a Fast-Follower city gave advice to their peers, and in six cases, a Front-Runner city recognised the learning objective. This observation is especially interesting given that it runs counter to the set-up of the Learning Platform Webinar, as well as the project set-up, which aimed at a learning directionality from Front-Runner city to Fast-Follower city.

Third, we see that the number of learning objectives varies per element. While some elements only harboured four learning objectives (the Connecting Nature Framework, and Reflexive Monitoring, others had more, up to 19 (co-production). At the same time, we see that for each element, a high number of learning objectives are shared, and responded to. This indicates that peer-to-peer learning is in principle useful for all framework elements, even those that do not generate many learning objectives. The difference in the number of learning objectives per framework element merely shows that some elements generate more learning objectives or challenges than others.

Reflexivity in Fast-Follower city learning objectives

In Section 4.2, we described reflexivity in the learning outcomes of the Front-Runner Cities. Similarly, we looked at reflexivity of learning objectives of the Fast-Follower Cities; did we observe any changes in rules, relations, practices, or discourse? Of course, but learning objectives are different from learning outcomes: the former are questions, while the latter are learnings. This means that for learning objectives, we cannot observe actual changes in rules, relations, practices, or discourse. Nonetheless, we think we can observe precursors to those changes, because of a different way of thinking about a certain topic. In a way, the learning objectives reveal intentions to implement those reflexivity changes.

For example, when Sarajevo asks: “How can we measure and impact the issues of pollutions, health and well-being, raising awareness on necessity of gardens like these?” (which falls under learning objective no. 4 in Technical Solutions, see Appendix E), we see intentions to change practices, and discourse. The intention to change practices is because for Sarajevo, measuring and recording the environmental and health impacts of nature-based solutions would be a new practice. The intention to change discourse is because the city wants to raise awareness of the necessity of gardens, and the perceptions of people – which entails a change in discourse.

Another example comes from A Coruña: when they express the wish “to change our governance model – from top-down to bottom-up” (learning objective no.6 in Governance), we analyse that they want to reflexively change existing rules, relations, and practices. Altering the governance model will incur a change in the ways the gardens are regulated, hence novel rules. Furthermore, potential new relations can emerge from bottom-up governance models, and the city has an explicit intention here to change the current organisational practice.

Whether the Fast-Follower Cities actually manage to implement these reflexivity changes is yet to be seen. However, expressing interest in these changes, and employing a different way of thinking about possible issues, indicates an increased chance of this implementation.

5 Conclusions and outlook

In the following, we reflect on key lessons learned from applying and analysing co-production of nature-based solutions in our Connecting Nature cities (Section 5.1), as well as from reflexive monitoring (Section 5.2). Finally, we present an outlook about how we seek to continue with our work beyond the Connecting Nature project (Section 5.3).

Overall, all Connecting Nature cities recognised the value of co-production to engage with and empower diverse actors and reflexive monitoring to facilitate continuous learning and adaptation in real time when planning, delivering and

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stewarding nature-based solutions. However, adopting new governance processes and tools that challenge conventional practices requires the creation of institutional and organisational space in cities and the acquisition of new skills and knowledge. It also requires new cultures within city governments to work across siloes.

5.1 Lessons learned for co-producing nature-based solutions in cities

The cities had different experiences with co-production and pursued different goals aligned with their nature-based solutions exemplar. Co-production has been challenging for the cities, because it was new to them and required various expertise and skills, as well as the creation of space to experiment with such novel ways of working. This was often at odds with the existing working environments in the cities that tend to be more rigid, hierarchical, and bureaucratic.

Notably, while co-production can in principle be initiated by public servants, citizens or other actors, we focus on co-production processes initiated by the teams from the different city governments participating in the Connecting Nature project. No matter by whom it is initiated and implemented, a central implication is that it shifts the roles of public servants from being service providers in an offer-oriented way, and the roles of citizens from being solely the receivers of services, towards all actors becoming service (co-)producers (Jaspers and Steen 2019; Brandsen and Honingh 2018). This is also what we recognise when analysing the co-production processes, particularly the co-production outcomes (Sections 3.2.4, 3.2.5, 3.2.6).

Benefits of co-production

All cities recognised co-production as an opportunity to engage with diverse actors in their cities for the planning, delivery, and stewardship of their nature-based solution exemplar. In this way, co-production is able to address the various governance needs for knowledge, partnerships and societal and political support identified in the Connecting Nature cities. The key benefits are as follows:

- Inclusive participation of actors with different expertise, background, gender, etc, that helps getting diverse input and contextualising solutions, building new relationships and partnerships and reaching unusual suspects;
- Co-production creates a positive feedback loop: while preconditioning open mindsets for collaboration and trust, experiencing co-production also further enhances such qualities and thus lays the ground for better collaboration;
- Co-production generates new, integrated and actionable knowledge for context-sensitive and multifunctional solutions, for example by opening up previously isolated problem perceptions and adding new insights to possible solutions;
- Engaging societal actors motivates and empowers them to become active in developing, using, and stewarding nature-based solutions;
- Co-production boosts partnerships and outreach across city departments and provides opportunities for advancing and extending urban policy and planning agendas, thus facilitating synergies of knowledge and resources towards shared goals.

Challenges and lessons learned

The experiences of the Connecting Nature cities with co-production also underscore that co-production is not a panacea. Co-production is not yet very common in urban settings, and often goes against the grain of conventional decision-making and planning. As such, it does not only pose many challenges for those wanting to engage in co-production processes, it is also often at odds with other conventional decision-making and planning processes. All cities state that they experienced their co-production processes as huge learning processes, and many lessons have already changed urban policy and planning practice in the cities towards more collaborative, open-ended and flexible approaches.

Our comparative analysis of how to ensure the six co-production principles gives a detailed guide on critical conditions and activities to ensure inclusive, legitimate and open co-production processes able to generate actionable knowledge, empower participants and align actors and agendas. Here, we highlight several cross-cutting challenges as well as related lessons for how to address them.

- ***No one-size-fits-all and depending on goals and settings:*** Co-production is not a one-size-fits-all approach and needs to be made fit to a specific city's contexts, needs and objectives. This is precisely what makes the co-production principles valuable: they give a guide on how to design, implement and reflect on co-production in line with specific needs and conditions in a certain context. However, we also found that due to the limited experiences with co-production, not all so-called co-production processes in the cities resembled co-production

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as it is defined – sometimes the processes were limited to public consultation (especially the strategic co-production processes in which cities sought to generate public feedback on their plans and strategies for nature-based solution exemplars, see Section 3.1.1). A risk is, of course, that co-production gets deflated of meaning. Many cities seemed to use co-production and collaboration interchangeably. Nonetheless, it is valuable to learn from these experiences and thus our approach to different types of co-production processes allows capturing a spectrum of collaboration and engagement of private actors. Specifically, the distinction in different co-production goals and settings (Section 3.1) facilitated better positioning of the different approaches. Similarly, disregarding scientific definitions of co-production, the cities found it valuable to distinguish for example between internal and external co-production – the former referring to co-production across different departments to break siloes, and the latter referring to co-production with private actors. In that regard, we also find that looking at these processes through the lens of the co-production principles, we can not only identify lessons about co-production but also about governance of nature-based solutions more generally. On a basic level, and notwithstanding the need to push for more advanced approaches to co-production, any form of collaboration has been considered novel and highly valuable in the cities.

- ***Creating space for co-production:*** Since co-production is a novel governance approach, the required experiences and skills to ensure inclusive, legitimate and open co-production with multiple outcomes have not yet been invested in. As it is not yet a common practice in urban governance and planning, it is often met with a high level of scepticism. It has been stated in the cities that sometimes there is just no time for participation in general, because decisions have to be made quickly. In addition, there are multiple competing priorities with insufficient time, so that there is no time to learn about, discuss and trial new methods of work such as co-production. It takes time to integrate it into the everyday design. This resonates with co-production literature: setting up co-production processes requires opening up organisational and institutional settings (e.g. by providing regulatory, financial and politically-free space) for open-ended experimentation, acquiring skills for designing and facilitating co-production processes with intended outcomes, and identifying and connecting actors for the co-production process (Ferlie et al. 2019; Djenontin and Meadow 2018). For example, from the Connecting Nature cities' experiences we learned about the importance to develop communication skills to engage citizens and citizen groups in order to co-produce narratives, understandings and contextualised problem framings that will resonate the co-production of nature-based solutions. The city of Genk provided a valuable example for how to not only set the scene for co-production but also to mainstream co-production across all urban planning and policy activities, by mobilising political support and institutional leadership, navigating across departmental siloes to create inter-departmental alliances and acquiring additional human resources with specific expertise in societal engagement. A challenge in all cities was to convince colleagues from other departments about the benefits of co-production. Organisational coaching programmes (see Appendix F) can support such processes.
- ***Ensuring inclusivity and mobilising diverse types of actors:*** Co-production ultimately intends to mobilise and empower a wide range of actors to participate in every aspect of nature-based solution planning, delivery, and stewarding. However, it is still challenging to reach out and motivate diverse actors to participate in co-production processes, and, particularly, to motivate them to become part of the implementation and to take up their own initiatives. On the one hand, it relates to the lack of experience of city governments to reach out to 'unusual suspects' and a lack of skills in mediating different languages, interests, etc. On the other hand, it is also difficult to attract people to volunteer on a regular basis (e.g. for the management of an urban garden) or engage in financing, because of a lack of knowledge about financial models or social innovations. Mobilising and empowering actors to become part of the process requires active communication, open engagement and legitimate processes with clear expectations to reconcile different interests, create ownership and build trust. It is important to create working knowledge of a specific neighbourhood or community, including specific needs and diverse types of actors. It is specifically important to ground co-production processes in specific places and spaces, for instance by collaborating with community engagement officers, linking to embedded community organisations or investing in dedicated expertise (e.g. social innovation) to build bridges with local communities. Additionally, continued communication and engagement is crucial, especially through 'fun' activities and formats.
- ***Dealing with politics and asymmetrical power relations:*** Co-production processes cannot avoid politics. Politics concerns the questions of who is involved in co-production processes and who benefits from the results, as well as how to ensure legitimacy of co-produced results. For example, when powerful socio-economic interests dominate greening initiatives they might be placed above other/social equity needs and priorities. Local residents and community groups might (fear to) be affected by gentrification. Politics also concerns the (re-)distribution of responsibilities of private actors vis-à-vis local governments, having different capacities and resources, as a (desired) result of co-production. It is important to keep in mind that co-production does not necessarily result in equal power relations but rather in empowering people through the process of collaborative learning and

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governance. Still, more attention needs to be paid to who are the traditionally ‘voiceless’, who are not only often under-privileged actors but also those who are not born yet or elderly populations, as well as to equal participation and how outcomes affect different (groups of) actors. Additionally, a strategy for co-production can be to avoid politically-laden environments or those with high political stakes in order to first focus on open exchange and trust building by leaving more leeway. Furthermore, expectation management is critical: don’t promise what can’t be kept.

- ***Co-production in times of the COVID19 pandemic:*** The COVID-19 pandemic hit mid-way through the Connecting Nature project. Due to the pandemic, priorities shifted (making nature-based solutions a lower priority), planning and delivery of physical interventions has paused or become slower, urban gardens and school gardens closed and pressures on the private sector increased (making it harder to secure private funding). This has especially affected co-production, because no in-person meetings could be held and it was more challenging to approach groups, especially vulnerable groups. Despite these drawbacks and barriers, the cities persisted and succeeded to keep their projects on track even with some delays. While face-to-face meetings were not possible, many cities experimented with new online formats for co-production. Glasgow continued collaboration with their “Friends of” groups in a virtual or hybrid way and created videos to support capacity building with a different legacy compared to one-off workshops. Additionally, the cities found that while immediate priority has shifted away from nature-based solutions, the lock-down experience highlighted the benefits of green and open spaces for mental and physical health and wellbeing. Some cities even stated that the pandemic provided opportunities for consolidation. In Poznań, the open garden had to be closed to residents, but this provided space for the team to develop new ideas for open gardens at kindergartens.

5.2 Lessons learned for reflexive monitoring

We believe the reflexive monitoring process was highly valuable to the cities. Structuring the peer-to-peer learning around reflexive monitoring and the Dynamic Learning Agendas was central to its success, and for fostering knowledge exchange that went both ways – front-runner cities to fast-following cities, and vice versa. In this section, we elaborate on the lessons learned: what worked well and what can still be improved and how.

All cities had to get used to working with this novel method. The terminology used, like the name itself, did not make it easier for them to start working with other colleagues and explaining what it is about. It also required investing time to learn about the method in the beginning. For example, A Coruña wrote in their Connecting Nature Framework report: “We had to learn how to address a barrier or an opportunity in a way that the goals of the project are targeted. It was hard to know what questions really need to be asked to have the most transformative impact” (A Coruña). Most cities found their own terms for the different steps and tools of the process while working with it. That shows that working with a complex method like reflexive monitoring together with the cities really was learning-by-doing and doing-by-learning.

Once the cities embraced the principles and started working with the tools, they valued that it helped them to be more proactive and anticipate earlier and in real-time to avoid problems in the process instead of evaluating what went wrong afterwards (Ioannina, Pavlos Melas). Genk changed their internal governance model based on their reflexive monitoring experience (see guidebook Lodder et al. 2022, p. 70-73). After four years that the Front-Runner Cities worked with reflexive monitoring, the Genk team was able to formulate their own learning outcomes. The Glasgow team used their experience with reflexive monitoring to organise their meeting structure differently. They struggled the most with the method and the terminology in the beginning, but they made it their own in the end. The Poznań team used reflexive monitoring more at the background of their existing meeting structure. Their understanding of the method increased rapidly over time resulting in formalising the reflexivity of their learning outcomes themselves. All Front-Runner Cities had their own way to internalise the method.

The Fast-Follower Cities valued the 1-on-1 learning sessions between them and the Front-Runner Cities to get tips and tricks on how to implement reflexive monitoring in their daily activities but also based on the content they discussed. For example, the governance model of Genk that inspired the city of Pavlos Melas to identify the main pillars according to its objectives. This helped them to coordinate all the departments and their partial projects under the same umbrella (Pavlos Melas). Sarajevo valued the advice of Glasgow to include the university of Architecture in the design phase of the exemplar.

Some of the cities even reported that the method and tools saved time and offered flexibility because learning outcomes are translated in actions at any time during the project evolution (Pavlos Melas, A Coruña). In Sarajevo they valued that recording the learning process of identification of partners created a replicable model based on the lessons learned instead

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of inventing the wheel every time. A Coruña became more aware of their main challenges and by engaging people from outside their team in the reflexive monitoring process it was easier to raise awareness and get them on. A Coruña also wrote that reflexive monitoring provides the big picture they needed to move forward with the implementation of our exemplar.

The Fast-Follower Cities had less time to work with the method and we did not come to analyse the reflexivity of their learning objectives and outcomes. We only focused on their learning objectives to support their work on their nature-based solutions through Learning Platform Webinars during the Knowledge transfer phase 2 process (see Section 4.1). However, a lot of the cities managed to work with reflexive monitoring themselves with support from the Front-Runner Cities and the materials provided. Sarajevo and A Coruña even worked with actors from outside their team on reflexive monitoring. This was something we never expected from the beginning because it was already a challenge to work with the method in smaller teams.

We can say that the structure of the six-step approach for reflexive monitoring worked well for the cities. While we do not know if six steps are the ideal number (we only tried out the six-step model), we can say that it was based on how the cities worked with it in practice. We designed the reflexive monitoring process based on the scientific literature in Deliverable 4 (Hölscher et al. 2019a) and adapted that based on the experience in the cities to arrive at the six-step model we presented in the guidebook (Lodder et al. 2022).

Reflection on Learning Platform Webinar structure

We think that the way we applied reflexive monitoring in the Learning Platform Webinar structure helps in disentangling complex projects which involve multiple disciplines. We believe it strikes a good balance between structuring the different issues and questions into the seven Connecting Nature elements, while showing the connections between them. This means that reflexive monitoring can provide a good overview, without turning the different categories into silos. As we learned from the cities, breaking existing silos is a challenge when working with nature-based solutions (Frantzeskaki et al. 2020; Hölscher et al. 2019a). Based on this experience we were able to co-develop the Learning Platform Webinar structure with the cities and other scientific experts in the project.

The knowledge transfer process with the Learning Platform Webinars, 1-on-1 learning sessions and learning objective analysis became a very useful and energising process for all cities and the Knowledge Hub experts (see 4.3). When allowing cities to exchange their learning objectives, we saw that despite their specific contexts, they had very similar questions and valued exchange on these questions. In addition, we should not assume the directionality of learning to be only from Front-Runner Cities to Fast-Follower Cities. In these exchanges about learning objectives, we often also saw learning from Fast-Follower Cities to Front-Runner Cities, or among Fast-Follower Cities.

Suggestion further development

We started working with reflexive monitoring in cities in parallel to them starting to work with their nature-based solution exemplars. We learned, because of the complexities involved in initiating all of the Framework Elements towards mainstreaming nature-based solutions, that it takes a few years before the cities started implementing their innovations that included learning outcomes with reflexivity changes. For the Front-Runner Cities, the duration of Connecting Nature was enough, but for the Fast-Follower Cities we did not have enough time to have learning outcomes in practice. Ideally, we would have had one more year including two more Learning Platform Webinars and two-four 1-on-1 learning sessions between the Front-Runner Cities and Fast-Follower Cities.

When given more opportunities for learning from Fast-Follower Cities to Front-Runner Cities, or learning among Fast-Follower Cities, we may have seen even more of it. Furthermore, if Fast-Follower Cities had more time to follow through with their learning objectives, we could have seen more implemented reflexivity changes, instead of only intentions to do so. Another year would also have resulted in more examples of Knowledge-hub activities as a follow-up of the Learning Platform Webinars that could then be connected to results in learning outcomes for the cities and analysing the reflexivity changes of them. We believe a follow-up project that brings more cities into this peer-to-peer process would address these issues and would be a valuable next step.

5.3 Strategy on continuation with co-production and reflexive monitoring after Connecting Nature

We have been working to put in place several mechanisms to ensure the long-term sustainability of our co-production and reflexive monitoring work – in particular to continue to spread knowledge about the framework and how to apply it in cities.

Generally, our resources on co-production and reflexive monitoring will remain online and openly accessible (Figure 8, Box 11).

Figure 8: Resources, webinars and platforms for co-production and reflexive monitoring

Box 11: Overview of resources on co-production and reflexive monitoring

Guidebooks

- **Co-production – the full practical guide:** <https://oppla.eu/product/24697>
- **Co-production mini guidebook:** <https://connectingnature.eu/innovations/co-production>
- **Reflexive monitoring – the full practical guide:** <https://oppla.eu/product/23324>
- **Reflexive monitoring mini guidebook:** <https://connectingnature.eu/innovations/reflexive-monitoring>

YouTube videos on co-production and reflexive monitoring webinars for UrbanByNature programme

- **Introduction to co-production:** <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5PI3ss3ZPf0>
- **Introduction to reflexive monitoring:** <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5PI3ss3ZPf0>

Testimonials of how the cities worked with co-production

- **Poznan:** https://youtu.be/-dXywO_HEgI
- **Genk:** <https://youtu.be/Wex9CG-TbbA>
- **Glasgow:** <https://youtu.be/MIVK7mJq6w>
- **Sarajevo:** <https://youtu.be/R9FmXM2BtQU>

Testimonials of how the cities worked with reflexive monitoring

- **Genk:** <https://youtu.be/499VvUAPbgE>
- **Glasgow:** <https://youtu.be/x2aBrIqhzOY>

Webinars, sessions and trainings will be given on co-production and reflexive monitoring:

- Launch of the reflexive monitoring guidebook at **The Nature of Cities festival** (29-30/3/2022)
- Sessions on co-production, reflexive monitoring, and the Connecting Nature Framework during the **Genk Impact Summit** (28-29/4/2022). A policy brief on co-production is prepared to share insights with policy makers during this summit as well.
- During the **Connecting Nature Roadshow**, the Connecting Nature Framework and guidebooks on all the elements of the framework will be introduced and shared with the cities visited (Paris, Zurich, Chemnitz, Pordenone & Genk).
- For the **Nature-Based Organisation community** on the Nature Based Enterprise Platform, a webinar on

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overcoming barriers for co-production will be held, based on the knowledge gained.

- **DRIFT courses and course materials** on co-production and reflexive monitoring will be used and offered to new clients. The course series on Just Sustainability transitions contains a lecture on co-production and reflexive monitoring, respectively, which will benefit from the course materials and the guidebook created during the project. Also, a recurring training solely focused on Reflexive monitoring will benefit from the course materials and guidebooks created during the project.
- The **EM|Path approach** will be continued to be offered as co-productive series of methods to prepare the ground for working on nature-based solutions through reconnecting people with nature and unlocking personal and local narratives (www.empathway.org). The Genk Summit will include a session for participants to experience The EM|Path approach (this will be co-facilitated with CN partners, and cities who have completed the process and can share their learning and experiences).

Online databases and platform will make the resources available:

- **Oppla platform:** The Oppla platform is the EU repository for nature-based solutions. It provides a knowledge marketplace, where the latest thinking on natural capital, ecosystem services and nature-based solutions is brought together. Its purpose is to simplify how we share, obtain and create knowledge to better manage our environment. On the OPPLA platform, a dedicated Connecting Nature Resource Centre has been established. Here, all guidebooks, including worksheets and examples will be shared, as well as video testimonials by the Connecting Nature cities, sharing their story. Specific search terms will enable other users to find the Connecting Nature resources as well, such as visitors of the Network Nature platform (which is linked to OPPLA).
- The **Nature-based Organisations community**, led by Horizon Nua, will continue the work of the Knowledge Hubs on co-production & governance and on reflexive monitoring by organising workshops and webinars. In these webinars, all resources are made available, especially the recorded webinars on the basis of co-production and reflexive monitoring, and the testimonials of the cities.
- **Task Force 6 in collaboration with OPPLA**, is preparing a decision tree for researchers on how to use co-production in their context by applying different concepts in co-production. The guidebook will be one of the resources included in the resource library linked to this.
- **UrbanByNature (UbN):** The UrbanByNature programme will continue to facilitate expertise-sharing and capacity-building of local governments, civil society and businesses around the world about how to implement nature-based solutions on a large-scale. Specifically, four UrbanByNature regional hubs (Korea, China, the Caucasus and Brazil) will continue to promote nature-based solutions and the Connecting Nature Framework.

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Appendices

Appendix A: A practical guide to using co-production for nature-based solutions

The guidebook is enclosed in a separate document, and can be found here: <https://oppla.eu/product/24697>

Appendix B: A practical guide to using reflexive monitoring for nature-based solutions

The guidebook is enclosed in a separate document, and can be found here: <https://oppla.eu/product/23324>

Appendix C: Overview of co-production and reflexive monitoring activities

The Appendix is enclosed in a separate document and can be accessed here:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1VxWYNNTArpNYXamTeMYmkfqDJK5cHpr4/view?usp=sharing>

Appendix D: Learning Outcomes Front-Runner Cities

The Appendix is enclosed in a separate document and can be accessed here:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1ed3rQ29_uklyyhGshKeSN29F6OSg8OIS/view?usp=sharing

Appendix E: Learning Objectives FRCs and FFCs per Connecting Nature Framework Element

The Appendix is enclosed in a separate document and can be accessed here: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1H9AYS-U1EPNII3Yse8_TYLT7mts0_M4R/view?usp=sharing

Appendix F: Organisational Coaching Programme

Appendix F.1: Task 2.3 Summary for Deliverable 7

The Appendix is enclosed in a separate document and can be accessed here:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1QhBGnDUDFi8u26FuL9SldOMxCIB_wRCx/view?usp=sharing

Appendix F.2: Organisational Innovation Coaching Programme

The Appendix is enclosed in a separate document and can be accessed here:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1R5B6CMhLLa1PFAXRpaRJZEj-nOP02fvu/view?usp=sharing>

Appendix C:

Overview of workshops and activities

When	What	Participating partners	Participating Frontrunner cities	Participating Fast follower cities
Co- production workshops and webinars				
26-2-2018	Frontrunner city workshops - Assessment of (a) organisational conditions, barriers and strategies, (b) policy needs and (c) experiences with co-production, to identify good practices for co-production and tailor the co-production methodology	DRIFT	Genk	
11-4-2018	Frontrunner city workshop - Assessment of (a) organisational conditions, barriers and strategies, (b) policy needs and (c) experiences with co-production, to identify good practices for co-production and tailor the co-production methodology	DRIFT	Glasgow	
26-4-2018	Frontrunner city workshop - Assessment of (a) organisational conditions, barriers and strategies, (b) policy needs and (c) experiences with co-production, to identify good practices for co-production and tailor the co-production methodology	DRIFT	Poznan	
June 2018	Co-production workshop at General Assembly meeting of the Connecting Nature project held in Ioannina, Greece	DRIFT	Glasgow, Genk, Poznan	Pavlos Melas, Burgas, Malaga, A coruna, Sarajevo, Ioannina, Nicosia
02.11.2018	Co-production guidebook webinar - to discuss the first draft of the guidebook on co-production	DRIFT	Glasgow, Genk, Poznan	
21.11.2018	Co-production focus group in Rotterdam, the Netherlands - presentation of co-production processes the frontrunner cities put in place	DRIFT	Glasgow, Genk, Poznan	
14.01.2019	Co-production Webinar #0 <i>with all the FFC's together</i>	DRIFT		Pavlos Melas, Burgas, Malaga, A coruna, Sarajevo, Ioannina, Nicosia
23.01.2019	Workshop on co-production during the 'Learning Transfer Workshop' in Nicosia - Peer-to-peer learning on co-production principles and good practices	DRIFT		Pavlos Melas, Burgas, Malaga, A coruna, Sarajevo, Ioannina, Nicosia
14-3-2019 18-3-2019 10-4-2019 2-5-2019 29-5-2019	Co-production workshop #1 <i>with each of the FFC's seperately 2019</i>	DRIFT		Pavlos Melas, Burgas, Malaga, A coruna, Sarajevo, Ioannina, Nicosia

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18-6-2019 21-6-2019 27-6-2019				
31-01-2020 3-2-2020 5-2-2020	Co-production webinar #1 <i>- with each of the FRC's separately</i>	DRIFT	Katrien, Peter (Genk) Agnieszka D, Natalia and Dominika (Poznan) Sean, Gilian, Rania (Glasgow)	
25-9-2020 24-9-2020 21-9-2020 28-9-2020 4-10-2020 29-9-2020 1-10-2020	Co-production workshop #2 <i>with each of the FFC's seperately 2020</i>	DRIFT		Pavlos Melas, Burgas, Malaga, A coruna, Sarajevo, Ioannina, Nicosia
20-10-2020	Co-production webinar #2 <i>with all the FRC's, 2020</i>	DRIFT	Glasgow, Genk, Poznan	
8-10-2021	Co-production webinar #3 <i>with all the FRC's, 2021</i>	DRIFT	Rania Sermpezi, Sean Kelly (Glasgow), Natalia Madajczyk, Agnieszka D. (Poznan), Mien Quartier (Genk)	
7-6-2021 8-6-2021 31-2021 28-6-2021 26-5-2021 4-6-2021 27-5-2021	Co-production workshop #3 <i>with each of the FFC's seperately 2021</i>	DRIFT		Pavlos Melas, Burgas, Malaga, A Coruna, Sarajevo, Ioannina, Nicosia
8-3-2021	Knowledge hub session: Peer 2 peer sharing - Genks Co - production governance model	UEL, DRIFT	Genk	all invited
11-5-2021	Knowledge hub session: Webinar 0 -Stakeholder mapping Webinar	OSMOS, DRIFT	all invited	all invited
13-5-2021	Knowledge hub session: Webinar 1_ Organizational coaching program: Stress management during Covid	UVT, UEL, DRIFT		Malaga, Sarajevo, pavlos melas, A Coruna
20-5-2021	Knowledge hub session: Webinar 2 - Organizational coaching program: Understanding how to foster interpersonal skills	UVT, UEL, DRIFT	Poznan	A Coruna, Malaga, , Burgas
27-5-2021	Knowledge hub session: Webinar 3 - Organizational coaching program: Collaboration & Teambuilding	UVT, UEL, DRIFT	Poznan	A Coruna, Sarajevo, Malaga, Nicosia
Reflexive monitoring workshops and webinars				
10.09.2018	Webinar reflexive monitoring - to introduce reflexive monitoring to the FRC's	DRIFT	Genk, Poznan & Glasgow	
20.11.2018	Workshop on the reflexive monitoring methodology in Rotterdam - to introduce Reflexive monitoring and facilitate peer-2-peer learning	DRIFT	Genk, Poznan & Glasgow	
12.12.2018	Webinar reflexive monitoring - to introduce reflexive monitoring to the FFC's	DRIFT		Pavlos Melas, Burgas, Malaga, A Coruna, Sarajevo, Ioannina, Nicosia

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23.01.2019	Workshop on reflexive monitoring during the 'Learning Transfer Workshop' in Nicosia	DRIFT,	Genk, Poznan & Glasgow	Pavlos Melas, Burgas, Malaga, A Coruna, Sarajevo, Ioannina, Nicosia
10-6-2019	FFC RM in practice 1-on-1 webinars	Igno Notermans and Daan Sillen (DRIFT)		Ioannina
13-6-2019	FFC RM in practice 1-on-1 webinars	Igno Notermans and Daan Sillen (DRIFT)		Nicosia
14-6-2019	FFC RM in practice 1-on-1 webinars	Igno Notermans and Daan Sillen (DRIFT)		A Coruna
16-7-2019	FFC RM in practice 1-on-1 webinars	Igno Notermans and Daan Sillen (DRIFT)		Bologna
17-6-2019	FFC RM in practice 1-on-1 webinars	Igno Notermans and Daan Sillen (DRIFT)		Sarajevo
18-6-2019	FFC RM in practice 1-on-1 webinars	Igno Notermans and Daan Sillen (DRIFT)		Malaga
19-6-2019	FFC RM in practice 1-on-1 webinars	Igno Notermans and Daan Sillen (DRIFT)		Pavlos Melas
25-9-2019	FFC RM in practice 1-on-1 webinars	Igno Notermans and Daan Sillen (DRIFT)		Burgas
6-5-2021	1-On-1 Support – for FFCs, to support development of RM Chapter of CN Framework report	Shibeal Mc Cann, Kato Allaert, Marleen Lodder (DRIFT)		Ioannina
14-4-2021	1-On-1 Support – for FFCs, to support development of RM Chapter of CN Framework report	Shibeal Mc Cann, Kato Allaert, Marleen Lodder (DRIFT)		Nicosia
15-4-2021	1-On-1 Support – for FFCs, to support development of RM Chapter of CN Framework report	Shibeal Mc Cann, Kato Allaert, Marleen Lodder (DRIFT)		A Coruna
16-4-2021	1-On-1 Support – for FFCs, to support development of RM Chapter of CN Framework report	Shibeal Mc Cann, Kato Allaert, Marleen Lodder (DRIFT)		Sarajevo
22-4-2021 6-5-2021	1-On-1 Support – for FFCs, to support development of RM Chapter of CN Framework report	Shibeal Mc Cann, Kato Allaert, Marleen Lodder (DRIFT)		Malaga
22-4-2021	1-On-1 Support – for FFCs, to support development of RM Chapter of CN Framework report	Shibeal Mc Cann, Kato Allaert, Marleen Lodder (DRIFT)		Pavlos Melas
15-4-2021	1-On-1 Support – for FFCs, to support development of RM Chapter of CN Framework report	Shibeal Mc Cann, Kato Allaert, Marleen Lodder (DRIFT)		Burgas
Learning experience webinars frontrunner cities				
20-6-2019 23-3-2020 21-9-2020 9-6-2021	Learning Experience Webinars - to Identify lessons about co-production that are captured through reflexive monitoring (input for co-production analysis)	Different element leads	The Reflexive monitors of Genk, Glasgow, Pozan, and some of their teammates	

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	- to reflect and facilitate peer-to-peer learning on the method of reflexive monitoring, introduction of learning outcomes structure			
Learning sessions frontrunner cities				
1-10-2018 9-10-2018 6-11-2018 6-12-2018	Learning session Genk 2018 -[4x]	DRIFT as Reflexive monitoring coach, elements leads for Co-production, technical solutions, impact assessment, governance e.a.	Peter Vos, (the Reflexive monitor of Genk) and teammembers (e.g. Mien Quartier, Katrien van de Sijpe)	
8-1-2019 14-2-2019 2-4-2019 5-6-2019 22-10-2019 16-12-2019 6-1-2020	Learning session Genk 2019 -[7x]	DRIFT as Reflexive monitoring coach, elements leads for Co-production, technical solutions, impact assessment, governance e.a.	Peter Vos, (the Reflexive monitor of Genk) and teammembers (e.g. Mien Quartier, Katrien van de Sijpe)	
4-3-2020 15-6-2020 3-9-2020 10-11-2020	Learning session Genk 2020 [4x]	DRIFT as Reflexive monitoring coach	Peter Vos, (the Reflexive monitor of Genk) and teammembers (e.g. Mien Quartier, Katrien van de Sijpe)	
15-2-2021 29-3-2021 1-6-2021	Learning session Genk 2021 -[3x]	DRIFT as Reflexive monitoring coach	Peter Vos, (the Reflexive monitor of Genk) and teammembers (e.g. Mien Quartier, Katrien van de Sijpe)	
3-10-2018 16-10-2018 13-11-2018 18-12-2018	Learning session Glasgow 2018 - [4x]	DRIFT as Reflexive monitoring coach, elements leads for Co-production, technical solutions, impact assessment, governance e.a.	the Reflexive monitors of Glasgow (Gilian Dick, Sean Kelly) and teammembers	
15-1-2019 22-1-2019 19-2-2019 19-3-2019 18-4-2019 21-5-2019 18-6-2019 9-2019 10-2019 12-2019	Learning session Glasgow 2019 - [9x]	DRIFT as Reflexive monitoring coach, elements leads for Co-production, technical solutions, impact assessment, governance e.a.	the Reflexive monitors of Glasgow (Gilian Dick, Sean Kelly) and teammembers	
30-1-2020 5-3-2020 1-4-2020 28-4-2020 23-6-2020 22-9-2020 17-12-2020	Learning session Glasgow 2020 - [7x]	DRIFT as Reflexive monitoring coach, elements leads for Co-production, technical solutions, impact assessment, governance e.a.	the Reflexive monitors of Glasgow (Gilian Dick, Sean Kelly) and teammembers (laura, Rania)	
14-4-2021 8-6-2021	Learning session Glasgow 2021 - [2x]	DRIFT as Reflexive monitoring coach, elements leads for Co-production, technical solutions, impact assessment, governance e.a.	the Reflexive monitors of Glasgow (Gilian Dick, Sean Kelly) and teammembers (laura, Rania)	

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5-10-2018 15-11-2018 5-12-2018	Learning session Poznan 2018 - [3x]	DRIFT as Reflexive monitoring coach, elements leads for Co-production, technical solutions, impact assessment, governance e.a.	the reflexive monitor of Poznan and teammembers (Agnieszka D. & Natalia)	
8-1-2019 12-2-2019 15-03-2019 26-3-2019 10-4-2019 17-5-2019 11-6-2019 19-10-2019 11-12-2019	Learning session Poznan 2019 - [9x]	DRIFT as Reflexive monitoring coach, elements leads for Co-production, technical solutions, impact assessment, governance e.a.	the reflexive monitor of Poznan and teammembers (Agnieszka D. & Natalia)	
28-1-2020 18-2-2020 17-3-2020 30-4-2020 18-6-2020 3-9-2020 5-11-2020	Learning session Poznan 2020 - [7x]	DRIFT as Reflexive monitoring coach, elements leads for Co-production, technical solutions, impact assessment, governance e.a.	the reflexive monitor of Poznan and teammembers (Agnieszka D. & Natalia)	
8-2-2021; 30-3-2021; 10-6-2021	Learning session Poznan 2021 - [3x]	DRIFT as Reflexive monitoring coach, elements leads for Co-production, technical solutions, impact assessment, governance e.a.	the reflexive monitor of Pzanan (Natalia)	
Learning platform webinars				
5-10-2020	Learning Platform webinar #0 - to set up the structure for Knowledge transfer – phase 2 and 1-on-1 learning sessions FRC & FFC	Leads of WP 2 and WP4, Knowledge hub leads [DRIFT, TCD, Green space schotland, Climate alliance, Horizon NUA, ICLEI, OPPLA]	Genk, Glasgow, Poznan	
7-12-2020	Learning Platform webinar #1 - to identify learning question sfor the knowledge hubs	Leads of WP 2 and WP4, Knowledge hub leads [DRIFT, OSMOS, UVT, ICLEI, Climate Alliance, TDC, UIRS, UBER, UDC, UEL, AMU, GeoGraphic, CENS, Bioazul, UBER, OPPLA, Green space schotland, Horizon NUA]	Genk, Glasgow, Poznan	Pavlos Melas, Burgas, Malaga, A coruna, Sarajevo, Ioannina, Nicosia
26-5-2021	Learning Platform webinar #2 - to validate findings from the learning objectives analysis and identify learning question sfor the knowledge hubs	Leads of WP 2 and WP4, Knowledge hub leads [DRIFT, OSMOS, UVT, ICLEI, Climate Alliance, TDC, UIRS, UBER, UDC, UEL, AMU, GeoGraphic, CENS, Bioazul, UBER, OPPLA, Green space schotland, Horizon	Genk, Glasgow, Poznan	Pavlos Melas, Burgas, Malaga, A coruna, Sarajevo, Nicosia

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		NUA		
20-10-2020	Learning Platform webinar #3 - to validate findings from the (extended) learning objectives analysis and look ahead with the knowledge hubs	OSMOS, UVT, ICLEI, Climate Alliance, TDC, UIRS, UBER, UDC, UEL, AMU, GeoGraphic, CENS, Bioazul, UBER, OPPLA, Green space schotland	Genk, Glasgow, Poznan	Pavlos Melas, Burgas, Malaga, A coruna, Sarajevo, Ioannina, Nicosia
1-on-1 Learning sessions frontrunner cities and fast follower cities				
30-11-2020 03-2021 07-2021	1-on-1 learning sessions FRC &FFC: [3x]	Dimitra Xidou (TCD)	Genk	Burgas
17-11-2020 03-2021 07-2021	1-on-1 learning sessions FRC &FFC: [3x]	Dimitra Xidou (TCD)	Genk	Pavlos melas
5-11-2020 03-2021 07-2021	1-on-1 learning sessions FRC &FFC: [3x]	Dimitra Xidou (TCD)	Glasgow	A Coruna
3-12-2020 03-2021 07-2021	1-on-1 learning sessions FRC &FFC: [3x]	Dimitra Xidou (TCD)	Glasgow	Malaga
3-12-2020 03-2021 07-2021	1-on-1 learning sessions FRC &FFC: [3x]	Dimitra Xidou (TCD)	Glasgow	Sarajevo
2-12-2020 03-2021 07-2021	1-on-1 learning sessions FRC &FFC: [3x]	Dimitra Xidou (TCD)	Poznan	Ioannina
30-11-2020 03-2021 07-2021	1-on-1 learning sessions FRC &FFC: [3x]	Dimitra Xidou (TCD)	Poznan	Nicosia
Webinars and workshops on the Connectign nature Framework				
21-4-2020	PSC call - first ideas on figure & terminology	DRIFT, TDC, UEL, Horizon Nua, ICLEI, UDC	Genk, Poznan, Glasgow	
14-5-2020	Working group session #1 - First ideas on figure & terminology	Stuart Connop (UEL), Isobel Fletcher (Horizon Nua), Marleen Lodder (DRIFT), Kato Allaert (DRIFT), Dimitra Xidou (TDC), Graphic designer	Poznan, Glasgow	Pavlos melas, A Coruna
26-5-2020	Working group session #2 - evaluate first designs for figure & terminology	Stuart Connop (UEL), Isobel Fletcher (Horizon Nua), Marleen Lodder (DRIFT), Kato Allaert (DRIFT), Dimitra Xidou (TDC), Graphic designer	Poznan, Glasgow	Pavlos melas, A Coruna
2-6-2020	Working group session #3 - finalize figure & terminology	Stuart Connop (UEL), Isobel Fletcher (Horizon Nua), Marleen Lodder (DRIFT), Kato Allaert (DRIFT), Dimitra Xidou (TDC), Graphic designer	Poznan, Glasgow	Pavlos melas, A Coruna
9-6-2020	PSC call – present proposed Framework figure	TDC, UEL, Horizon Nua, ICLEI, DRIFT,	Genk, Poznan, Glasgow	Pavlos Melas, Burgas, Malaga, A

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		UDC		coruna, Sarajevo, Ioannina, Nicosia
15-7-2020	Webinar: Re-introduction to Connecting nature framework	DRIFT	Genk, Poznan, Glasgow	Pavlos Melas, Burgas, Malaga, A coruna, Sarajevo, Ioannina, Nicosia
5-5-2021	CN Framework narrative workshop	Kato and Shibeal (DRIFT), Svenja (Climate Alliance), Gerardo (BioAzul), Dimitra (TDC), Paulina (UEL)	Glasgow	Malaga, Sarajevo & A Coruna
11-5-2021	CN Framework narrative workshop	Kato and Shibeal (DRIFT), Svenja (Climate Alliance), Gerardo (BioAzul), Dimitra (TDC), Paulina (UEL)	Genk	Burgas & Pavlos Melas
12-5-2021	CN Framework narrative workshop	Marleen and Shibeal (DRIFT), Svenja (Climate Alliance), Gerardo (BioAzul), Dimitra (TDC), Paulina (UEL)	Poznan	Nicosia & Ioannina
Webinars & workshops for multiplier cities				
5-3-2020	Webinar #7, The value of reflexive monitoring for nature-based solutions project - part of webinar #7 of the urbanByNature programme, Brazilian stream (@BR) https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DThsJldv6iY	Marleen Lodder - DRIFT, ICLEI		
9-7-2018	A workshop with the Brazilian multiplier cities about co-production principles by the ICLEI team in Brasilia (09.07.2018).	Katharina Holscher DRIFT, ICLEI		
11-07-2019	Webinar#2, How to foster co-creation for NBS implementation? - Part of the Brazilian stream of UrbanByNature	Katharina Holscher - DRIFT, ICLEI		
25-6-2020	Webinar #2: How to co-create Nature-based solutions? - Part of the Caucasus stream of UrbanBynature	Kato Allaert- DRIFT, ICLEI		
27-10-2021	Urban by Nature webinar – China on Co-production https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5PI3ss3ZPf0&t=17s	Carien van der Have - DRIFT, ICLEI		
December 2021 - march 2022	Online learning track on co-production within the context of nature-based solutions - Four workshops for 35 registrants, learning about co-production for naturebased solutions, in collaboration with UrbanByNature.	Marieke Verhagen, Giorgia Silvestri – DRIFT, ICLEI		

Appendix D: Learning outcomes Front-runner Cities

GECTP = CTP of Genk

GLCTP = CTP of Glasgow

POCTP = CTP of Poznan

In black the CTPs from 2019-2020

In green the CTPs from 2020-2021

#	Learning outcomes	CTP	LQ
1	To overcome barrier of siloed organisation, novel governance structures were developed to allow cross- organisational collaboration	GECTP3.19+4.10; GECTP 3.25; GECTP3.28; GECTP3.40; GECTP11.33b GLCTP 15C; GLCTP2.16 POCTP2+3.5+5.3;	GELQ3.41 GLLQ2.16.1
2	To overcome challenges of involving enterprises in NBS delivery, innovative approaches were developed to collaborate with and support enterprises	GECTP#; GECTP3.29 GLCTP 5.3 POCTP2;	POLQ2.2
3	New opportunities detected to expand the scope of the NBS exemplar.	GECTP#; GLCTP15B; POCTP3; POCTP2.6;	POLQ2.6;
4	Find opportunities to keep colleagues engaged	GECTP3.17; GECTP5.12 GLCTP2; POCTP3.1; POCPT3.2 (old); POCTP3.3; POCTP3.6; POCTP3.2 (new); POCTP5.4	GLLQ2.0 POLQ3.2
5	From barriers to opportunities by capacity building to facilitate NBS co-production by communities	GECTP3.18 GLCTP4+6; GLCTP3.1; GLCTP2.6a POCTP3.7	

6	Continuation activities beyond Connecting Nature	GECTP6.27; GLCTP7.1+7.2; POCTP5.2	
7	Using city-wide events, strategies to present the narrative of NBS exemplar to increase (political) support	GECTP5.12; GLCTP7+8; GLCTP7.2 POCTP4	GLLQ7.1
8	Opportunity to include nbs into multiannual budgets and policy planning	GECTP6.18; GECTP6.26; POCTP5	
9	Opportunities to utilize 'grey solution'-budgets for nature-based solutions	GECTP 6.31+6.20+3.18; GLCTP5; POCTP 5.3+2	
10	Opportunities to develop novel co-production approaches	GECTP11.22+6.30; GECTP11.32; GECTP11.33a; GECTP11.34; GECTP11.37 GLCTP15a; GLCTP2.6 POCTP5.3	GELQ11.11; GELQ11.10; GELQ11.12
11	Switch between strategic and operational levels	GECTP6.28+14.3; GECTP6.37; GLCTP11 POCTP3.3; POCTP2.4;	POLQ2.3;
12	Opportunities for upscaling based on implementation of exemplar by other actors	GECTP11.27; GECTP11.26; GECTP11.35; GLCTP8; POCTP5.3; POCTP1.1; POCTP2.3	POLQ1.3; POLQ2.1; POLQ2.3
13	Barrier to attract local partners with co-production skills	GECTP11.25+11.23; POCTP2+5	

14	Shifting from Planning to Delivery requires change of governance styles	GECTP3.26; GLCTP2.6; POCTP 3.3:	GELQ3.13 GLLQ2.6 POLQ3.1
15	External funding applications based on CN Framework, perceived as recognition for innovative work	GECTP3.44; POCTP2	POCTP2.1
16	Replicating innovative structures developed in CN result in new practices of other departments.	GECTP14.7; GLCTP2.2; GLCTP2.3	GLLQ2.3.1
17	Simple communication about NBS is not easy but is very effective to get strategic actors involved	GECTP11.34b POCTP5.4	POLQ5.3
18	CN Framework can be used as to report on progress of nature-based solution projects (e.g. gap-analysis).	GLCTP15;	GLLQ

#	Similar barriers / opportunities that resulted in innovations in cities	Reflexive Learning Outcomes in terms of changes in the context (rule, relation, practice, discourse)			Innovation area (CN Framework)		
		Genk	Glasgow	Poznan	Genk	Glasgow	Poznan
1	<p>To overcome barrier of siloed organisation, novel governance structures were developed to allow cross- organisational collaboration</p> <p>GECTP3.19+4.10: Designing and introducing a novel governance model for more effective formats and methods to achieve the implementation of the Stiemer Programme</p> <p>GECTP3.25: The team realised that they work differently than the permits department but that they have no intention of trying to change the permits department way of working (practice).</p> <p>GECTP3.28: First time our director explicitly promotes a different way of tendering of a sewage project, turning it into an integral redevelopment process.</p> <p>GECTP3.40: Meta-analysis of Stiemerprogramme</p>	<p>GECTP 3.19+4.10 New practices and relations because of different types of meetings (more single purpose rather than steering committees) and new ways of working with and involving actors for these meetings. New rules coming out of the new governance model in terms of how the project manager organises the Stiemerday meetings, who is involved, what the focus and meeting format</p>	<p>GLCTP 15C: The team invested in the relation with NS that now seems to pay off in this novel governance structure for cross-service collaboration. This would be a solution to create collaboration on the stewardship phase of the NBS by combining the budgets of the multiple service agencies.</p> <p>GLCTP2.16:</p>	<p>POCTP2+3.5+5.3:In collaborations , the city team, bringing in their budget and knowledge, wants to team up with partners that can invest.</p> <p>This approach leads to new relations, by opening up from a focus on collaborations with other departments</p>	<p>GECTP 3.19+4.1 Co-production: Monthly Stiemerday has a new structure, in which project partners (internal and external) can easily collaborate.</p> <p>GECTP 3.19+4.1 Indicators: Implementing policy plan also creates need for indicators</p> <p>GECTP 3.19+4.1 GECTP3.19+4.1 Financing:</p>	<p>GLCTP15C Financing: Potentially, because it will be easier to combine budgets under this governance structure. To make sure that you can access multiple budgets.</p> <p>GLCTP15C Governance: it is a novel governance structure that needs to be set up.</p> <p>GLCTP2.16:Governance: the</p>	<p>POCTP2+3.5 +5.3 Co-production: The city team will collaborate with external partners such as district councils, citizens, enterprises.</p> <p>POCTP2+3.5 +5.3 Governance: The city team will further collaborate with other city hall departments</p> <p>POCTP2+3.5</p>

<p>and governance model. By explicitly unravelling its structure and components and by copying it to other programmes (e.g. energy), the team gained thorough understanding of our governance models and its constituent parts.</p> <p>GECTP11.33b: Participation Session Slagmolen Environment: Participation process for 1 of 4 pilot projects</p> <p>3) Participation triggered department of Mobility to couple their projects to Stiemer Programme (co-benefit of participation).</p> <p>4) For process to be better rooted, next time more upfront engagement of key-stakeholders</p> <p>GLCTP15C: Identified the need of a cross-service strategy (with DRS, education, ... plus outside GCC) will result in an innovative governance structure. This has been a challenge for a long time, and would be a big breakthrough if it's realised – which has a good chance.</p> <p>GLCTP2.16: The team realized that there is a lack of consistent, established and agreed internal cross-</p>	<p>will be, etc.</p> <p>GECTP3.25: This realisation was a learning moment for the team and creates a new discourse for them on how to collaborate with other departments and be flexible to other ways of working, to get the most out of it for the team's projects.</p> <p>GECTP3.28: It is a new practice to collaborate directly with the sewage infrastructure partners instead of via the city's Infrastructure department. The practice is not yet institutionalised so it hasn't led to new rules yet.</p>	<p>The structure that the team designed for the Open Space team is a new rule. The structure is inspired by their reflexive monitoring process, the learnings sessions, how they internally discuss the tracker and how they prepare for these meetings.</p> <p>GLCTP2.16: The open space team meeting is also a new practice for the team. It also affects relations as already existing relationships</p>	<p>to city districts and inhabitants (for now) to also include enterprises.</p> <p>It could <i>potentially</i> change the city team's practice, as working with a new type of partners requires this.</p> <p>It could <i>potentially</i> also broaden the discourse on how other partners use nature-based solutions.</p> <p>CTP3.5: By empowering partners, the</p>	<p>Financing of the policy plan is also a challenge.</p> <p>GECTP3.19+4.1 Governance: New organisational strategies are developed.</p> <p>GECTP3.25: Governance: related to collaboration within the city hall.</p> <p>GECTP3.28: Governance: related to new practices and relations within departments and with project partners. This means that we change from working</p>	<p>open space team meeting and the underlying structure are part of a new governance approach.</p>	<p>+5.3 Financing: The collaborations are co-financed with the external partners.</p> <p>POCTP2+3.5 +5.3 Technical solutions: <i>potential</i> impact on the type of technical solutions that are implemented</p> <p>POCTP2+3.5 +5.3 Entrepreneurship: <i>potential</i> impact on how entrepreneurs work with nature-based</p>
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<p>service governance structure at management/senior management level. They therefore established Open Space team meeting with key officers at operational management level that focuses on the 15 themes of the Open Space Strategy. This meeting formalizes what was previously an informal networking process.</p> <p>GLLQ2.16.1: How do we develop an internal governance structure that is sustainable?</p> <p>POCTP2+3.5+5.3: The city team realized that their work on the project needs to shift more towards promoting nature-based solutions among other partners (like departments/district councils/by working on proposal Norwegian fund) that could co-finance the solution.</p> <p>POCTP5.3: New opportunity to collaborate with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - another department dealing with district councils for nature-based solutions - with colleagues from our 	<p>GECTP3.28: This leads to novel relations between the team's department and the Infrastructure department as well as between the team and the sewage infrastructure partners. It can lead to a new collaboration model for similar sewage projects in the city of Genk.</p> <p>GECTP3.40: It is a novel practice to integrate transition management and innovation management in the governance model.</p> <p>GECTP3.40: The coalition management leads to novel</p>	<p>became more established through the open space team meeting.</p>	<p>team creates new relations and is changing a discourse. They stimulate others to think about their work in relation to nature-based solutions. This way the concept of nature-based solutions gets internalised by the partners as well.</p> <p>CTP 5.3: New collaborations with another department and unit leads to new</p>	<p>with partners such as Fluvius and Infrac (sewage infrastructure) via the Infrastructure department towards directly collaborating with them to create an integrated development process.</p> <p>GECTP3.40: Governance: related to the governance model</p> <p>GECTP11.33b: Governance: collaboration and strategic alignment with mobility department.</p>		<p>solutions</p> <p>CTP5.3: Technical solutions: Implementing nature-based solutions in shared backyards.</p> <p>Co-production: Through the collaboration between other departments , the district council and the team, the departments and district council will become involved in co-production.</p> <p>Financing: opportunities</p>
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	<p>department (but another unit) who implement a programme “Change your backyard” – revitalisation of shared backyards in the City centre.</p> <p>POCTP3.5: Towards empowering green agents and other partners rather than just collaborating with them</p>	<p>relations.</p> <p>GECTP3.40: The governance model in itself creates novel rules for how to implement the program on a strategic and operational level. There are two changes in discourse: the first one is related to how reflexive monitoring is implemented in a more accessible way, by naming it learning groups. Furthermore, it is a change in discourse to distinguish between the programme and project level.</p> <p>GECTP11.33b:</p>		<p>relations.</p> <p>The team will support both units by</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - promoting NBS among district councils - supporting “Change your backyard” program by rolling out nature-based solutions, this is a new practice. 			<p>s for sharing funding within department and with district councils.</p> <p>Governance: New organisational structures in the departments and with the district councils.</p> <p>Entrepreneurship: in relation to architects - promotion of NBS like natural playgrounds among different partners with their own budget create potential for</p>
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		<p>It is also a novel practice to include the mobility department. They were invited because of their expertise on this project but it led to alignment of several projects to create a more strategic way of operating together.</p>		<p>For the team, it also leads to a new discourse on how to collaborate and on the use of nature-based solutions.</p> <p>New rules regarding organisational structures and how to collaborate across siloes within the department are created.</p>			<p>NBS architects to multiply their work.</p> <p>CTP3.5: Governance: organisational innovation as a strategy for silo bursting</p>
2	<p>To overcome challenges of involving enterprises in NBS delivery, innovative approaches were developed to collaborate with and support enterprises</p> <p>GECTP#: Realised the need for clear</p>	<p>GECTP#: A rule?</p> <p>GECTP3.29: It is new in terms of relations and practices for the team to have this</p>	<p>GLCTP5.3: This way new relations are explored through the networks of</p>	<p>POCTP2:The framework is a novel practice and will result in legal rules</p>	<p>GECTP3.29: Governance: related to new practices and relations with project partners.</p>	<p>GLCTP5.3: Co-production: this is a novel way to co-produce a teaching</p>	<p>POCTP2: Co-production: this framework will be developed</p>

<p>formulation of what is a Stiemerdeal and what not.</p> <p>GECTP3.29: Procedure of 'Open Oproep' we used appointing Tractebel as agency for development of Masterplan allows for continued cooperation on the long term.</p> <p>GLCTP5.3: Collaboration on NBE program was established using local networks to identify suitable partners. These partners have reached out across their networks to promote the pilot programme and to help find NBE's to participate.</p> <p>GLLQ5.3: How can we use existing programmes like 'Stalled Spaces' to help identify spaces or pilot schemes/test beds for NBE participants?</p> <p>POCTP2: Because of the innovative activities that the Poznan team is doing, they realised the need for new frameworks to address the collaboration with enterprises.</p> <p>POCTP2.2: Working with a private sponsor requires more time at first but can result in a well-designed process and more financing</p>	<p>type of collaboration. The team has realised that their long-term relationship with Tractebel is very symbiotic: Tractebel knows and works with the nature-based solutions strategy of the city since the beginning. It also simplifies the tendering process, not having to look for a new supplier for every phase. The long-term partner knows the project and can easily continue, so it saves the team time.</p>	<p>partners</p> <p>GLCTP5.3: The new practice is to work with enterprises, to develop the NBE program makes them think about what the team would like to teach the NBEs.</p>	<p>guiding future collaboration with commercial enterprises that work on nature-based solutions.</p> <p>POCTP2.2: The relation with the private company is new but worked out this time because team realized their strength is setting expectations about the quality.</p> <p>POCTP2.2 Practice: due to the covid pandemic and this</p>		<p>programme together with local partners</p> <p>GLCTP5.3: Financing: The programme includes content around how enterprises can be funded and what sort of business modelling they could adopt.</p> <p>GLCTP5.3: Entrepreneurs hip: this programme is developed to attract more NBEs</p> <p>GLCTP5.3: Governance: because they also collaborate with the centre for civic innovation and</p>	<p>together with interested commercial enterprises.</p> <p>POCTP2: Governance: new legal rules open up for new collaborations and a new type of governance.</p> <p>POCTP2.2: Co-production: process together with schools and sponsors. The Sponsors where not very eager to be involved. There needs</p>
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	<p>possibilities.</p> <p>POLQ2.2: How to identify and involve private sponsors in the up-scaling activities?</p>			<p>intermediary role of the team and the school, the company and their own director, it takes more time. But also because it's the first time they are doing this.</p>		<p>it is a novel way how collaboration is set up</p>	<p>to be a clear offer for sponsors / businesses to be involved, but also flexibility to co-create the offer with the schools and potential sponsor.</p> <p>POCTP2.2: Governance: align financing with internal requirements</p> <p>POCTP2.2: Financing: working with a private company is a novel way of funding nbs</p>
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3	<p>New opportunities detected to expand the scope of the NBS exemplar.</p> <p>GECTP#: Suds and Soda from Genk came from tour Glasgow / interaction with Stuart about what SUDS are and resulted in the uptake of this project in the Stiemer Valley.</p> <p>GLCTP15B: Realised they can learn from the way communities organise themselves during COVID around local challenges can be connected to the need for NBS in the area, to improve the OSS.</p> <p>POCTP3: Application to Norwegian fund opens new opportunities to work together with the Department of Education on schools with a different target audience (children from 7-12) and other types of NBS.</p> <p>POCTP2.6: Having 2 instead of 5 playgrounds is not a problem, but an opportunity to deepen. It means that the team has more time to look after</p>	<p>GECTP#: Suds and Soda from Genk came from tour Glasgow / interaction with Stuart about what SUDS are and resulted in the uptake of this project in the Stiemer Valley. This was a novel practice because in Genk they did not implement SUDS yet.</p>	<p>GLCTP15B:Practice: The local residents didn't have access to high quality open space in the neighborhood . The pandemic made them organise themselves to clean up their courtyards and the connected area with beds. These spaces are not mapped on oss because they are on private land. The CN-team realized when they map these type of initiatives</p>	<p>POCTP3: New relations with schools for children of age 7 to 12 and further collaborations with the Department of Education. The new target audience (primary school in steads of kindergartens) asks for a different approach regarding the type of NBS and the co-production process.</p> <p>POCTP3: New</p>	<p>GECTP# Technical Solutions: there was always an ambition to include SuDS in the exemplar in Genk. The conversations evolved into an exploration of how to build engagement and capacity into the SuDS ambition through innovation and demonstration. This has led to the inclusion of nature-based solution SuDS engagement and demonstration</p>	<p>GLCTP15B:Co-Production: learn how communities organise themselves – to uses when designing CP process</p> <p>GLCTP15B:Governance: how you relate to these initiatives, reflect upon what the role of GCC/OSS/CN-team is.</p>	<p>POCTP3: Co-production: Involving primary school kids in the design, delivery and stewardship requires a different co-production process with novel tools, e.g. digital.</p> <p>POCTP3: Technical solutions: Developing other types of playgrounds for older kids is a new technical solution to fit the new</p>

	<p>them, to enrich the co-creation process to find more innovative solutions.</p>		<p>they can learn from this practice to improve their OSS in terms of e.g. how they relate to each other and reflect on how to support these types of initiatives.</p>	<p>practice of linking the investment in the NBS with educational value of the NBS in the proposal. This is also done in the NBS projects with the kindergartens , but for older kids this requires different materials to be developed. As one of the schools is involved in another project linking ecological aspects with IT solutions, this opens-up a novel way</p>	<p>n in the Stiemer Vallei programme and more broadly.</p>		<p>target audience.</p> <p>POCTP3: Financing: The Norwegian fund was discovered by the head of the department and requires the development of a new model for linking NBS investment with educational value.</p> <p>POCTP3: Governance: further collaboration with Department</p>
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			<p>of interacting via digital applications.</p> <p>POCTP2.6: It is a novel practice for the team to move from replicating nbs projects to deepening them (designs for schools instead of kindergartens).</p> <p>POCTP2.6: It is a novel relation to have the councillors involved.</p> <p>POCTP2.6: This might potentially lead to a</p>			<p>of Education on a new age group and new collaboration with schools.</p> <p>POCTP2.6: Co-production: different type of CP with the schools</p> <p>POCTP2.6: Technical solutions: the design of the natural playgrounds for schools of older children is very different than that of younger kids.</p>
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				change in discourse about nature-based solutions.			<p>POCTP2.6: Financing: Novel financing options through civic budget and collaboration with private companies.</p> <p>POCTP2.6: Governance: how the team works in relation to the councillors involved.</p>
4	<p>Find opportunities to keep colleagues engaged</p> <p>GECTP3.17: Initiating a supervision meeting appears to be a good solution to adopt Stiemer Masterplan vision in other projects/initiatives of Stad Genk.</p> <p>GLCTP2:</p>	<p>GECTP3.17: This new supervision team meets on a monthly basis and brings together colleagues from different departments that all have an impact</p>	<p>GLCTP2: Face to face conversations are very beneficial and provide opportunity to have more informal</p>	<p>POCTP3.1: The Poznan team can use this new lens to create new relations. For example, to talk to the maintenance department</p>	<p>GECTP3.17: Technical solutions: During this meeting the technical solutions are discussed with the</p>	<p>GLCTP2: Technical solutions: On site it was easier to see and evaluate the topography, constraints,</p>	<p>POCTP3.1: Technical solutions: this new lens facilitates identification of already implemented</p>

<p>Discovering how effective site visits can be to strengthen relations with and learn about projects of colleagues from other departments.</p> <p>POCTP3.1: Looking at Poznan through a lens of nature-based solutions made the team realize that the tram tracks are nature-based solutions as well.</p> <p>POCPT3.2 (old): Collaboration of the Poznan team in URBACTIII Health & Green space project opens doors for collaboration with other city hall departments.</p> <p>POCTP3.3: During a H&G workshop with core group of local URBACT members green agents cross-departments found each other and became enthusiastic about future collaborations. Expected change: enhancing and enriching the Connecting Nature impact on the activities of the project team and Poznań City Hall, increasing awareness concerning NBS in Poznań City Hall and Poznań.</p> <p>POCTP3.2 (new): Investing in well-organised meetings pays off in terms of ownership. The eyeopener</p>	<p>because they are responsible for the implementation of parts of the Master plan of the Stierner Valley. The 'designers' of the Masterplan and the Genk-team organise this meeting to 'safe-guard' that everything is in line with the vision of the masterplan. Herewith the Genk-team is supervising implementation of masterplan of Stierner. These new regular meetings are a new practice for the actors involved because before they got a task assigned that they executed without being</p>	<p>conversations (e.g. on the train, outside of the office). This helps to strengthen the relation between the colleagues from different departments. This will become a new practice because it is good to have these face to face conversations with colleagues from different departments on a regular basis.</p>	<p>that oversees the tram tracks, to create awareness and potential collaborations on nature-based solutions. Realising that e.g. tram tracks in a grass beds are nature-based solutions creates an opportunity to change the discourse around nature-based solutions. For example, how to present what nature-based solutions are by presenting we already have a lot of them in our city.</p>	<p>responsible actors who will implement them and the actors who 'safe-guard' the vision of the masterplan.</p> <p>GECTP3.17: Governance: With this new supervision team, the organisational settings change.</p>	<p>access, etc.</p> <p>GLCTP2: Governance: It will become a new practice to meet with colleagues from different departments through site visits to strengthen the relation and as a good starting point for collaboration.</p>	<p>technical solutions in Poznan.</p> <p>POCTP3.1 Governance: the new lens provides opportunities to talk and work with different departments and change the governance of nbs.</p> <p>POCPT3.2: Governance: new organisational structures emerge (the URBACT local group) out of these new collaborations with other</p>
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<p>workshop confirmed that it is important for the strategic and operational people to meet. This is organised through core group and thematic groups of the Urbact Local Group.</p> <p>POCTP5.4: Communication is a powerful tool for promoting the work the team does on NBS, especially connected to the H&G project. It helps to convince and educate top-level management, decision-makers and internal officers (who will be implementing the nbs).</p> <p>POLQ5.2: How to promote NBS among different partners?</p>	<p>involved in the bigger picture of the master plan process and all actors this involves.</p> <p>GECTP3.17: The relations between actors change because colleagues from different departments that usually don't work together, from now on meet on a regular basis in these meetings. Other departments involved are: permit department for private developments, spatial development department, department responsible for purchasing – important role</p>		<p>POCTP3.2: The visit from URBACTIII stakeholders accelerated the collaboration: the involvement of other departments was important and the site visit was a good incentive to realise new relations.</p> <p>POCTP3.3: Discovery through the workshop with core group of local URBACT members that there are "green agents" all over the city hall on the officers'</p>			<p>departments</p> <p>.</p> <p>POCTP3.3: Co-production: Potentially this process will lead to inviting people from outside the city hall to develop the nbs.</p> <p>POCTP3.3: Financing: Potentially this might lead to novel ways of financing by merging budgets between departments</p> <p>.</p>
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		<p>with link to impacts on Stiemer Valley. These meetings involve these departments with the architects of master plan to align their developments with the master plan. The meetings take place on a monthly basis.</p>		<p>rather than on the project lead or head of department levels. This resulted in new relations because these green agents currently rarely meet. POCTP3.3: Practices are changed to a more co-productive way of working. Activities that complement each other are created bottom-up on the initiative of the green agents (instead of because of the strategic alignment on a higher level). To</p>			<p>POCTP3.3: Governance: new organisational structures emerge out of these new collaborations with other departments .</p> <p>POCTP3.2: Governance: Collaboration between other departments and different levels at the city hall.</p> <p>POCTP5.4: Co-production: Communicating about projects can be used as a</p>
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			<p>burst silos, linking and meeting regularly with all green agents from across the city hall would be useful. Green agents generally have a better understanding of the barriers regarding nature-based solutions and how to overcome them.</p> <p>Exchange of knowledge is essential between “regular” city hall officers as it helps to solve many ambiguities at the planning stage of different NBS.</p>			<p>catalyst for internal co-production.</p> <p>POCTP5.4: Impact assessment: Indicators are used in the communication to prove nbs' effectiveness and keep colleagues critical.</p> <p>POCTP5.4: Technical solutions: Facilitates better communication about technical solutions?</p> <p>POCTP5.4:</p>
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				<p>[EXAMPLE: we were discussing in our ULG the possibility of building green tram track in the investment planned in the city centre. It seemed so obvious for many colleagues that this NBS is perfect for this. But the representative of Road Management Board explained in a very informative manner that there are some investments where such solutions are not possible,</p>			<p>Governance: Communication happens also via the green agents at the city hall.</p>
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			<p>but we might use some alternatives.]</p> <p>All of this will contribute to maintaining their enthusiasm and this momentum to collaborate on green projects (NBS) from the different departments.</p> <p>New rules about how to collaborate across departments are herewith being created through collaborating on NBS at the operational level.</p> <p>POCTP3.2: Relation:</p>			
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			<p>Strengthen existing relations by organising regular and well facilitated meetings with clear follow-up and clear aims. But also survey afterwards that they can give honest feedback confirmed this.</p> <p>POCTP3.2: Rule: potential governance structure that can be replicated for other type of project.</p> <p>POCTP3.2: Practice: Reaching decision</p>			
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			<p>makers can be a challenge but this can be done via operational people who have good connections to decision makers.</p> <p>POCTP5.4: Communicating about nbs projects helps to strengthen internal relations. Promoting nbs projects and spreading professional knowledge about them is a new practice that the team applies to prevent greenwashing and motivate professional civil servants</p>			
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				to stay critical about the quality and applicability of nbs. Update 30-03-2021: Through promotion and communication activities, the discourse is shifted from green to co-benefits.			
5	<p>Barriers to keep colleagues engaged</p> <p>GECTP5.12</p> <p>GL</p> <p>POCTP3.6: Confirmation of how important it is for the Poznan team to have in person meetings.</p>	<p>(from CTP5.12)</p> <p>Still, it remains a barrier to implement the support from the strategic level into the work of colleagues that take care of implementation and delivery. This struggle is similar to the one with the treehouse and the</p>		<p>POCTP3.6:</p> <p>The changes to how the team works due to the covid-19 crisis (remotely instead of together at the office) proved how important the practice of meeting in</p>			<p>POCTP3.6:</p> <p>Some activities related to co-production, governance and technical solutions are postponed because they can't be carried out online.</p>

		Coppeelaan project (at the strategic level they have the commitment, but at the operational level there are still many barriers).		person is.			
6	<p>From barriers to opportunities by capacity building to facilitate NBS co-production by communities</p> <p>GECTP3.18: Started experiment to include co-production process into the preparation of the tendering process for the SUDS&SODA project together with the department of Construction and Infrastructure to overcome gap between vision and implementation.</p> <p>GLCTP4+6: Identified the need to work towards a strategy for civil servants that can support capacity building in local communities to sustain and maintain long-term NBS.</p> <p>GLCTP4: Reframing workshops as training to engage people</p>	<p>GECTP3.18: For preparing tenders together with the department of Construction & Infra, co-production needs to be part of the process to make it successful, which requires a new relation. The Genk team realised that they speak a different language than the department of Building & Infra. They hope the co-production can close or at least</p>	<p>GLCTP4+6:The need for community capacity building made the team focus on the development of a new practice for educating their colleagues. A first step is to start tracking all the different existing tools in an organic way in the tracker.</p>	<p>POCTP3.7: It is a new practice for the team to make these instruction movies.</p>	<p>GECTP3.18: Co-production: The Genk team has developed a co-productive way of working with the department of Building & Infra.</p> <p>GECTP3.18: Technical Solutions: Co-creative approach in tendering procedure enables the</p>	<p>GLCTP4+6:Co-production: the capacity building strategy is closely linked to nbs co-production processes</p> <p>GLCTP4+6:Financing, business and governance models: knowledge on this is lacking in many community groups</p> <p>GLCTP4+6:Entr</p>	<p>POCTP3.7: Co-production: The movies will be used by teachers for (online) training, to teach kids about NBS but also for entertainment.</p> <p>POCTP3.7: Technical solutions: The movies, as a digital, online</p>

<p>GLCTP3.1: Working together virtually with Friends of groups is a new way of establishing these community groups. It is a hybrid between on the ground and virtual activities for the park. More of the Friends of groups means more representation which will make engagement easier when these spaces will be redeveloped but can also be challenging when groups have different goals.</p> <p>GLCTP2.6a: As a direct result of the changed working conditions during the pandemic, videos are now being developed for the capacity building of the <i>Friends of community groups</i>.</p> <p>POCTP3.7: The online instruction movies that the team made due to COVID-19 about the eco-demonstrators are a tool for ensuring the project's quality after Connecting Nature.</p>	<p>clarify the gap and help finding innovative solutions for tendering NBS by including e.g. environmental aspects into the criteria that are standard cost-quality criteria established for grey infrastructure.</p> <p>GECTP3.18: By including a co-production process into the procurement process, the procurement practice is meant to be changed.</p>	<p>Focusing on long-term community capacity building, also with regards to e.g. financing, is new for the team.</p> <p>GLCTP4: Survey participants in the Stalled Spaces project indicated to be interested in trainings rather than workshops.</p> <p>GLCTP4: This requires a change in discourse about how to present what GCC offers so it is interesting for</p>		<p>combining of different departmental goals into the Technical design.</p> <p>GECTP3.18:Governance: by changing the way of working into a co-productive way, a collaborative governance model is created</p>	<p>epreneurship: entrepreneurs hip spirit is also lacking amongst many community groups</p> <p>GLCTP4+6:Governance: project management and other skills gaps within local community groups who are taking responsibility for delivering NBS</p> <p>GLCTP4: Co-production: provision of trainings to engage/motivate communities and build capacity</p>	<p>resource, are a technical solution in itself.</p>
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			<p>participants.</p> <p>GLCTP4: It is also about new practices in how to engage with people and the strengthening /revising of relations between GCC and communities.</p> <p>GLCTP3.1: It is a novel practice for the Friends of groups, to have online activities they offer next to their offline work. GCC has facilitated new ways of working with these groups via their online resources.</p>			<p>GLCTP3.1:Governance: collaboration with the Friends of consultation is a novel governance process for the city</p> <p>GLCTP3.1:Co-production: The friends of groups are organising engagement activities with local actors, users, GCC, ...</p> <p>GLCTP3.1: Financing: Friends of groups have access to different kinds of funding than the council, which might bring new financing</p>	
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			<p>This new process is more efficient, so more groups are set up, more funding to be accessed and more relations being created.</p> <p>GLCTP2.6a: It is a new practice to use videos for capacity building of community groups.</p>			<p>opportunities</p> <p>GLCTP2.6a: Governance: new ways of capacity building of community groups.</p>	
7	<p>Continuation activities beyond CN</p> <p>GECTP6.27: Because the Genk team invested in process innovation with strategic partners, they are now benefiting from funding received by one of those strategic partners.</p> <p>GLCTP7.1: Strategically using the COP26 and the Climate Emergency</p>	<p>GECTP6.27: New relations between actors increase reflexivity because strategic partnerships that benefit both parties are built. Involving strategic</p>	<p>GLCTP7.1+7.2 : A new discourse around nature-based solutions and open space is emerging: the work of the CN team can</p>	<p>POCTP5.2: The team realised that they need support from experts within the city government for dealing</p>	<p>GECTP6.27: The process innovation is the result of prior co-production activities of the Genk team with external</p>	<p>GLCTP7.1+7.2: Indicators: the impact of demonstrator projects is measured by indicators.</p> <p>All others</p>	<p>POCTP5.2: The new process will include all elements of the framework because it is about</p>

	<p>announcements</p> <p>GLCTP7.2: Identified the need for demonstrators and indicators to raise profile of OSS in different professional networks in order to be able to continue the OSS work after CN.</p> <p>POCTP5.2: CTP5.2: Scaling-up interventions like the nature-oriented playgrounds requires a novel process to ensure the quality of the intervention and new skills for the team.</p>	<p>partners in the process pays off. By "mainstreaming" the process, a process that was started by the Genk team, is continued by its strategic partners. The failed UIA application can be seen as a driver and this resulted in the fact that different partners find each other without us and the enthusiasm is contagious.</p> <p>New practices increase reflexivity because the Genk team and the strategic partners work together differently than before. The discourse changes as well because the involved</p>	<p>be linked to strategies from the COP26, the Climate Emergency call etc.</p>	<p>with multi-annual planning (upscaling). Additionally, they need expertise from CN partners for quality checks of interventions. This will be leading to new relations.</p> <p>It is a new process for them. The team's actions will contribute to new practices, when they are more structured. They are already taking</p>	<p>strategic actors who are now producing their own projects in line with the Stiemer Valley programme.</p> <p>GECTP6.27:It concerns attracted funding so it has an effect on financing, business and governance models.</p> <p>GECTP6.27:It is an example of a novel type of governance of nbs.</p>		<p>planning and upscaling the interventions</p>
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		partners can tell the narrative of the Stiemer Valley themselves without involvement of the Genk team.		action (e.g. manual on how to develop nature-oriented playground) but the actions don't happen in a structured way. They also realized at this stage it requires them taking the lead to continue what they started in Connecting Nature: other departments/actors wouldn't implement the gardens and playgrounds			
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				as the team wishes. It is still so novel that they need to be involved to secure the quality.			
8	<p>Using city-wide events/strategies to present the narrative of NBS exemplar to increase (political) support</p> <p>GECTP5.12: Positioning the Stiemer valley into a strategic narrative to be part of wider city strategies.</p> <p>GLCTP7+8: National Park City campaign being launched in Glasgow is an opportunity for CN and OSS.</p> <p>GLCTP7.2: The legacy of the summit has changed the discourse of how decision-makers are talking about NBS in Glasgow</p> <p>GLLQ7.1: How do we maximise the opportunity to use COP/fringe events as a platform to raise the profile of the open space strategy delivery plan</p>	<p>GECTP5.12: Having a narrative that relates to wider city and SDG strategies helps to include the Stiemer valley in policy plans by, for example, convincing decision-makers of the project's significance and herewith creating new relations. This increased support leads to a new discourse around the project's significance and the</p>	<p>GLCTP7+8: By being involved in the campaign, the CN team will develop new relations through the online forum and with the other stakeholders involved. Some of these stakeholders are organisations that the team hasn't worked with</p>	<p>POCTP4: By reaching out to private companies though the actor mapping, new relations are created. It is also a new practice to approach companies in this way as the team never participated/presented their activities</p>	<p>GECTP5.12: Financing: with the narrative the Stiemer valley is integrated in the policy plans which secures its financing.</p> <p>GECTP5.12: Governance: This learning relates to support of decision-makers for the project and how the project is</p>	<p>GLCTP7+8: Co-production: through collaboration in the campaign group.</p> <p>GLCTP7+8: Technical solutions: Delivery actors are involved in the campaign's network.</p> <p>GLCTP7+8: Financing: Participating in the network might also give</p>	<p>POCTP4: Co-production: This is a new co-production activity (actor mapping contractors).</p>

	<p>and nature-based solutions as an approach to key issues?</p> <p>POCTP4: Use Polish Eco fair in autumn 2020 to promote the Poznan Summit in summer of 2021 and to reach out to private companies (NBEs) as part of the mapping of potential contractors that can construct eco-demonstrators (FUA 2.2).</p>	<p>implementation and scaling of nbs.</p>	<p>previously.</p> <p>Glasgow's participation in the campaign will also lead to a new discourse on the impact of nbs.</p> <p>GLCTP7.2: The legacy of the summit has changed the discourse of how decision-makers are talking about NBS in Glasgow.</p>	<p>in fairs before.</p>	<p>backed up and funded internally.</p>	<p>ideas or opportunities for funding nbs.</p> <p>GLCTP7+8:Entrepreneurship: in the network multiple SMEs are included.</p> <p>GLCTP7+8:Governance: potential new collaboration with local communities, with other departments, with other stakeholders</p> <p>GLCTP7.2: Governance: different levels of GCC are being engaged via the Summit.</p>	
9	<p>Opportunity to include nbs into multiannual budgets and policy planning</p>	<p>GECTP6.18: They learned that the budgeting process</p>		<p>POCTP5: The</p>	<p>GECTP 6.18: Financing: This is now 5-</p>		<p>Poznan CTP5: The</p>

	<p>GECTP6.18: Realized that concrete budget estimate backfired because they had the feeling, they made presumptions about budgets that should not be made by the Genk-team because the mayor/policy makers don't want to see them upfront.</p> <p>GECTP6.26 "Good preparation is everything" The Genk team received full funding for the Stierner program because they (and the deputy mayor) prepared a very thorough project proposal.</p> <p>Glasgow: OSS itself</p> <p>POCTP5: Scaling-up interventions like the nature-oriented playgrounds requires a novel process to ensure the quality of the intervention and new skills for the team.</p>	<p>is not transparent, and they discovered that there are unwritten rules and important power relations. It is still a struggle how to build a good and trustworthy relationship with the city council.</p> <p>Because the team took the initiative the people in power felt overstepped. Also, a personal distrust between Katrien and Mayor means it is not clear how to proceed and position K in department. Combination of both made it backfire more (maybe if another department did this not that</p>		<p>team realised that they need support from experts within the city government for dealing with multi-annual planning (upscaling). Additionally, they need expertise from CN partners for quality checks of interventions. This will be leading to new relations.</p> <p>It is a new process for them. The team's actions will</p>	<p>year planning document, we learned for next time (beyond CN how to do this). Within CN it is hard to know what the impact is.</p> <p>GECTP 6.18: Governance: Internal lobbying as strategy how does it work? Not clear how this worked. Here they identified issues that need to be tackled.</p> <p>GECTP 6.26: Financing: It concerns funding applications so therefore touches upon financing,</p>		<p>new process will include all elements of the framework because it is about planning and upscaling the</p>
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		<p>complicated).</p> <p>There seemed to be unwritten rules that were now discovered and not followed. When they ask for the budget, we came up with a proposal. Also, because there were no rules for financial / budget planning yet. Because this was not there, they experimented this way. Normally this was largely done by the financial department. Normally incremental budgeting coordinated by financial department, they ask us for input. They now made a wish list.</p>		<p>contribute to new practices, when they are more structured. They are already taking action (e.g. manual on how to develop nature-oriented playground) but the actions don't happen in a structured way. They also realized at this stage it requires them taking the lead to continue what they started in Connecting</p>	<p>business and governance models.</p> <p>GECTP 6.26: Governance: the deputy mayor had a strong personality which helped to persuade the council.</p>		
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	<p>It was a novel practice for the team: they put in the financial plan, number and strategy. This seemed to be more information than they wanted at that point in time. They want that when they ask for it.</p> <p>GECTP 6.26:</p> <p>Despite fears that e.g. preparing the budget would backfire, the project proposal got granted. This is due to the clear budget and the advocating of the deputy mayor, who backed the proposal. Afterwards he said he could defend the project because the Genk-team</p>		<p>Nature: other departments/actors wouldn't implement the gardens and playgrounds as the team wishes. It is still so novel that they need to be involved to secure the quality.</p>			
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		<p>delivered very detailed plans. Other plans with less detailed planning and preparation did not receive funding.</p> <p>GECTP 6.26: New relations have been created by this way of working because Katrien and Peter are invited now to take this experience with them into the higher-level planning meetings.</p> <p>GECTP 6.26: Practices changed because now the Genk team will incorporate this way of working in future project proposals as well.</p>					
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10	<p>Opportunities to utilize ‘grey solution’- budgets for nature-based solutions</p> <p>GECTP 6.31+6.20+3.18: Breakthrough with getting an innovative nbs solution on a funding program for grey solutions.</p> <p>GLCTP5: Realising by connecting the OSS to the existing system of e.g. building applications, it is easier to update the OSS automatically.</p> <p>POCTP 5.3+2 Educational department;</p> <p>‘Change your back yard’; POCTP5.3: New opportunity to collaborate with: another department dealing with district councils for nature-based solutions and with colleagues from our department (but another unit) who implement a programme “Change your backyard” – revitalisation of shared backyards in the City centre.</p> <p>school playgrounds POCTP2: Application to Norwegian fund opens new opportunities to work together with the Department</p>	<p>GECTP 6.31+6.20+3.18: Environmental Agency) to allow applications for nature-based solutions (currently still needs to be approved by minister of Environment). They created a new category for 'pilot projects on climate adaptation'. This was the result of a process in which the Genk-team created novel relations to overcome the current systems' boundaries by breaking through the silo thinking culture. Other cities and their mayors contributed in raising the pressure to</p>	<p>GLCTP5: Connecting the OSS like this leads to new relations between the team and the department that updates the current system and between the team and the public that can update the OSS themselves.</p> <p>Linking the OSS system to the established system and having the possibility for the public to update it, is a new practice that moves towards a more integrated,</p>	<p>POCTP5.3: New opportunity to collaborate with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - another department dealing with district councils for nature-based solutions - with colleagues from our department (but another unit) who implement a 	<p>GECTP 6.31+6.20+3.18: Co-production: the change was the result of a process that involved multiple actors.</p> <p>GECTP 6.31+6.20+3.18: Technical solutions: it will contribute to the implementation of the SUDS and SODA project.</p> <p>GECTP 6.31+6.20+3.18: Governance: the new co-production process means changes for the internal</p>	<p>GLCTP5: Co-production: knowledge is collected by and with the local communities.</p> <p>GLCTP5: Indicators: because they are the key elements of the OSS</p> <p>GLCTP5: Governance: new collaboration with local communities and with other departments</p>	<p>POCTP5.3: Technical solutions: Implementing nature-based solutions in shared backyards.</p> <p>POCTP5.3:Co-production: Through the collaboration between other departments, the district council and the team, the departments and district council will become involved in co-production.</p>
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	<p>of Education on schools with a different target audience (children from 7-12) and other types of NBS.</p>	<p>change it. The organisation itself uses this change to create a novel discourse around the services they offer.</p>	<p>cross-departmental, participatory way of working.</p>	<p>programme “Change your backyard” – revitalisation of shared backyards in the City centre.</p> <p>POCTP2: New relations with schools for children of age 7 to 12 and further collaborations with the Department of Education. The new target audience (primary school instead of</p>	<p>organisation</p>		<p>POCTP5.3: Financing: opportunities for sharing funding within department and with district councils.</p> <p>POCTP5.3: Governance: New organisational structures in the departments and with the district councils.</p> <p>POCTP5.3: Entrepreneurship: in relation to architects - promotion of NBS like</p>
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			<p>kindergartens) asks for a different approach regarding the type of NBS and the co-production process.</p> <p>POCTP2: New practice of linking the investment in the NBS with educational value of the NBS in the proposal. This is also done in the NBS projects with the kindergartens , but for older kids this requires different materials to</p>			<p>natural playgrounds among different partners with their own budget create potential for NBS architects to multiply their work.</p> <p>POCTP2: Co-production: Involving primary school kids in the design, delivery and stewardship requires a different co-production process with novel tools,</p>
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			<p>be developed. As one of the schools is involved in another project linking ecological aspects with IT solutions ,this opens-up a novel way of interacting via digital applications.</p>		<p>e.g. digital.</p> <p>POCTP2: Technical solutions: Develop other types of playgrounds for older kids are new technical solutions to fit the new target audience.</p> <p>POCTP2: Financing: The Norwegian fund was discovered by the head of the department and requires the development</p>
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							<p>of a new model for linking NBS investment with educational value.</p> <p>POCTP2: Governance: further collaboration with Department of Education on a new age group and new collaboration with schools.</p>
11	<p>Opportunities to develop novel co-production approaches</p> <p>GECTP11.22+6.30: After the first unsuccessful process, an entirely new co-creation process has been designed for the Slagmolen area.</p> <p>GECTP11.32:</p>	<p>GECTP11.22+6.30 : The new co-creation process for the Slagmolen area is designed and thought-through beforehand compared to the</p>	<p>GLCTP15a:: Relation:</p> <p>The steering committee group of the Growchapel project in Drumchapel is</p>	<p>POCTP5.3: New collaborations with another department and unit leads to new</p>	<p>GECTP11.22+6.30: Co-production: novel approach for co-production process with Natuurpunt and other</p>	<p>GLCTP15a: Indicators: this will help to move forward form largely anecdotal evidence (via the indicators selected by</p>	<p>POCTP5.3: Technical solutions: Implementin g nature-based solutions in</p>

<p>Participation of “Friends of Stiemer” seemed very valuable, also in meeting with mainly experts. Participation was based on self-selection of participants who wanted to attend the expert meeting.</p> <p>GECTP11.33a: Participation Session Slagmolen Environment: Participation process for 1 of 4 pilot projects Many learning lessons/reflections: 1) Important to involve important stakeholders in design of process. 2) Next time also mix experts and citizens?</p> <p>GECTP11.34a: The clean-up campaign in Stiemervalley was a successful action: 160 participants - 263 garbage bags - +1000kg 1) Alternative recruitment of participants (inspired by Stiemerlab) - not only general communication but direct contact to local organisations/merchants at different locations. 2) This is also a good way to map the social fabric in valley.</p> <p>GECTP11.37: Working with a certain community builder from Buurtwerk in Termien - close to Slagmolen led to a new perspective on the project area</p>	<p>more improvised and intuitive approach last time. This is a new practice for the team.</p> <p>GECTP11.32: The team realised that the groups of citizens and experts can be mixed. They never did this before so this is a novel practice.</p> <p>GECTP11.32: And this way novel relations were created. The team thought the “Friends of the Stiemer” would be anxious to actively participate in the meeting with experts but that wasn’t the case. Maybe belonging to 'Friends of the Stiemer' empowers them</p>	<p>a novel way to involve key agencies to respond to local problems. It is relatively unusual to have a project steering committee group for a co-production process that consists of a good mix of local actors (police, doctor's practice, ...). Based on the outcomes of the BMC workshop, there will also be a sub-group to look at specific issues. Police Scotland noticed the benefits of Bellahouston</p>	<p>relations.</p> <p>The team will support both units by</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - promoting NBS among district councils - supporting “Change your backyard” program by rolling out nature-based solutions, this is a new practice. <p>For the team, it also leads</p>	<p>partners.</p> <p>GECTP11.22+ 6.30: Governance: the new co-production process means changes for the internal organisation.</p> <p>GECTP11.32: Co-production: co-production between citizens (volunteers) and experts.</p> <p>GECTP11.33a: Co-production: novel type of participation process with citizens and experts.</p> <p>GECTP11.34: Co-</p>	<p>Sandy and team that have already been identified in Bellahouston and Drumchapel) to an evidence based approach that can become a take an off-the-shelf approach with indicators based on hard data.</p> <p>GLCTP15a: Co-production: the steering committee approach is an innovative way to facilitate co-production processes with unusual suspects like the doctor’s practice.</p>	<p>shared backyards.</p> <p>POCTP5.3: Co-production: Through the collaboration between other departments , the district council and the team, the departments and district council will become involved in novel co-production processes.</p> <p>POCTP5.3: Financing: opportunities for sharing funding</p>
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<p>boundaries: the boundary is not necessarily limited to the inhabitants of a neighbourhood but can be widened to the users of the project area (that live somewhere else).</p> <p>GLCTP15a: Realized that the steering committee approach is an innovative way to facilitate co-production processes that address local problems by replicating the Bellahouston gardens to other areas</p> <p>GLCTP2.6a: As a direct result of the changed working conditions during the pandemic, videos are now being developed for the capacity building of the Friends of community groups.</p> <p>POCTP5.3: New opportunity to collaborate with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - another department dealing with district councils for nature-based solutions - with colleagues from our department (but another unit) who implement a programme “Change your backyard” – 	<p>in this kind of meetings.</p> <p>GECTP11.33a: The team made new relations with the department of mobility and realized they need to involve important expert stakeholders earlier in the design of the process. They came up with novel practices to interact with the stakeholders more up-front in the process to better root it in their practices as well. Based on previous learning outcome they want to connect expert and citizens in participatory work for the Slagmolen site as</p>	<p>garden for the neighborhood , and since they received complaints via local politicians about mental, physical health – they formed a steering group to realise a project and connected to Sandy (CN team).</p> <p>practice: Working with the steering committee approach is an innovative way to facilitate co-production processes that address local problems by replicating</p>	<p>to a new discourse on how to collaborate and on the use of nature-based solutions.</p> <p>New rules regarding organisational structures and how to collaborate across silos within the department are created.</p>	<p>production: Mapping and contacting local stakeholders based on spatial location was a new method for the team. Mapping the social fabric of the area for a successful campaign. Building sense of belonging through the campaign.</p> <p>GECTP11.37: Co-production: the community builder (from Buurtwerk) is part of an external organisation that the city team co-</p>	<p>GLCTP2.6: Co-production: new ways of engaging with community groups.</p>	<p>within department and with district councils.</p> <p>POCTP5.3: Governance: New organisational structures in the departments and with the district councils.</p> <p>POCTP5.3: Entrepreneurship: in relation to architects - promotion of NBS like natural playgrounds among different partners with</p>
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	<p>revitalisation of shared backyards in the City centre.</p>	<p>well.</p> <p>GECTP11.34a It's a novel practice to identify stakeholders to invite by location. This resulted in novel relations for the team like restaurant owners.</p> <p>GECTP11.37: A novel discourse emerges when rethinking the project area, its boundaries and its users.</p> <p>GECTP11.37: Novel relations emerge from this new perspective, as it allows community builders from elsewhere to do relevant work with users of the project area.</p>	<p>the Bellahouston gardens to other areas</p> <p>GLCTP2.6 It is a new practice to use videos for capacity building of community groups.</p>		<p>produces the Stiemerprogram with</p>		<p>their own budget create potential for NBS architects to multiply their work.</p>
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12	<p>Establish new connections between strategic and operational levels</p> <p>GECTP6.28+14.3 Next step in implementation of (parts) of policy plan based on (lessons from) governance model for Stiemer programme</p> <p>GECTP6.37: Shift in the mindset of strategic people about the connection between NBS and their own work, leading to an increased ownership of the topic.</p> <p>GLCTP11: Realising the need to elevate collaboration to higher strategic levels. Discovery that the team is not being consulted on GCC property sales prior to sales taking place.</p> <p>POCTP3.3 bottom-up approach?: During a H&G workshop with core group of local URBACT members green agents cross-departments found each other and became enthusiastic about future collaborations. Expected change: enhancing and</p>	<p>GECTP6.28+14.3: The policy plan of Genk is built up from 13 policy objectives – each objective is translated into an action plan and then into actions. Their department is responsible for 3 actions and Peter and Katrien are responsible for climate adaptation action plan. Other 2 are mobility and housing. This raises the question: How to organise a governance model to incorporate CN project for this. which is also the opportunity: Embed things they learned from</p>	<p>GLCTP11: Property Sales is being re-integrated into GCC, relationship is complex, and there is a need for better communication and collaboration. To facilitate this, conversations need to be elevated to a higher strategic level. This relates to creating new relations (less formal, better working relationships) between the departments</p>	<p>POCTP2.4: It is a new practice for the Poznan team to do lobbying themselves (instead of their deputy director).</p> <p>POCTP2.4: The Poznan team renewed its relation with a councillor, now talking to him in his political role about budget for the natural playgrounds in the kindergartens. It resulted in</p>	<p>GECTP6.28+1 4.3: Indicators: implementing the policy plan will also mean monitoring its progress.</p> <p>GECTP6.28+1 4.3: Financing: they will also have to face the question of how to finance their policy plan – partly budget from city, will also have to look for external funds.</p> <p>GECTP6.28+1 4.3: Governance: it is a higher level</p>	<p>GLCTP11: Governance: new ways of governing how we manage our assets across departments, e.g. instead of just selling surplus open space</p>	<p>POCTP2.4: Governance: Lobbying as a new governance practice for the Poznan team, liaising with politicians.</p> <p>POCTP2.4: Financing: The goal of the lobbying is to get money for the next phase of the multi annual program of investments in kindergartens, managed by the department</p>

	<p>enriching the Connecting Nature impact on the activities of project team and Poznań City Hall, increasing awareness concerning NBS in Poznań City Hall and Poznań. (they use the strategy of green agents to tackle this challenge.)</p> <p>POCTP2.4: The Poznan team started lobbying themselves, with the support of the deputy director, rather than waiting for the deputy director to do the lobbying. And almost secured budget from educational department.</p>	<p>CN project into this higher level governance structure. This is a novel collaboration with other colleagues and thus contributes to new relations and possibilities to work integrated together (new relations).</p> <p>GECTP6.28+14.3: Practice: Peter and Katrien are now participating in this meeting.</p> <p>GECTP6.37: Relations: three different types of relations changed: 1) close collaboration of Francine (director Strategic City Development); 2) increased ownership of director</p>	<p>at strategic levels and new practices for collaboration</p>	<p>2 schools receiving additional funding.</p>	<p>governance structure in which they are now involved with the Stiemer Programme.</p> <p>GECTP6.37 Tech solutions: Proposal Gardens of Waterschei submitted for Stadsvernieu wing call flemish government is a step forward in implementing the gardens.</p> <p>GECTP6.37 Governance: novel relations internally and increased ownership on the strategic level leads to</p>		<p>of education.</p>
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		<p>Veronique; 3) Long-term partnership Tractebel paying off;</p> <p>GECTP6.37 Discourse: At the strategic (management) level, they are understanding better how to master the topics from a NBS perspective and they are seeing the benefits of NBS for their own work. Submitting the proposal of the Gardens of Waterschei and the increased relevance of the Stiernerdeals created new momentum to pick-up and include this novel discourse into various strategic plans and</p>			<p>changes in governance relations.</p>		
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		activities.					
13	<p>Opportunities for upscaling based on implementation of exemplar by other actors</p> <p>GECTP11.27: The Stiemerdeals are starting to work as an open invitation to new actors to get involved.</p> <p>GECTP11.26: A Stiemerdealmaker arranges a new deal. This is the first time a “second degree deal” takes place.</p> <p>GECTP11.35: Realisation that purchasing strategy is not straightforward to take over by volunteers. Volunteers from an NGO backed out when asked to be involved in communicating and working with their network on the purchasing strategy of the city.</p>	<p>GECTP11.27: The Stiemerdeals are successful because they 1) are linked to a physical location (novel practice), 2) have a compelling story/narrative (novel discourse), 3) are easily accessible thanks to a clear contact point (novel rule/structure) and 4) allow actors to join a network (create novel relations).</p> <p>GECTP11.26: The 2nd degree deal shows that the city team’s investment in novel relations is</p>	<p>GLCTP8: A novel collaboration (relation) of the team with Urban Good expands the OSS to more layers, e.g. showing uses of open space. In addition, Urban Good makes offline paper maps, making them accessible to different audiences.</p>	<p>POCTP5.3: New collaborations with another department and unit leads to new relations.</p> <p>The team will support both units by</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - promoting NBS among district councils - supporting 	<p>GECTP 11.27: Co-production: The Stiemerdeals are a method for co-production.</p> <p>GECTP 11.27: Financing, business and governance models: The Stiemerdeals involve novel models of financing, business and governance.</p> <p>GECTP 11.27: Entrepreneurship: The Stiemerdeals are stimulating</p>	<p>GLCTP8: Entrepreneurship: mapping tool comes from SME</p> <p>GLCTP8: Financing & business models: opening up new funding opportunities</p>	<p>POCTP5.3: Technical solutions: Implementing nature-based solutions in shared backyards.</p> <p>POCTP5.3: Co-production: Through the collaboration between other departments, the district council and the team, the departments</p>

<p>GLCTP8: National Park City campaign being launched in Glasgow is opportunity for CN and OSS.</p> <p>POCTP5.3: New opportunity to collaborate with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - another department dealing with district councils for nature-based solutions - with colleagues from our department (but another unit) who implement a programme “Change your backyard” – revitalisation of shared backyards in the City centre. <p>POCTP1.1: The co-development of three budget scenarios seemed a successful strategy for delegating the NBS planning and delivery to a local kindergarten.</p> <p>POLQ1.3: How to design a good project and ensure that NBS are involved, understood and promoted?</p> <p>POCTP 2.3: Scaling-up from spatial design focus in kindergartens to more</p>	<p>working. The idea of unlocking ‘dormant’ capacity is a novel practice for the Stiemerdeals. This leads to a novel discourse on how the Stiemerdeals work and are continued, growing.</p> <p>GECTP 11.35: The team tested a novel relation, forming a partnership between volunteers and the city department to implement a purchasing strategy. They discovered that colleagues from the department are open for it. For the volunteers on the other hand they did not want to take this role.</p>		<p>g “Change your backyard” program by rolling out nature-based solutions, this is a new practice.</p> <p>For the team, it also leads to a new discourse on how to collaborate and on the use of nature-based solutions.</p> <p>New rules regarding organisational structures and how to collaborate</p>	<p>entrepreneurship and bringing entrepreneurs together.</p> <p>GECTP 11.27: Governance: The Stiemerdeals require a novel way of governing by the city team, e.g. with regards to the contact point and facilitating the network.</p> <p>GECTP 11.26: Co-production: The Stiemerdeals are a method for co-production.</p> <p>GECTP 11.26: Financing, business and</p>		<p>and district council will become involved in novel co-production processes.</p> <p>POCTP5.3: Financing: opportunities for sharing funding within department and with district councils.</p> <p>POCTP5.3: Governance: New organisational structures in the departments and with the district</p>
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	<p>complex process of combining educational and promotional/raising awareness climate change adaptation with the use of physical infrastructure and spatial designs.</p> <p>POLQ2.1: How to create the portfolio of potential external public resources for up-scaling?</p> <p>POLQ2.3: How to secure that city budget resources are still available for implementation of NBS interventions?</p>	<p>The team thinks that might have to do with it being an unclear role in which they didn't have any mandate and possibly a conflict of interest.</p> <p>GECTP 11.35: It is a novel practice to collaborate with NGOs in this phase of the process.</p>		<p>across silos within the department are created.</p> <p>POCTP1.1 Practice: The Poznan team made three budget scenarios for a green classroom at a kindergarten, in collaboration with the architect, the kindergarten, the district council, the local initiative centre and a local activist. Based on the scenarios, the kindergarten was able to</p>	<p>governance models: The Stiemerdeals involve novel models of financing, business and governance.</p> <p>GECTP 11.26: Entrepreneurship: The Stiemerdeals are connecting entrepreneurs.</p> <p>GECTP 11.26: Governance: The Stiemerdeals require a novel way of governing by the city team, e.g. with regards to building up relations with new actors.</p>		<p>councils.</p> <p>POCTP5.3: Entrepreneurship: in relation to architects - promotion of NBS like natural playgrounds among different partners with their own budget create potential for NBS architects to multiply their work.</p> <p>POCTP1.1 Co-production: with the</p>
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				<p>continue the process themselves, with the Poznan team in a support role in case of questions.</p> <p>The team used the same elements as in Wilda district and translated it to the new context. They also added the expertise of an architect who knows about interior space and that has experience with application</p>	<p>GECTP 11.35: Co-production: the city department wants to co-produce the purchasing strategy with volunteers from NGOs.</p> <p>GECTP 11.35: Governance: they also collaborated with the purchasing department on this experiment.</p>		<p>architect, the kindergarten, the district council, the local initiative centre and a local activist</p> <p>POCTP1.1: Technical solutions: A green classroom as a novel way of developing the technical solution of an nbs</p> <p>POCTP1.1: Financing: the classroom needs extensive investments and that was</p>
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			<p>procedures.</p> <p>POCTP 2.3: Relation: Based on needs, resources and location of the school, CN team offered solutions. The educational offer and infrastructure design is co-designed with the schools.</p> <p>POCTP 2.3: Practice: The schools become ambassadors for topics such as biodiversity, air quality and water.</p>			<p>why the scenario's (s-xxl) where created. From small to large investments. This turned out useful for the civic budget because they could use the budget estimates S. For the bigger versions other sources can be found/applied...</p> <p>POCTP 2.3: Co-production: co-design</p>
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							<p>with schools</p> <p>Technical solutions: the collaboration with schools also touches upon the technical design of the nbs</p> <p>Financing: as a unit they never used the Norwegian fund as a financing source</p>
14	<p>Barrier to attract locally embedded consultants/partners/entrepreneurs who have knowledge about co-producing nature-based solutions</p> <p>GECTP11.25: Realisation that a place can be an accelerator for</p>	<p>GECTP11.23: Despite having found a very good candidate, the city team decided not to hire this party because: 1) too expensive for</p>		<p>POCTP2+5: In collaborations , the city team, bringing in their budget and</p>	<p>GECTP11.23: Co-production: Being locally embedded is important in the co-production</p>		<p>POCTP2+5:C o-production: The city team will collaborate</p>

	<p>participation and social innovation.</p> <p>GECTP11.23: Realisation that an important criterion for hiring an external consultant is their local embeddedness.</p> <p>POCTP2+5: The city team realized that their work on the project needs to shift more towards promoting nature-based solutions among other partners (like departments/district councils/by working on proposal Norwegian fund) that could co-finance the solution.</p>	<p>long-term cooperation, 2) not part of local network. Based upon this, they look for local based partner for long term sustainable partnership. In retrospect, we believe this kind of relationship & trust is more important than the consultancy service itself. Potential parties identified: RLKM/IOED based on their 'heritage area': they have a long-term sustainable partnership with the city and other involved actors already. This insight leads to a novel practice of searching for partnerships and</p>		<p>knowledge, wants to team up with partners that can invest.</p> <p>This approach leads to new relations, by opening up from a focus on collaborations with other departments to city districts and inhabitants (for now) to also include enterprises.</p>	<p>process.</p> <p>GECTP11.23: Governance: Local embeddedness allows for long term relationships.</p> <p>GECTP11.25: Co-production: The role of place is important in the co-production process.</p> <p>GECTP11.25: Governance: How to use a place as starting point, where applicable, is a new governance method for the city team.</p>		<p>with external partners such as district councils, citizens, enterprises.</p> <p>POCTP2+5: Governance: The city team will further collaborate with other city hall departments .</p> <p>POCTP2+5: Financing: The collaborations are co-financed with the external partners.</p>
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		<p>hiring locally.</p> <p>GECTP11.25: A location to which people feel connected/committed seems to be a source of inspiration/enthusiasm for many that stimulates the dynamic and herewith to create novel relations. It leads to a novel practice when acceleration through place is considered in the city team's way of working.</p>					
15	<p>Shifting from Planning to Delivery requires change of governance styles</p> <p>GECTP3.26: Realisation that we need to transition our way of governing the implementation phase of the project.</p>	<p>GECTP3.26: This new phase requires sets of new relationships and practices geared towards delivery of the</p>	<p>GLCTP2.6: Practices: novel to use story mapping to showcase funding opportunities,</p>	<p>POCTP 3.2: It is a novel practice to not only organise a brainstorm to</p>	<p>GECTP3.26: Governance: related to new practices, relations and discourse</p>	<p>GLCTP2.6: Financing: for Glasgow it is novel to use story mapping to showcase</p>	<p>POCTP 3.2: Co-production: especially because NGOs</p>

	<p>GLCTP2.6: The team discovered story mapping as an opportunity to showcase funding opportunities in a dynamic way to policy makers.</p> <p>GLLQ2.6: How can the Connecting Nature team and partners help to build this capacity so that we achieve successful delivery of NBS whilst reducing the burden on GCC teams?</p> <p>POCTP 3.2: Realising the team are not only the organisers of sessions like the Urbact Local Group but they can also exchange and propose their own ideas and put them on the agenda.</p>	<p>Stiemervalley's projects.</p> <p>GECTP3.26: It also changes the discourse, how their colleagues first saw the team as the ones that are visioning and planning to a shift towards implementing and delivering.</p>	<p>to use it to share learning and as an engagement tool. Making it visual helps in the discussions with other policy makers. Learning is about discovering new ways to visualizing the actual light bulb moment is the new relationships that this helped to built and the novel discourse this helped to strengthen because it changed the way people think about it.</p>	<p>harvest ideas but to contribute to the brainstorm themselves.</p> <p>POCTP 3.2: A novel relation is formed when the team takes up the role of not only facilitators but also of experts. It leads to a different perception of the team by others.</p>	<p>within the city hall</p>	<p>funding opportunities, to use it to share learning and as an engagement tool.</p> <p>GLCTP2.6: Governance: related to new practices, relations and discourse within the city hall.</p>	<p>involved and see them in this new role.</p> <p>POCTP 3.2: Governance: Changed role within the city, from facilitators to experts on their projects and nature-based solutions.</p>
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16	<p>Successful external funding applications/granted based on CN Framework, perceived as recognition for innovative work</p> <p>GECTP3.44: The team received 2.01 m€ investment funding for Gardens of Waterschei, which is not only funding but mainly (and finally) recognition for Stiemer Programme. They received very nice feedback: "Tuinen van Waterschei is an innovative leverage project. It has broad support and is sufficiently mature for realisation. Due to the radical choice for nature-based solutions and the interlinking of ecological, economic and social objectives, this project contributes greatly to the renewal of the city renewal innovation programme"</p> <p>POCTP2: When working on tenders/applications that ask for complex solutions, the team bumped into the barrier: they are not able to fit their proposal into the system of the tender/application. The tender/application asks for</p>	<p>GECTP3.44: The recognition for the team and the Stiemer programme equals a recognition for implementing and scaling nature-based solutions. This implies changes in relations in how they collaborate with their colleagues. GECTP3.44: Also new practices because this way of working is valued by more people and will be 'normalised'. GECTP3.44: It also contributes to a novel discourse because within the cities NBS are now also recognised as an</p>	<p>GLLEW:#: We mainly use the framework for approving incoming funding applications ourselves. We are using it for our strategic program. It helps us to discuss what is wrong and right for each of the elements. It is helpful to start the conversation</p> <p>On a strategic level: it has been</p>	<p>POCTP2: Rules: e.g. limited words and categories are especially challenging when working with nbs in tenders and project applications.</p> <p>POCTP2: Practice: The solution was to create appendixes in which they could write more, but not sure if this was successful. Next time they would do it differently.</p>	<p>GECTP3.44: Technical solutions: recognition for nature-based solution approaches</p> <p>GECTP3.44 : Co-production: the proposal includes citizens-oriented public private partnership</p> <p>GECTP3.44 : Financing: the proposal is</p>	<p>GLLEW:#: all elements are used to assess projects under the OSS.</p>	<p>POCTP2: Technical solutions: It is hard to explain a complex solution like a technical solution for nbs in current tender/applications due to the format of the tender/application.</p> <p>POCTP2: Governance: it is complex to apply for tenders e.g. with cross-departmental</p>

	<p>complexity but doesn't have a template for it.</p>	<p>important strategy to get these types of funding.</p>	<p>fundamental : it is a check for myself. Does this project have everything it takes: when other project apply to work with us.</p>	<p>The consultant they collaborated with (which was last minute now) realized they forced more on the appendixes and not on the short forms. Next time they will also ask different things.</p>	<p>based on a strategy of combining citizens-oriented public private partnership.</p> <p>GECTP3.44 : Entrepreneurship: the proposal includes the involvement of entrepreneurs of the Stalenstraat</p> <p>GECTP3.44: Governance: it is also a recognition for working horizontally</p>		<p>collaboration</p>
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17	<p>Replicating innovative structures developed in CN results in new practices of other departments.</p> <p>GECTP14.7: First time the team’s governance model has been replicated for other big programme, the Genk Energy Coalition.</p> <p>GLCTP2.2 The team is reviewing the current practice of how outdoor learning spaces are selected because they want to implement a new structure for this process with the OSS delivery plan. To make this work they need to learn how to change the practice of the actors who are doing it in a different way now</p> <p>GLLQ3.1: How can the Connecting Nature team convince education colleagues to change their practice and provide us with the information we need to plan for outdoor learning opportunities in our open spaces into the future?</p> <p>GLCTP2.3 The team is realising that they need to work with Parks & Education to help build a profile of</p>	<p>GECTP14.7: Replication of governance model gave the team more insights in generic elements of their governance model. The fact that it could be replicated to other sectors (energy instead of water) means that the model caused changes in rules, relations, practices and discourse.</p>	<p>GLCTP2.2: The practice to find a space is currently very ad hoc, with OSS delivery plan, a novel structure (rule) is created: the decision process will be easier and more strategic because it is connected to the OSS. It is also a novel practice to focus on long-term use of the sites for nurseries for the city.</p> <p>GLCTP2.3: First the team wants to</p>		<p>GECTP14.7: Governance: replication of governance model</p>	<p>GLCTP2.2: The nurseries identify the spaces, so they are co-producing this with the city.</p> <p>The OSS is a novel governance structure to replace the current way the outdoor learning spaces are selected.</p> <p>GLCTP2.3: Governance: currently the working group consists of internal actors</p> <p>Indicators: characteristics can be used to select</p>	

	<p>the characteristics to plan for outdoor learning spaces. For this a working group structure was set up.</p>		<p>change the way of thinking (discourse) from ad-hoc selecting spaces for outdoor learning to strategic approach using OSS with characteristics. Working with characteristics makes it easier to select sites that are suitable for outdoor learning. This needs to become the new practice for GCC Education that they want to build with a working</p>			<p>indicators for tracking progress.</p>	
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			<p>group who will decide on the characteristics that are needed and review them over time. This is a new relation between the two departments.</p> <p>Working group model might help on other aspects of OSS delivery plan as well. (scaling up to other themes e.g. biodiversity)</p>				
18	<p>Simple communication about NBS is not easy but is very effective to get strategic actors involved</p> <p>GECTP11.34b: The clean-up campaign</p>	<p>GECTP11.34 b Working with a tailored communication strategy for this</p>	<p>GLLEW#: Governance & co-production: The</p>	<p>POCTP5.4: Practice: Through promotional</p>	<p>GECTP11.34b: Governance: The communication strategy for</p>	<p>GLLEW#: The city noted that they required a communicatio</p>	<p>POCTP5.4: Co-production:</p>

	<p>in Stiemervalley was a successful action: 160 participants - 263 garbage bags - +1000kg</p> <p>3) Important campaign from perspective of high-level communication strategy (affection-activation)</p> <p>GLLEW#: we don't have a communication strategy. We then realized that we need this again and created one. It is now being seen as an exemplar to be used in other projects as well.</p> <p>POCTP5.4 Sometimes you need to compromise between details about content NBS and the short catchy story to attract people so they will be interested in hearing more about the details.</p>	<p>project allows the team to connect their activities to the communication in a very initiative way. (cognitive phase, affective phase, conversion phase). This is a novel rule because it never was organised so strategically and integrated before and other projects in the city don't work like this yet .</p>	<p>communication strategy was a novel practice for the team and resulted in more projects using it which created novel relations and it has been translated into a novel rule.</p>	<p>videos, the team can attract more people into the details of NBS. So thinking about next steps is needed to ensure when you get questions about details, you have materials to share like the catalogue, website materials, etc.</p>	<p>the Stiemervalley improved the project's governance.</p>	<p>n strategy for the Connecting Nature work. Then realised that it could cover not only the Open Space strategy but also that it would be better to cover the whole Planning Service. This created a Planning Service Communication Strategy that is now seen as an exemplar for other parts of the directorate that they sit with in</p>	<p>the promotion is a way to attract actors from outside the organisation</p>
19	<p>CN Framework can be used to report on progress of nature-based solution projects (e.g. gap-analysis).</p> <p>GLCTP15: Discovering the use of the CN framework as an effective tool</p>		<p>GLCTP15: The CN framework is seen by the team as a living</p>			<p>GLCTP15: All the framework categories apply.</p>	

	<p>and living document e.g. to carry out gap analysis.</p> <p>GLLQ15: How can we effectively use the CN framework to add value to local Open Space projects?</p>		<p>document: it allows for a sense check to evaluate the work. It can, for example, be used as a tool for a gap analysis to discover what aspects they are missing. The CN project is about implementing and combining the different types of innovations to change the rules, relations, practices and discourses since working with NBS requires this.</p>				
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Appendix E: Learning objectives FFCs and FRCs

Learning objectives	Cities with the questions	Response (by which cities)
<i>Connecting Nature Framework</i>		
1. How to use the Connecting Nature Framework as a communication tool?	A Coruña, Nicosia, Pavlos Melas	Genk, Ioannina
2. How to work with the Connecting Nature Framework to scale-out from project level to city strategy level?	A Coruña, Burgas, Málaga, Nicosia, Pavlos Melas, Sarajevo	
3. How to create space/time to use the Connecting Nature Framework?	A Coruña, Málaga, Nicosia, Sarajevo	
4. How to balance the different elements of the Connecting Nature Framework	Poznań, Nicosia	
<i>Technical solutions</i>		
1. How to identify spaces for nature-based solutions (cities need more space)?	A Coruña, Burgas, Ioannina, Málaga, Nicosia	Glasgow
2. How to deal with trade-offs (e.g. between biodiversity versus recreation)?	Burgas, Ioannina, Pavlos Melas	Genk
3. How to design nature-based solutions to enhance biodiversity?	Sarajevo, Burgas	Glasgow
4. How to boost awareness of environmental/ health benefits of the nature-based solution?	A Coruña, Málaga, Nicosia, Pavlos Melas, Sarajevo	
5. How to efficiently update existing infrastructure?	Burgas, Ioannina, Nicosia	
6. How to cooperate with external bodies/ expertise to design and/or implement the nature-based solution?	A Coruña, Burgas, Ioannina, Nicosia, Pavlos Melas, Sarajevo	
7. How to satisfy the criteria / definition for nature-based solution?	Sarajevo	
8. How to combat vandalism/ protect NBS ?	Pavlos Melas	Genk
<i>Governance</i>		
1. How to engage with other departments ? / break silos	A Coruña, Burgas, Ioannina, Málaga, Pavlos Melas, Glasgow	A Coruña, Genk
2. How to continue cross-departmental collaboration in COVID times ?	Ioannina, Málaga, Nicosia	
3. How to wage political support ?	Sarajevo	Glasgow
4. How to shift the existing governance model	A Coruña, Ioannina	A Coruña
5. How to get experience in organising a strategic adaptive governance process to oversee complex large scale NBS?	A Coruña, Málaga, Nicosia, Pavlos Melas	A Coruña
6. How to design and implement bottom-up governance models?	A Coruña, Ioannina, Nicosia	

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7. How to organise continued support for the NBS ?	A Coruña, Burgas, Málaga, Nicosia, Pavlos Melas	
8. How to align the goals of the NBS with the wider goals of the city in order to build the case for delivering multiple benefits ?	Burgas, Málaga, Nicosia, Pavlos Melas	
<i>Financing and business models</i>		
1. How to increase the prioritisation of the NBS on funding agendas ?	A Coruña, Burgas, Nicosia, Pavlos Melas	Ioannina Glasgow
2. How to strategically link the NBS to other departments in order to raise more funding ?	A Coruña, Ioannina, Nicosia, Pavlos Melas, Sarajevo	
3. How to deal with CSR ? What is the protocol ?	Poznań	Nicosia
4. How to fund / create revenue for the stewardship phase of the project ?	A Coruña, Burgas, Ioannina, Málaga, Nicosia, Pavlos Melas, Sarajevo	Genk
5. How to find collaborating parties that are funded elsewhere ?	Málaga, Pavlos Melas, Sarajevo	
6. How to engage the private sector /raise awareness and interest in projects among the private sector to attract funding ?	A Coruña, Burgas, Málaga, Nicosia, Pavlos Melas, Sarajevo	
<i>Nature-based entrepreneurship</i>		
1. How to find potential entrepreneurs ?	Nicosia, Pavlos Melas	Nicosia
2. How to find maintenance entrepreneurs for the maintenance of the gardens ?	A Coruña, Málaga, Nicosia, Pavlos Melas, Sarajevo	
3. How to establish an NBE pilot /incubator programme ?	Glasgow	Málaga
4. How to deal with the logistics of an incubator programme ? e.g. economic evaluation, physical space.	Málaga	Glasgow
5. How to use accelerator/ incubator to promote NBS in locality ?	A Coruña, Málaga, Nicosia	
6. How to manage expectations of participants / outcomes in NBE pilot programmes - incubator and/ or accelerator ?	Málaga	Glasgow
7. How to successfully market the pilot / incubator programme to attract the right participants ?	Nicosia, Glasgow	Málaga
8. How to create economic opportunities, specifically for the maintenance phase of the NBS ?	Burgas, Málaga, Nicosia, Pavlos Melas, Sarajevo	
<i>Co-production</i>		
1. How to encourage/ motivate stakeholders to join the initiative, engaging "outsiders" or when people are not committed ?	Burgas, Málaga, Nicosia, Pavlos Melas, Sarajevo	Nicosia Glasgow
2. How to encourage and support other organisations to organise co-	A Coruña, Málaga, Sarajevo	

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production activities?		
3. How to engage organisations through co-production activities?	A Coruña, Burgas, Ioannina, Pavlos Melas, Sarajevo	Glasgow, Genk
4. How to carry out effective co-production with stakeholders in COVID times?	A Coruña, Burgas, Málaga, Nicosia, Pavlos Melas, Sarajevo	Glasgow
5. How to manage conflict among NBS users ?	A Coruña, Pavlos Melas	Glasgow
6. How to manage the expectations of collaborators in Co-production processes ?	Burgas, Nicosia	
7. How to prevent gentrification through co-production?	Málaga	
8. How to/ when to use co-production tools ?	A Coruña, Burgas, Málaga, Nicosia, Sarajevo	
9. How to engage large stakeholder groups through co-production (instead of consultation)	Málaga, Nicosia, Pavlos Melas, Sarajevo	
10. How to carry out public consultation regarding draft design of NBS	Sarajevo	Glasgow
11. How to engage private sector stakeholders?	A Coruña, Burgas, Málaga, Nicosia, Pavlos Melas, Sarajevo	Poznań
12. How to engage organisations through co-production activities?	A Coruña, Ioannina,	
13. How to facilitate knowledge exchange between different groups?	Pavlos Melas, Sarajevo	
14. How to decide to engage specific stakeholder groups at what stage of the project?	Burgas, Nicosia, Pavlos Melas, Sarajevo	
15. Who are the required partners and how can we bring them together ?	Málaga, Nicosia, Pavlos Melas, Sarajevo	
16. How to bring plot owners/ managers together, communicate interest in the plot and possibly arrive at a shared vision ?	A Coruña, Málaga	
17. How to support cultural and sport activities to increase social cohesion?	Ioannina, Pavlos Melas	
18. How to decide on next steps after a co-production activity ?	Burgas, Ioannina, Málaga, Nicosia, Pavlos Melas, Sarajevo	
19. How to encourage a changed approach to the way land is managed ?	Málaga	Glasgow
<i>Reflexive monitoring</i>		
1. How to integrate Reflexive monitoring into daily practice ?	Burgas, Ioannina, Málaga, Nicosia, Sarajevo	Glasgow
2. How can we move from using Reflexive monitoring from officer to senior level ?	A Coruña, Sarajevo	
3. How to elaborate upon items on the Dynamic Learning Agenda ?	Ioannina	

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4. How to efficiently/ effectively use Reflexive monitoring ? i.e. internal use versus attempting to use RM with external stakeholders	Málaga	
<i>Impact assessment</i>		
1. How to find impact assessment expertise within the city ?	A Coruña, Málaga, Pavlos Melas	Glasgow
2. How to evaluate the (indirect) benefits ?	Nicosia, Pavlos Melas, Sarajevo	
3. How to narrow down/ select appropriate indicators ?	Pavlos Melas	Genk
4. How to find expertise outside the city ? e.g. universities	Ioannina, Málaga, Nicosia, Pavlos Melas, Sarajevo, Poznań	Nicosia
5. How to budget monitoring?	A Coruña, Málaga, Nicosia, Pavlos Melas	
6. How to do surveys during COVID ?	A Coruña, Sarajevo	

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Task 2.3 summary for Deliverable 7

Task description in proposal

Task 2.3: Development of successful organisational strategies: for implementing change and actions to deal with hindrances in front-runner cities (both governmental and business) and develop adapted practices for fast-follower and multiplier cities.

Start: M3 End: M24. Lead Partner: UVT. Partners involved: AMU, DRIFT, UDC, UEL, ICLEI, Poznań, Glasgow, and all fast-follower cities.

An online survey will be conducted by UVT among quintuple helix actors who were involved in the development process, and also online consultations for a more qualitative approach. In addition, the same methodology will be used in order to identify the current resources and potential hindrances in cities that will initiate change, also with the purpose to identify the target cities' needs and characteristics in order to maximize stakeholders' engagement and ensure the deployment of nature-based solutions (UVT, AMU, DRIFT, UDC, UEL, ICLEI). Once the data in this respect are gathered, a training workshop will be organised by UVT in collaboration with all cities, in order to calibrate a change and development plan of intervention. This task will be based on results obtained from the assessment exercise carried out in Task 1.5 and will be informed by Task 2.1 and 2.2. The results of this task will then be fed into the co-production guidebook in Deliverable 4 and 7.

Update task 2.3

Task 2.3: Development of successful organizational strategies: for implementing change and actions to deal with hindrances in front-runner cities (both governmental and business) and develop adapted practices for fast-follower and multiplier cities

Start: M3 End: M24. Lead Partner: UVT. Partners involved: AMU, DRIFT, UDC, UEL, ICLEI, Poznań, Glasgow, and all fast-follower cities.

The in the first reporting period completed work on organizational barriers and opportunities was fed into the co-production guidebook and the identification of governance needs for co-production (Task 2.2, Deliverable 4). In addition, a literature review on organizational strategies supported the conceptualization of the co-production principles, in particular in terms of how to facilitate the design and delivery of these principles. Currently, and in collaboration with Task 3.4, a coaching programme is developed building on the acquired understanding of the frontrunner cities' organisational barriers, needs and opportunities, as well as organisational innovations the cities are already working on. The coaching programme also addressed explicitly the governance needs identified in Task 2.1 and the learning objectives identified during the Knowledge Transfer workshop in Málaga (October 2019). The programme will also include insights derived from the reflexive Monitoring calls about on going organisational barriers and innovations in the cities. The coaching programme will result in strategies to develop organisational innovations to deliver scaled-up nature-based solutions.

The programme will be led by DRIFT, UEL and TDC and supported by different partners (e.g. UVT, ICLEI, Geenspace Schotland) with the front-runner cities in an iterative process adapted to the city's needs (as part of this task and task 3.4). The results will also feed into the participatory planning and governance indicators for work package 1.

Coaching programme for CN Cities by UVT, supported by UEL and DRIFT

Introduction: Organisational coaching program development

The organizational coaching program was developed under the task 2.3, concerned with "Development of successful organizational strategies: for implementing change and actions to deal with hindrances in front-runner cities (both governmental and business) and develop adapted practices for fast-follower and multiplier cities.", is based on the work undertaken in WP1 (the assessment of organizational processes in cities) and developed in

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collaboration with WP3, Task 3.4. Moreover, the coaching program addressed explicitly the governance needs (identified in Task 2.1), as well as the learning objectives identified during the Knowledge Transfer workshop in Málaga, 2019, including insights derived from the Reflexive Monitoring calls about on-going organisational barriers and innovations in the cities.

The process of assessing organizational characteristics in cities (WP1) was comprised of several phases of information gathering, resulting in recommendations for each city assessed, in order to successfully implement change - intrinsic with new and innovative organizational processes due to NBS projects. Workshops were held in each FRC (between February and April 2018) for initial data gathering to define the hindrances and resources available in each city. With these sessions it started the process of collecting organizational innovations that the FRCs are already working on as inspiration for the other Connecting Nature Cities as well as the barriers that need to be overcome in order to have a successful innovative city making process for implementing NBS. The common identified drivers (resources) are related to really good intradepartmental social support; access to accurate information; and positive attitudes towards working together, whereas the barriers are related to working horizontally; departmentalization; no informal means of communication or space for informal gatherings and discussions; top-down initiatives (NBS); (information) overload of some City Hall employees, a role model/champion is missing, and a stiff organizational structure.

During the AGM meeting in 2018, short 15 minutes' meetings were held in order to discuss with representatives of each FRC regarding the initial results of the data gathering in the respective city and to formulate a strategy for how to best assist them in dealing with hindrances and enhance the resources already available. Literature reviews were also undertaken in order to be able to offer research based suggestions for the specificities of each city. Moreover, two online meetings were held in the summer of 2018, with two of the three FRCs (Genk and Poznan).

Insights were formulated for each FRC, and based on the barriers and resources identified, a battery of organizational-relevant indicators suitable for all the FRC's was created. Specifically, the challenges identified for each city were summarized into specific insights with the purpose to obtain potential areas of organizational development (objectives), and the resources were similarly treated in order to reflect "strength" areas. As observed from the insights identified for each city, common patterns emerged. The common dimensions and subsequent indicators identified were: leader support, cooperation and internal communication.

In 2019, a series of coaching programs and webinars were proposed with the main purpose of providing knowledge and encouraging strategies to develop organizational innovations to deliver scaled-up nature-based solutions. Specifically, WUT designed a coaching program on organizational strategies for a) developing collaborative work environments for new partnerships and synergies; b) developing leadership skills; and c) mobilising societal support and managing stakeholder dynamics. Thus, three main areas were of importance: building relevant resources at work, dealing efficiently with work stressors, and building a collaborative work environment. The program was thought as online-based webinar series, with three modules. The first module "Mapping resources, stressors and internal communication and collaboration challenges" would have resulted in a summary of the preparatory work within the frontrunner cities to ensure favourable organizational conditions and strategies for implementing NBS within the city-team. This module would have been used as input for second module that starts with the first online lecture of the training. The second module was thought to present the principles to "Overcome organisational barriers by creating a collaborative work environment for NBS", whereas the third one was focused on strategic leadership, titled "Mobilise and create leadership for NBS implementation".

With the start of the COVID-19 pandemic, the coaching program underwent several changes in order to keep up with the new challenges imposed and adapted to the needs of the cities. The final form for these webinars was reached in early 2021, with a three-session course based on two major themes: 1) developing new organisational skills and capacities such as interpersonal skills and team building for NBS delivery, and 2) breaking down silos and building collaboration across departments to deliver NBS. These themes were identified and agreed upon based on the work done under both WP2 and WP3 (DRIFT and UEL), as well as after consulting with the front-runner cities. This process ensured that the needs of the cities are well recognized and addressed.

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Organisational coaching program Webinar series

The webinars' topics were focused on three main themes:

Webinar 1: Stress management

Attendents: 12

Video: <https://youtu.be/fI0kVixJSfk>

The first webinar aimed at drawing attention on essential concerns of individuals considering their multiple roles (employees, parents etc.) and potential struggles encountered when aiming to be performant in several life domains, especially in the time of a pandemics. The main message was that before attempting to consider specific issues in professional contexts, we need to consider ourselves as whole persons, with a fundamental need to stay healthy mentally and physically before engaging in various professional challenges. The webinar was designed to provide participants with an understanding of some of the psychological underpinnings of their wellbeing and with a series of good practices to help them to prevent stress and deal with stress and stressors when necessary.

Specifically, the webinar started with a discussion on the challenges we face in a VUCA reality and the bigger picture of our times, and then continued with a psychophysiological explanation on how stress happens. To offer responses for three key questions: How can we restore balance? How can we do it easily and Can we do it constantly, we addressed the following topics:

- *Recovery strategies*

How to recover efficiently during the day: *microbreaks*

Key points on keeping your recovery on track

- *Work life-personal life*

How to redefine boundaries?

How to keep a better balance?

- *Good habits*

Strengthen personal resources

Specific strategies for dealing with stress

For each theme we provided a relevant theoretical frame, relevant research that supports its applicability and several evidence-based practices to support energy restoring processes, juggling multiple roles and responsibilities (currently most of them in the same space of one's home) and consolidate personal resources and healthy habits.

1. Webinar 2: Understanding how to foster interpersonal skills

Attendents: 12

Video: <https://youtu.be/M8pqUWpZHPI>

The second webinar focused on the understanding of intrapersonal processes, namely emotions, and interpersonal processes such as active listening and feedback. The content aimed at explaining what emotions are, their components and what emotions do we have. The practical focus detailed how can we manage our emotions and which strategies can help with coping with certain situations and which are rather relevant for mental health in the long run. We explained how emotions are responsible for our personal processes and our interactions. Further we focused on an essential interpersonal skill, namely active listening. We explained why we are sometimes bad listeners and how can we improve our active listening skills. The last part of the webinar was centered on feedback, with the aim of understanding how it can be most efficient for healthy interpersonal relationships and a better performance for ourselves and our colleagues.

2. Webinar 3: Collaboration and teambuilding

Attendents: 14

Video: <https://youtu.be/FaeYIXwxHQ4>

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The third webinar drew attention on healthy organizations. We discussed relevant examples of good practices and how individual and organizational wellbeing is fostered in various work contexts. Key issues on partnerships, collaboration and synergies were covered, focusing on how to develop collaboration capability and, more on the practical side, how to implement practices for a collaborative environment in the work setting. For a better understanding of the collaboration challenges, we tapped into the communication styles, focusing on how assertiveness can be developed and applied in various contexts.

Theoretical Background

The theoretical background of the topics discussed during the webinars were presented as to encourage the understanding of the psychological mechanisms that explain the individual reactions and strategies related to the various phenomena discussed. Specifically, as regards the first webinar — Stress management —, we described the following theories and the associated research:

The job demands-resources model; (JDR; Bakker & Demerouti, 2017); The effort-recovery model (ERM; Meijman & Mulder, 1998); Conservation of resources theory (COR; Hobfoll, 1989). Using the lens of the JDR model we explained the relevance of the balance between demands and resources from the individual's environment, and the role of personal resources in the process. The ERM model was used to explain how the psycho-physiological systems are taxed when dealing with challenges and how the recovery processes need to take place to recharge after invested effort. The COR explains how people seek to get, keep, and protect resources, how stress is related to lowering of resources and the importance of focusing on restoring consumed resources. When discussing emotions we focused on Feldman-Barrett's (2017) conceptual frame and Russel's (2006) framework of emotions. We also tapped into the role of mental filtering and how biases can affect our listening process (e.g., Kahneman, 2015). For the collaboration capability part, we focused on the Blomqvist and Levy (2006) framework focused on trust, commitment, and communication.

Reflections on outcomes of organizational program

The webinar was designed to help participants understand important mechanisms related to individual and organizational well-being and familiarize with specific practices relevant for self-management, self-regulation, efficient interpersonal communication, and teamwork. To facilitate gaining knowledge and exercise behaviors and approaches that could turn into healthy habits. To facilitate engagement, we used the Mentimeter platform where participants could answer in real time and see all the responses provided. This tool facilitates interaction in the online environment and authentic answers by its anonymous way and sharing ideas and having more insights on how other people are thinking. The interactive manner included direct communication with questions and reflections that invited participants to link the new information with current issues and concerns they have about themselves or their work environment. Also, the webinar's support included, after each chapter, key take-aways slides with essentials regarding each topic discussed.

Results

Delivering scaled-up nature-based solutions is possible and more likely to be implemented successfully when individuals, groups, organisations and communities are aligned towards the same goal and have built the capacity to do so. The coaching programme, and a potential continuance, helped individuals in their organizational roles reflect on their strengths, needs and key organizational objectives. Any innovative approach is based on values, knowledge, and willingness to contribute to one's community and beyond. We believe the webinars managed to support participants to understand how self-management tools can help with daily stressors and current issues in a more effective way and therefore gaining more space to engage in innovative approaches. Moreover, knowledge about facilitating good communication and collaboration at work, especially cross-departments, can stimulate progress towards the desired goals as regards nature-based solutions and moving beyond silo thinking. Importantly, learning about how good practices focused on interaction, communication and teamwork can facilitate an actual implementation into current organizational activities. This part where employees improve collaboration at different levels and this becomes a habitual way of approaching goals in organizations is an essential premise for working successfully together on more ambitious projects. Therefore, such coaching programmes need to be relatively consistent until the organizations get more familiar with new ways of working, as this taps into their organizational culture. With such a mind and working set, more complex approaches have better chances not just to be implemented once, but to be sustainable.

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The programme was part of the knowledge hub Co-production & Governance led by DRIFT, UEL and supported by UVT. The content created for the coaching programme was used as the basis for a toolkit with slides which can be used by cities who have not participated in the webinars. This toolkit has been included in the practical guide for using co-production for nature-based solutions (attachment of Deliverable 7).

Organisational Innovation Coaching Programme

May 2021

A practical perspective on the
Connecting Webinars 2021

focused on

Stress management

Interpersonal skills

Collaboration and team building

Coralia Sulea, PhD, associate professor
Patricia Albuлесcu, PhD student, research assistant
West University of Timisoara

Objectives

Stress management especially in COVID times

The participants were able to learn:

How to recover efficiently after work activities.
How to keep a better balance between work and life.
How to form good habits in managing stress and well-being.

Understanding how to foster interpersonal skills

The participants were able to learn:

How can we better manage emotions.
How to better actively listen.
How to give efficient feedback.

Collaboration and team building

The participants were able to learn:

Which are key aspects of collaboration.
What are effective and problematic communication styles.
What are some key issues of assertiveness.

Practical ideas on
managing self during
stressful times and building
healthy relationships and
teams

Nowadays we are engaged in a busy lifestyle, VUCA reality (volatility, uncertainty, complexity, ambiguity), increased competition. On top of this, there is also our fear of missing out all this information with the potential of being useful in our lives. Pandemics life add new stressors and challenges.

How can we manage stress and balance?

It is important to check how you feel.

Did you feel lately?

tired
unable to disconnect
having trouble with sleeping
irritated

If the answer is Yes, please take into consideration the following ideas for maintaining balance. They can also be practices for stress prevention, which is always better.

Restore your resources

Restoring or filling used resources in professional activities like physical energy or attention play a critical role in psychological and psychosomatic well-being and are also relevant for performance.

When stressed (but not only), focus on nature: walk in the park, play with animals, take care of your garden. This helps because we are physically and mentally adapted to natural environments.

Moreover, nature, through intrinsic qualities, draws our involuntary attention and allows for the recovery of the tired attentional system; it stimulates awe and joy at a basic level.

Restore your resources

Efficient microbreaks (5-10 minutes) during worktime

[boosting energy // preventing fatigue // stimulating performance](#)

Watch a video (explanatory, funny, with animals, a river, meaningful)

Meditate

[Listen to nature's sounds](#)

Do a bit of movement (walk in the room, stretch, mild physical exercises)

Read something for your own pleasure

Engage in meaningful contact (offer someone help at work, discuss common interests)

(Albulescu, Macsinga, Rusu, Sulea & Tulbure, 2022 submitted manuscript)

Restore your resources

Keep in mind:

Browsing your smartphone during a break is the same as not taking a break at all.
(Kahn & Kurtzberg, 2019).

Some websites might help: [Window swap](#)

Even a 30-second break can reduce stress: stare at a plant, look at an old photograph, talk to your dog, look outside at 20 meters length (panoramic view)

- Take breaks when you feel the need to, in the morning, preferably
- Do something that brings you joy
- Prioritize what is focused on nature and physical activity

Restore your resources

30 minutes for eating outside the working area

10 minutes of brisk walking

Mindful walking

Just breathe

Regular breaks are important, since the recovery effects from holidays seem to fade away in about 2-4 weeks 😞.

Boost your vacation recovery effects

- Engage in physical activities
- Avoid negative incidents
- Engage in pleasant vacation activities of your own choice
- Plan more vacations throughout a work year
- Prepare well before going on vacation to prevent hassles (!Reach a consensus with co-travelers about vacation activities)
- Prevent high work demands immediately afterwards
- Share vacation experiences

Have a better work-family-self relationship when you work from home

- fake commutes (in the morning, dress and take a walk in the park or go to the office and come back)
- rituals at the end of the day (dress in different clothes)
- organize your workspace (only do work, add plants, put reminders of your work and office)
- organize your schedule (clearly defined work hours)

[Focus yourself](#)

Organize your mind and work

Mind sweep

Schedule 20-30 minutes to put on the paper what concerns you. You can use post-its. Place them in the place where you collect all your ideas and notes.

- Microbreaks // Mindfulness // Short nap // Yoga
- Organize your workspace // Move or dance for a few minutes
- Defocus

Job crafting

= increase resources and challenges and lower stressors

- Learn new things
- Use fully your skills
- Ask colleagues for advice
- Volunteer for interesting projects
- Organize your activities (!**POMODORO**)

A task is divided in parts of 25 minutes. After each part there is a 5 minutes break.

After 4 parts x 25 minutes take a longer break (20-30 minutes)

What else might help?

FIND A MORNING AND EVENING RITUAL THAT BRINGS YOU JOY AND FACILITATES THE FLOW

ARRANGE FOR UNINTERRUPTED FOCUSED TIME

REDUCE DISTRACTIONS

FOCUS ON SMALL GOALS, SMALL WINS

Quick Ways to
Manage Your Stress:
*Celebrate
Yourself*

Be consistent with your good practices. Build a habit.

Make a list with 3 habits that you think might help. Fill out the table below:

	Habits	With which existent habit might it be associated?	What clues might help?	How easy it is to accomplish? 1 - very easy 2 - easy 3 - hard 4 - very hard	How attractive is it? 1- very attractive 2 - attractive 3 - somewhat attractive 4 - very attractive
1.					
2.					
3.					

Emotions

Understand your emotions and other emotions is crucial for connections and healthy relationship.

Each emotion plays has a function and helps us understand how the context has an impact on us, on our needs and values. Each emotion has a need, therefore addressing emotions in a right way is relevant for our intrapersonal and interpersonal balance.

How emotions help us?

Joy – helps us to:

- Use inductive reasoning more easily;
- Be creative;
- Think innovatively (*outside the box*);
- Relate more easily with one another.

Sadness – helps us to:

- Withdraw and reflect on our own mistakes;
- Draw the sympathy and help of others;
- Protect ourselves from the aggression of others;
- Empathize with those who have suffered a loss.

Fear – helps us to:

- Prepare better;
- Be more vigilant;
- Make life-saving decisions.

Anger – helps us to:

- Intimidate others to avoid a confrontation;
- Prepare for a confrontation;
- Mobilize to demand our rights;
- Overcome an obstacle.

Panicked	Stressed	Tense	Stunned	M O O D	Surprised	Upbeat	Motivated	Ecstatic
Furious	Frustrated	Nervous	Restless		Hyper	Cheerful	Enthusiastic	Inspired
Apprehensive	Angry	Irritated	Annoyed		Energized	Lively	Focused	Excited
Troubled	Worried	Uneasy	Peeved		Pleasant	Joyful	Hopeful	Blissful
M	O	O	D	M	E	T	E	R
Pessimistic	Concerned	Down	Apathetic	E T E R	Easygoing	Chill	Content	Fulfilled
Grim	Lonely	Sad	Bored		Secure	Thoughtful	Satisfied	Grateful
Miserable	Sullen	Exhausted	Tired		Calm	Complacent	Restful	Balanced
Hopeless	Desolate	Spent	Drained		Sleepy	Relaxed	Tranquil	Serene

Are the names of emotions important?

Yes, because they can help you better identify how you feel. Differentiating between being annoyed and furious can help finding an adequate emotional regulation strategy.

[All known emotions](#)
[Lisa Feldman Barrett PhD](#)

How can we manage our emotions?

- Identifying specific and authentic emotions
- Being curious about their meaning
- Recategorizing how we feel
- Mindful acceptance
- Self-distancing

Focus on Personal Development

- Feeling and expressing gratitude
- Developing optimism;
- Anchoring difficult situations well managed in the past;
- Reflecting on how another person might feel in our situation;
- Perspective taking (how important will the present issue be in 5 years?).

How can we respond skillsfully to the emotions of others?

How can we listen to others so we increase our understanding?

Really focus our attention to:

- to **hear** the words spoken
- to **understand** their meaning, in the speaker's frame of reference
 - Listen with a friendly curiosity (process the information without judging it);
 - Make sure you understand correctly.

How can we improve our active listening skills?

- We clarify **our intention** with which we listen (What we aim at?);
- We are aware of the internal state. Do we have available the needed resources to listen in this way?;
- We get rid of distractions;
- We use various techniques (e.g. paraphrasing to check and show that we understand, asking clarification questions);
- We identify contradictions between verbal and non-verbal language;
- We investigate discrepancies, if any;

How can we improve our active listening skills?

Paraphrasing and reflection

- *Looks like...*
- *Let me see if I understood correctly...*

Information request

- *It's an interesting idea. Tell me more.*
- *Give me an example so I can understand what you meant.*

Clarifying questions

- *When you say that you are not satisfied with our programs, what is it that you do not like?*
- *What do you think about this idea? Does it suit your needs?*

How can we give efficient feedback

Feedback yield good results for the organization and employees when:

- is **contingent** (immediate and behavior-centered)
- is offered **frequently** enough (depending on context and person)
- is **informal**
- is focused both on the **strengths** (appreciative) and on concrete actions in **need of development**
- includes **recommendations** or leads to specific actions to improve things
- is **agreed** by both parties

Collaboration

To get here:

#collaboration & #partnership = working together successfully toward a common vision

We need this:

#communication=sharing needs, ideas, resources, build common knowledge

#trust-building=respect for others work and mutual understanding, communicate honestly and assertively

#meaningful work=what is meaningful for the society, organization, individual

#burst siloes

How to build collaboration?

1. Trust:

be honest; discuss openly; begin with trust

2. Clarify Roles:

review team member roles; clarify goals and responsibilities and; support one another

3. Communicate Openly & Effectively:

work to clear up misunderstandings; seek to understand all perspectives; recognize colleagues; listen actively

4. Appreciate Diversity of Ideas:

evaluate a new idea based on its merits; try to learn as much as you can from others.

5. Balance the Team's Focus:

regularly review and evaluate the effectiveness of team meetings; hold team celebrations for achieving results

Good practices for a collaborative environment

#have Lunch Together (even online). Socialize or/and try to learn from one-another expertise

#organize a Learning Day where employees from all levels of the organization can learn about the latest strategies and initiatives

#share best practices

#present a topic or question and then allow groups of people to collaborate on as many ideas as possible in a short amount of time.

use Ideas Platform where people come together to share, discuss and vote on ideas for specific topics and ideas.

Best practices for virtual collaboration

1. Identify & create protocols for each of your channels
2. Make sure that everyone needed to be seen can be seen
3. Prepare beforehand (test the technology, stick to meeting basics and minimize presentation length)
4. Use icebreakers
5. Involve everyone
6. Find new ways to show and tell online
7. Take time for reflection and feedback
8. Embrace trust and transparency
9. Make the new normal work for you

Good practices Tip sheet

- Meet with colleagues from other departments to understand their work and professional goals and share yours as well
- Organize meetings to discuss common interests and what is meaningful work
- Use online platforms (e.g., Teams from Microsoft, Slack) to share and discuss on common issues
- Have a person responsible for cross-departmental collaboration and communication

Thank you for your attention!

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